

**NIHILISM REPRESENTED BY METEION IN NAOKI YOSHIDA'S
*FINAL FANTASY XIV: ENDWALKER***

THESIS

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FACULTY OF LETTERS
DR. SOETOMO UNIVERSITY
SURABAYA**

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THESIS

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by

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ABSTRACT

Annasai, Axlinabila Annisa. 2024. Nihilism Represented by Meteion in Naoki Yoshida's *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*. English Literature Program, Faculty of Letters, Universitas Dr. Soetomo. Advisor: Dr. Hariyono, S.S., M.Pd.

Keywords: *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*, *Friedrich Nietzsche*, *Naoki Yoshida*, *Nihilism*, *Übermensch*.

This thesis is entitled Nihilism Represented by Meteion in Naoki Yoshida's *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*. The theories of this thesis are nihilism and *Übermensch*, which are based on Friedrich Nietzsche's perspective. The objectives of this study are to identify Meteion's proofs of nihilism, which are recognition of nihilism, systematization of nihilism, and disbelief in the true world, as well as to find out the effects of nihilism in Meteion, which is becoming an *Übermensch*. The thesis writer used descriptive qualitative research within the hermeneutics approach for the analysis in this thesis. The results of this thesis are Meteion's journey through nihilism emphasizes the effort to find meaning in life and the possible sadness that might result from the notion that existence has no value. However, her last moments show a spark of hope and the chance to make one's own meaning in life, which fits with the idea of the *Übermensch*.

ABSTRAK

Annasai, Axlinabila Annisa. 2024. Nihilism Represented by Meteion in Naoki Yoshida's Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker. English Literature Program, Faculty of Letters, Universitas Dr. Soetomo. Advisor: Dr. Hariyono, S.S., M.Pd.

Keywords: Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker, Friedrich Nietzsche, Naoki Yoshida, Nihilism, Übermensch.

Skripsi ini berjudul Nihilism Represented by Meteion in Naoki Yoshida's Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker. Teori yang digunakan dalam skripsi ini adalah nihilisme dan Übermensch, yang berdasarkan perspektif Friedrich Nietzsche. Tujuan dari penelitian ini adalah untuk mengidentifikasi bukti nihilisme Meteion yang meliputi pengakuan terhadap nihilisme, sistematika nihilisme, dan ketidakpercayaan terhadap dunia yang sebenarnya, serta untuk mengetahui efek nihilisme pada Meteion yang menjadi Übermensch. Penulis skripsi menggunakan penelitian kualitatif deskriptif dengan pendekatan hermeneutika untuk analisis dalam tesis ini. Hasil dari penelitian dalam thesis ini adalah perjalanan Meteion melalui nihilisme menekankan upaya untuk menemukan makna dalam hidup dan kemungkinan kesedihan yang mungkin timbul dari gagasan bahwa kehidupan tidak memiliki nilai. Namun, momen terakhirnya menunjukkan percikan harapan dan kesempatan untuk menciptakan makna hidup sendiri, yang sesuai dengan konsep Übermensch.

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Axlinabila Annisa Annasai

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

A. Background of the Study

Human beings' efforts in searching for meaning in life have become a question in the history of human beings. When the topic of the meaning of life comes up, people tend to pose one of three questions: "What are you talking about?", "What is the meaning of life?", and "Is life in fact meaningful?" (Metz, 2021). In order to answer the question of the meaning of life, religions, philosophical thoughts, arts, and ideologies are present for the fulfilment of the gap. In their search for the meaning of existence, humans engage in much internal conversation so that their lives do not become meaningless. Historically, there exists a philosophical school known as nihilism, which posits that life is inherently meaningless.

In the world of literature, different philosophical ideas and beliefs have left deep marks on the stories, characters, and themes that can be found on its pages. Among these philosophies, nihilism stands out as a particularly interesting and, at times, frightening view of the human situation. Nihilism questions the very idea of existence by saying that life has no meaning, purpose, or worth in and of itself. Friedrich Wilhelm Nietzsche, a German philosopher known for his critique of traditional European morality and religion, and his profound influence on 20th- and early 21st-century philosophy, art, literature, and culture, has produced literary works that serve as a powerful vehicle for exploring the concepts of nihilism and the existential crises he conveys.

The relationship between literature and philosophy is, in fact, close (M'Begniga, 2022: 23) because literature explains the values in people's lives. When someone enjoys reading literary works, they can be lost in thinking about the philosophical thoughts of the authors, exploring profound ideas about the human condition, morality, existence, and the intricate tapestry of life's complexities that these works often unravel. These contemplative journeys through literature provide a unique avenue for individuals to delve into the depths of their own beliefs, values, and the interconnectedness of humanity, fostering a deeper understanding of themselves and the world around them. By reading those, readers can get fresh ideas and thoughts that affect their way of thinking. Traditionally, readers enjoy reading literary work in the form of poetry, drama, and prose. The three forms are traditionally regarded as the genres of literary works. However, with the development of technology, literary work can now be formed and enjoyed through electronic ways because of advanced technology.

Electronic literature, also known as digital literature, is literary fiction and poetry created for the computer and the network. Genres of electronic literature, while focused on poetics, have connections to other forms of digital culture, such as network art and computer games (University of Bergen, 2023). Miléna Janoo, from the University Paris 8, states that electronic literature is regarded as a hybrid art form that requires its users to navigate through the literary work through a digital setting, which makes the technological medium an element of exchange (Janoo, 2016). Electronic literature is a form of literary work that is influenced by the characteristics of digital text, emphasizing the unique qualities of new media and

exploring innovative methods of writing inside programmable platforms. E-literature has much in common with new media art and is an excellent example of the creativity that helps readers learn about new media literacy. As literary works, electronic literature can also be formed in electronic or digital poetry, cyberdrama, and Interactive Fiction. Because of this, the thesis paper contains dialogue among the characters, which can be included as cyberdrama.

Among the multitude of electronic literature writers, the thesis writer has chosen to focus on a particular selection. Through this exploration, the thesis writer has gleaned profound philosophical insights from the narratives and dialogues within video games written by various creators, including Naoki Yoshida, the mind behind the renowned *Final Fantasy XIV*. The reason for selecting their works lies in the rich tapestry of philosophical and existential themes interwoven throughout these narratives, which are profoundly relevant to pursuing life's meaning. The thesis writer herself, finds great enjoyment and intellectual stimulation in contemplating philosophical ideas, both within the realm of literary works and during the study of philosophy courses.

The popularity that Naoki Yoshida gained is accepted by many audiences, based on his achievements, which can be proved through his awards as the winner of the Game of the Year and Videogame Excellence in Narrative from SXSW Film Festival 2022. Other awards from the 25th and 26th Annual D.I.C.E Awards from 2021 and 2022 are the winner of the Role-Playing Game of The Year and Online Game of the Year (*Final Fantasy XIV Official Website*, 2023). These awards show that Naoki Yoshida and Natsuko Ishikawa, who created and wrote *Final Fantasy*

XIV: Endwalker, are highly regarded in the gaming world. The story is filled with exciting battles and emotional moments and has been praised as one of the best in the Final Fantasy franchise. The Endwalker expansion was very popular when it was first released that Square Enix, the game's company, suspended its sale.

Naoki Yoshida and Natsuko Ishikawa have created and written many cyberdrama scripts. However, the thesis writer chooses *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker* expansion because it conveys the thought philosophy of nihilism, which the thesis writer wants to study more. After all, nihilism is a thought that searches for meaning in life even though it then views it as empty or meaningless.

This study focuses on the theme of nihilism in the video game *Final Fantasy XIV* through a character called Meteion. Published in 2010, *Final Fantasy XIV* is a Massively Multiplayer Online Role-Playing Game (MMORPG) developed and published by Square Enix. The game has a strong emphasis on storytelling, with a main scenario that progresses through major patches and expansions. *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker* is the fourth expansion pack released in 2021 with a hundred and eight quests in total (Final Fantasy XIV Online Wiki, 2023). As the name suggests, an expansion pack adds new features to a role-playing game, board game, video game, collectible card game, or small wargame that already exists. These add-ons usually make games that have already been launched better by adding new levels, weapons, items, characters, adventures, or storylines. In the Endwalker expansion, players continue the story as they face a new threat to the world. To prevent the destruction of reality, they travel beyond Eorzea to the moon, encountering new allies and enemies and making difficult choices. Therefore, the thesis writer relates

and focuses this research between Naoki Yoshida and Natsuko Ishikawa's *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker* and nihilism thoughts that Friedrich Nietzsche proposes.

Nihilism, the belief that life has no inherent meaning or value, is important to study because it is relevant in the modern world, where society's values and beliefs constantly evolve. This philosophy, which emerged in 19th-century, has various forms, including existential, cosmic, and moral nihilism, each with its own implications on individual and collective behavior (Quadri, 2022: 1). Nihilism can be described as one of the greatest crises of human societies around the world. Daniel L. Leonard from The Harvard Crimson believed that many Harvard students (and young people more broadly) are already nihilists and also said that the upcoming generation could be the most nihilistic in history. The effect of nihilism on the culture and values of our modern-day society has been widespread (Quadri, 2022: 3). As society continues to evolve, it will be interesting to see how the philosophy of nihilism adapts and changes along with it.

In the realm of popular culture, video games have grown in popularity and importance as a form of entertainment and storytelling. *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*, in particular, has garnered critical acclaim for its narrative structure, character development, and exploration of complex philosophical concepts, which makes Meteion closely linked to the theme of nihilism in the game. Studying how Meteion's lore explores nihilism can provide insights into how popular culture addresses philosophical concepts and what it means for society's understanding of these issues.

The results of this study provide a deeper understanding of how the lore of Meteion faces nihilism in *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*. By examining the narrative structure and character development, readers can gain insights into how popular culture addresses complex philosophical concepts and what it means for society's understanding of these issues. This study may also contribute to a broader discourse on the role of entertainment media in shaping cultural values and attitudes, especially through the portrayal of nihilism in popular video games.

B. Statements of the Problem

Based on the explanation from the background of the study, the thesis writer arranges questions to be examined in more detail as follow:

1. What are the proofs of nihilism in Naoki Yoshida's *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker* through Meteion?
2. What are the effects of Meteion's nihilism in Naoki Yoshida's *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*?

C. Scope and Limitation of the Study

The scope of the study is literally study on Nihilism Represented by Meteion in Naoki Yoshida's *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*. It is limited to analyzing how the game portrays nihilism through the lore of the character called Meteion. The

thesis writer focuses on exploring the proofs of nihilism through Meteion and the effects of Meteion's nihilism. From a hundred and eight quests of Endwalker expansion in total (Final Fantasy XIV Online Wiki, 2023), the thesis writer uses eleven quests out of nineteen that involve Meteion for the data. The study primarily uses qualitative research methods and information from the game, such as dialogue and cutscenes, as the primary data source.

D. Objectives of the Study

Based on the statements of the problem, the thesis writer formulates about the objectives of the study in this thesis as follows:

1. To investigate the proofs of nihilism in Naoki Yoshida's *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker* through Meteion.
2. To find out the effects of nihilism in *Naoki Yoshida's Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker* through Meteion.

E. Significances of the Study

1. Theoretical

By reading this thesis, the readers are expected to start to use electronic literature as a source of data and to engage more closely with great thinkers such as Nietzsche and Sartre. Therefore, the readers can learn that electronic literary works

do not always convey messages with light or populist themes. On the contrary, Naoki Yoshida's works deliver deep philosophical thoughts like nihilism.

The significance of the theoretical study in this thesis entitled *Nihilism Represented by Meteion in Naoki Yoshida's Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker* lies in its contribution to the development of literary theory. The study's findings can improve the thesis writer's understanding of how literary works can resolve complex philosophical topics like nihilism. Additionally, it could provide the readers with new perspectives on judging video games as literary works. This study may improve the readers' awareness of the literary potential of video games and how they can be utilized to examine intricate philosophical issues by thoroughly analyzing how nihilism is represented in Naoki Yoshida's *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker* through Meteion.

2. Practical

By reading this thesis, the readers can understand that even though they cannot find the meaning of life in this world, they should continue their life through their choices and actions.

For the game industry and beyond, this thesis has important practical effects. This research improves player experiences, directs game development, and fosters broader dialogues about profound philosophical ideas in popular culture by examining how the game portrays nihilism. Understanding how nihilism is represented in a well-known MMORPG like *Final Fantasy XIV* deepens players'

immersion in the game and leads to a greater comprehension of how video games may convey complicated ideas and encourage critical thinking. This approach also encourages conversations about how nihilism affects people's views, values, and mental health, bridging the gap between gaming and more significant societal considerations.

F. Keys to Specific Terms

The thesis writer explains the key terms to make it easier for readers.

1. Nihilism is the belief that all values are baseless and that nothing can be known or communicated (Pratt, 2023).
2. *Übermensch* from Nietzsche's writings is a call for personal self-discovery and self-overcoming rather than a call for superior human "race." (Maden, 2022).
3. Final Fantasy XIV is a Massively Multiplayer Online Role-Playing Game (MMORPG) developed and published by Square Enix in 2010. Final Fantasy XIV released the fourth expansion pack called "Endwalker" on December 7, 2021.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW TO RELATED LITERATURE

A. Previous Studies

The thesis writer finds that there are various studies about Nihilism and Final Fantasy XIV in order to help this study. The writers are (1) Elisabeth Koyfman from City University of New York, (2) Muhammad Naufal Abiyyu from Padang State University, (3) Destrian Mahendra from University of Technology Yogyakarta, (4) Satrio Jagad from Diponegoro University, and (5) Leo Bunyea from Worcester Polytechnic Institute.

The first previous study is a thesis entitled *The Search for Existential Meaning: Tracing Leo Tolstoy's Nihilism Through his Later Works* (Koyfman, 2023), written by Elisabeth Koyfman in 2023. Koyfman analyzed Leo Tolstoy's works through an existential and ethical nihilistic perspective. Koyfman's thesis said that Tolstoy's later works were an explosive rejection of meaningless conventions that he had been a part of, like materialistic consumption, corrupt religious practices, and the literary genre of fiction itself. As a result of Koyfman's writing, it can be said that Tolstoy's nihilism was a symptom of the society he lived in and that his writing served as an essential platform for criticism of the common ideals of that society. Tolstoy had a hard time finding a clear meaning in life in his lifetime and grew increasingly nihilistic, feeling more and more hopeless about society. Tolstoy is not in line with the idea that happiness and meaning in life come from achieving fame, marriage, and wealth. Instead, he made his own meaning and

encouraged his readers to do the same. The similarity between Koyfman's thesis and this thesis is that Tolstoy and Meteion had difficulty finding meaning in life. Both portrayals of nihilism explore the concept and its implications on individuals and society, with characters struggling with the meaning of life and grappling with nihilistic ideas. However, in the context in which Final Fantasy is set in a fictional universe while Leo Tolstoy is a real-life author, the characters' responses in which Meteion embraces destructive nihilism. At the same time, Tolstoy rejects meaningless and encourages readers to create their own meaning, and medium of expression which Final Fantasy is a digital medium. Koyfman is based on written works that differ between the two portrayals.

The second previous study was written by Muhammad Naufal Abiyyu from State Padang University, named *Escaping from Existential Nihilism in Chuck Palahniuk's Fight Club (1996)* (Abiyyu & Anwar, 2023). This research delved into Chuck Palahniuk's 1996 novel *Fight Club*, which explored the consequences of pursuing perfection to the point of self-destruction and escaping from despair. These issues manifest in the protagonist's life, referred to as The Narrator (Unnamed). The study poses two research questions: (1). What are the causes of existential nihilism that exist in the narrator's life? (2). How does the narrator escape existential nihilism to make his life meaningful?

Abiyyu focuses on both Friedrich Nietzsche's existential nihilism theory and Sigmund Freud's psychoanalysis theory. Utilizing psychoanalysis as the analytical method, it delves into The Narrator's struggle with destructive habits and his quest for perfection, which initially leads to a sense of despair and passive

nihilism. However, as the story progresses, he becomes more actively engaged in his pursuit of meaning, ultimately rejecting his fixation on perfection. The thesis argues that the novel serves as a parable for existential nihilism, illustrating The Narrator's routines and beliefs mirroring his perception of life's meaninglessness. As a result, the narrator has a belief that can help him overcome existential nihilism and find meaning and value in his life. There are several similarities between Abiyyu's writings and this thesis. Both writings explore themes of nihilism with a focus on the destructive consequences, and also examine the characters' journeys from despair towards finding the meaning and value in life. However, there are also differences. While Abiyyu's study uses Freud's psychoanalysis, this thesis focuses more on Nietzsche's nihilism theory as it pertains to *Meteion*. Furthermore, the two works' contexts are different; Abiyyu's is based on a novel, while this thesis is based on a video game narrative, which may involve different narrative and interactive elements.

The third previous study was written by Destrian Mahendra from the University of Technology Yogyakarta in 2021, called *The Idea of Nihilism Reflected by Character Gaear in Fargo (1996) Movie Directed by Joel and Ethan Coen* (Mahendra, 2021). This study examines the portrayal of nihilism through the character Gaear in the film "Fargo" (1996). It discusses the Coen brothers' perspective on portraying Gaear as a nihilist to better comprehend why he might be deemed one. Mahendra found that Gaear's personality is abnormal. Mahendra and the thesis writer both studies focus on the theme of nihilism, use a specific character, and are based on narrative works. However, different from Mahendra, the thesis

writer studies a normal character, Meteion, that being normal in a world without meaning is not easy. While the thesis presents Meteion as a normal character struggling with nihilism, it could further explore how Meteion's struggle reflects the broader human struggle with existential despair and the search for meaning in a seemingly meaningless world.

The fourth previous study is a thesis named *Moral Nihilism as Reflected by Joker in the Dark Knight Movie* (Jagad, 2017), written by Satrio Jagad from Diponegoro University in 2017. This thesis focuses on the character of the Joker as a moral nihilist in the film *The Dark Knight*. This study aims to analyze the character of Joker from the movie as he acts immorally and believes in nothing. The thesis writer applies Friedrich Nietzsche's and Donald Crosby's theories of nihilism and moral nihilism, which are utilized within the thesis to examine the issue. The results of this study show that the Joker's character can be interpreted as a representation of nihilism, especially moral nihilism. The Joker serves as an example of Friedrich Nietzsche's nihilism theory in the film, where he shows the idea that nothing has any meaning to him and is, therefore, reduced to nothingness, no matter what it may be. Joker has no intention of seeking any specific things like money, fame, or respect. Despite this, he does not care about his actions because nothing is right or wrong. As it turns out, Joker also encounters the three types of moral nihilism, in which he rejects any value in this world. Both Jagad and the thesis writer use Nietzsche's nihilism theory. While both studies explore the theme of nihilism through popular media characters, they differ in the characters' responses to nihilism. The Joker embraces nihilism and acts without regard for

morality, while Meteion initially embraces nihilism but ultimately rejects it in favor of hope for a future answer.

The last previous study is a thesis called *Using Research Driven Design to Reimagine Systems of Gender in Final Fantasy XIV* (Bunyea, 2020) by Leo Bunyea from Worcester Polytechnic Institute in 2020. This research focuses primarily on gender modeling in avatar creation tools found in MMORPG Final Fantasy XIV. This study highlights a significant issue related to avatar-creation tools used in gaming. These tools often limit the range of body types and identities that players can represent within the game world. To address this problem, the research follows Brenda Laurel's research-driven design approach and applies it to Final Fantasy XIV's existing system. They create a paper prototype and actively involve feedback from a group of queer players who self-identify as such. The insights gained from these players and the adjustments made to the prototype led to a set of recommendations for those who design such tools. In the end, the study identifies three key improvements that greatly benefit queer players: including pronoun identification, recognizing gender identity, and separating these aspects from a character's physical appearance. Implementing these suggestions in design can contribute to more inclusive gaming environments that support a wide range of queer identities.

The outcomes of this study hold great importance because they originate from a minority voice within the gaming community. The playtesting results and the revisions made to the prototype offer a clear set of guidelines and suggestions for enhancing the inclusivity of avatar creation systems concerning gender

representation. Additionally, the initial survey data, when considered alongside the interview transcript, reveal an interesting inconsistency in how aware queer individuals are of their own unique requirements.

Bunyea's thesis investigates gender portrayal in Final Fantasy XIV's avatar creation tools, with a focus on improving inclusivity for queer identities. It takes a research-driven approach to design and actively engages the queer gaming community. While both theses share a common focus on Final Fantasy XIV, both differ significantly in research focus, methodology, and outcomes. Bunyea's study is more design-oriented and aims to improve the game's inclusivity, while this thesis is more philosophical, aiming to understand the game's narrative and theme.

B. Theoretical Background

B.1. Nihilism

The word "nihilism" is derived from the Latin nihil, which means "nothing" and "that which does not exist." It can be found in the verb "annihilate," meaning to destroy and entirely reduce to nothing. A true nihilist would believe in nothing, have no loyalties, and have no purpose other than, perhaps, an impulse to destroy (Pratt, 2023). Nihilism has taken on a variety of stances, such as the denial of existence, meaninglessness, or the futility of life, human ideals, knowledge, or a particular set of entities. Nihilists think that existence is ultimately meaningless and that all ethical beliefs are false. Nihilists may experience despair and believe there is no point in their existence. Nihilism can promote irresponsible and harmful

behavior and decrease the value of human life. Nihilism and existentialism are frequently mistaken for one another, and numerous philosophers have asserted that the two schools of thought are either comparable or mutually exclusive. The fact that Friedrich Nietzsche has significantly influenced both ideas is largely to blame for this misconception. Therefore, the two philosophies are linked together.

According to Nietzsche, nihilism means that the highest values devalue themselves. Nihilism, then, is the recognition of the long waste of strength, the agony of the “in vain,” insecurity, the lack of any opportunity to recover and to regain composure— being ashamed in front of oneself, as if one had deceived oneself all too long (Nietzsche, 1968: 12). Nietzsche’s nihilistic thinking cannot be separated from the view that God is dead. The death of God is essential in nihilism because, in European philosophical thought, God is the cause of all causes, as Aristotle’s view is *causa prima*. With the death of God, Nietzsche argues that morality and the meaning of life-based on divinity are no longer valid. Thus, human existence on earth is not caused by God but occurs without the person’s will as a causal link to the material world. According to Nietzsche, the old moral and existential frameworks based on divinity are no longer valid after the Death of God. As a result, humans are ‘thrown’ into a universe where God does not create their existence but occurs without the person’s desire as a causal link to the material world.

Human beings, according to Heidegger, are ‘thrown’ into the world, which means that they find themselves in a world that they did not choose, and this reality pre-exists and outlasts them. It is like being thrown into the world without choosing

the starting point of a human being's life or their final destination. "This 'throw' is not something that we have done but something that we find done to us; we are not the agents but the recipients, those affected by it; it is something that has 'already' happened in some sense, something we did not choose and could not choose. A throw suggests a momentum to our lives that we did not engender and perhaps are unable to stop" (Cowles, 2017: 6). This concept underscores the passive nature of existence, as individuals are not the initiators but rather the recipients of this 'throw' into existence. It is something that has already occurred, emphasizing the unchosen and uncontrollable aspects of life.

Sartre espoused the view that life is meaningless but urged readers nonetheless to make a free choice that would give people lives meaning and responsibility (O'Brien, 2023). All human behavior can thus be described as a secondary particularization of a fundamental project which expresses the subject's free choice, and conditions the intelligibility of their actions (Reynolds, 2022). Sartre argues that in order to analyze a human subject and comprehend the meaning that guides their existence as a whole, humans must understand the particular form of unity that underlies their diverse behaviors and attitudes. To fight against nihilism, we must understand that life is not futile and meaningless. As explained by Jean-Paul Sartre, humans create their own meaning and essence through their choices throughout their lives. That being said, we may fight against nihilism by embracing our freedom, giving our lives value, refusing to believe in anything beyond reality, and appreciating life.

Nihilism is a complicated philosophical theory that deals with basic questions about the meaning and purpose of life, the nature of existence, and the human condition, making it an essential topic for study. Readers can learn more about these problems and the various ways that people have tried to address them throughout history by studying nihilism. Nihilism can impact how humans perceive the world, their role in it, and their interactions with other people. This has real-world ramifications for how people live their lives. Nihilism can help people better understand these problems and gain a more complex understanding of the universe by challenging anthropocentric views, which encourages individuals to see that their existence is not inherently meaningful or purposeful, but rather that value, meaning, and purpose are assigned by a subject upon an object, and that these are not inherent in the objects themselves. Nietzsche stated that “If ye believed more in life, then would ye devote yourselves less to the momentary” (Common, 2006: 46). To give life a meaning: that has been the grand endeavor of all who have preached ‘truth’; it is something you *create*, it is the expression of a particular kind of life and being which has, in you, ventured to assert itself (Nietzsche, 1974: 17). There are three states of nihilism, according to Nietzsche;

Table 1. The Indicators of Nihilism

Recognition of Nihilism	Systematization of Nihilism	Disbelief in True World
Nihilism occurs as a psychological state when individuals constantly seek meaning in events and find none. This disappointment comes from the realization that	When one has proposed a totality, a systematization, or even any organization in all events and beneath all circumstances, and when a soul that longs for	Nihilism has a third and final manifestation as a psychological condition. Given these two realizations—that becoming has no purpose and that beneath all

<p>the important reasons they thought existed in life, such as love, happiness, or even annihilation, do not seem as meaningful as they once thought. Nihilism happens when the pursuit of any big goal in life, whether specific or universal, leads to profound disappointment when one realizes that all previous ideas about life's goals are inadequate. This happens when a person starts feeling that humans are not important in how the world changes and grows, resulting in a sense of purposelessness and a lack of accomplishment, leading to emotions of despair and futility. (Nietzsche, 1968: 12).</p> <p>The thesis writer investigates that it means the awareness that traditional values, beliefs, and meaning systems (such as Christianity) are untrue and that life, existence, and the world are inherently devoid of objective meaning, purpose, truth, or essential value.</p>	<p>admiration and reverence has become enmeshed in the notion of some ultimate form of domination and rule (if the soul is that of a logician, complete consistency and real dialectic are more than enough to reconcile it to everything), nihilism as a psychological state is reached (Nietzsche, 1968: 12).</p> <p>The thesis writer implies from the statement above that human often seek to make sense of the world by believing in a higher power or religion. This belief is the source of our sense of value. When human learn that there is no higher power or religion, they lose faith in their own value and fall into nihilism, which is the belief that life has no inherent meaning or value.</p>	<p>becoming, there is no great unity in which the person could fully immerse himself in something of ultimate value—there is still a way out: one can declare this entire world of becoming to be a lie and create a real world that exists outside of it (Nietzsche, 1968: 13).</p> <p>The thesis writer understands from the quotation above means that life is just a series of changes without any ultimate goal or larger meaning. When humans realize this, they might be tempted to invent a “true world” of meaning. However, when they realize that this “true world” is just a made-up place, they reach the final stage of nihilism. This stage involves accepting the reality of change as the only reality, even though this reality is difficult to endure because it lacks inherent meaning or purpose. Therefore, the thesis writer can highlight that the characteristics of nihilism are recognition of nihilism, systematization of nihilism, and disbelief in the true world.</p>
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The idea of nihilism can be applied to this tale of cyberdrama since the Meteia, which is Meteion and her sisters, decided to put an end to all life in the universe as a kindness because they believe that life is misery. This is consistent with the concept of nihilism, which is the rejection of moral and religious values and the ensuing conviction that existence has no purpose. The Endsinger, which is a monster from Meteion and her sisters fused together, claim that hopelessness would always triumph over optimism can alternatively be seen as nihilism.

B.2. *Übermensch*

In Friedrich Nietzsche's *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*, the idea of the *Übermensch* (Overman or Superhuman or Superman) is presented as a standard that humanity should aspire to. The *Übermensch* is not a demand for a superior human race, but rather for personal self-discovery and self-overcoming. It is about being the best version of oneself, overcoming petty 'man' desires, and moving beyond illusions to live and enjoy the here and now of life on Earth. In this form, we create our own values, overcome any problems or issues we may encounter, and most importantly, master ourselves (Hauk, 2022). The concept of the *Übermensch*, or "overman," is a challenge to humanity to rise above the emptiness left by the absence of divine meaning. It encourages individuals to create their own purpose and strive for something beyond themselves. This idea comes from a world that does not seem to have any value on its own, and it encourages people to keep getting better. It is a call to action for mankind to overcome the despair of nihilism and develop new ideals.

For Nietzsche, the *Übermensch* is a being who is able to completely affirm life: someone who says ‘yes’ to everything that comes their way; a being who is able to be their own determiner of value; sculpt their characteristics and circumstances into a beautiful, empowered, ecstatic whole; and fulfill their ultimate potential to become who they truly are (Maden, 2022). Nietzsche (2006: 30) wrote in his book, “A new pride taught me mine ego, and that teach I unto men: no longer to thrust one’s head into the sand of celestial things, but to carry it freely, a terrestrial head, which giveth meaning to the earth!”. The thesis writer implies that someone can discover meaning and purpose in life by accepting his worldly life and experiences. This is an important part of Nietzsche’s concept of the *Übermensch*, who establishes his own values and gives meaning to life on Earth rather than looking for it in an otherworldly realm or divine being. Nietzsche viewed the *Übermensch* as a perfect model that people can continuously aim for, but never completely achieve. The *Übermensch* is constantly growing and changing, never reaching a final or complete state.

Übermensch overcame nihilism by establishing new values, “But it is meant to be a possibility which men of the present could realize with all their spiritual and physical energies, provided they adopted the new values.” (Nietzsche, 2006: xi). This refers to Nietzsche’s concept of the *Übermensch*, or Overman, which he portrays as a goal for humanity to aspire for. The quotation implies that the realization of the *Übermensch*—a figure who embodies strength, vitality, and the creation of new values—is a possibility within the reach of modern individuals,

provided they are willing to devote their full spiritual and physical energies to the adoption of these new, life-affirming values.

Nietzsche employed the metaphor of a hammer in his work “Twilight of the Idols” to depict the process of demolishing old values and forging new ones. “Nietzsche picks up a hammer to sound out the old philosophical idols. Finding them to be hollow, he takes a firm grip to flatten and smash, claw and bludgeon. But a hammer can also be a fairly useful tool for building new structures” (B-Gray, 2023). The thesis writer understand that a hammer serves dual purposes - it can both demolish and build. This duality mirrors Nietzsche’s philosophical stance, which is not solely about deconstruction, but also about creation. Nietzsche is recognized for his critique and dismantling of antiquated ideas, but he also endeavored to establish fresh concepts in their stead. His goal was to supplant obsolete standards and conventions with philosophies that were more affirming of life, resilient, and genuine.

Table 2. The Indicators of *Übermensch*

Overcoming Nihilism	Creating New Values	The Will to Power
Nietzsche challenges people to rise beyond their current situations and become something greater by establishing the <i>Übermensch</i> as the ideal for humanity. This involves a process of self-discovery and self-overcoming.	Nietzsche’s <i>Übermensch</i> is someone who creates their own values and meaning, which can be unique to each individual.	Nietzsche’s concept of the will to power is about the desire to show one’s power and make a unique life path. This desire is not just about controlling others, but more about controlling oneself and creating personal values and meanings.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHOD

A. Research Design

The research design for this study is a descriptive qualitative approach, which aims to address the research questions by analyzing and interpreting the textual data available in the form of dialogue and cutscenes that depict Nihilism in Naoki Yoshida's *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker* through Meteion. The descriptive qualitative research is used within hermeneutics approach. Dialogue with the text is a process that occurs continually in the course of time (Gadamer in Abshor, 2010: 69). The qualitative approach is chosen because it focuses on capturing the meaning and experiences of Meteion's dialogue with other characters in order to discover how they contribute to the game's narrative exploration of nihilism.

By using hermeneutics, the exploration of nihilism can be identified. In hermeneutics, the conditions Gadamer expands upon can all be applied in the reflective actions of an interpreter's experience with the spoken word and (transcribed) written language (Regan, 2012: 289). Gadamer develops the three different levels of reading to clarify the broader structure of hermeneutics. The first reading is an aesthetically perceptive reading, the second is an exegetical reading, and the third is a historical reading. The three successive readings of a text are compared with the movements of comprehension, interpretation, and application (Parris, 1999: 165).

Gadamer’s hermeneutics ascribes comprehension as a communicative event that has its basic characteristic on the hermeneutical conversation (Gadamer in Abshor, 2010: 68). By using this approach, researchers can get indicators about the phenomenon in this study. Denzin and Lincoln claim that qualitative research involves an interpretive and naturalistic approach: “This means that qualitative researchers study things in their natural settings, attempting to make sense of, or to interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them” (2000: 3).

Figure 1. A Hermeneutics Framework for the literature review process

Detailed subject exploration is prioritized over a quantitative or numerical approach in the research design. Based on the provided example, this research design only examines Meteion’s path and how nihilism is portrayed in Meteion.

Meteion, as the character that is studied in this research, would be analyzed from Meteion’s dialogues, Hermes’ dialogues as her creator, and interactions with other characters.

B. Source of Data and Data

The main source of data is *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker expansion*. The director of this game is Naoki Yoshida, and the writer is Natsuko Ishikawa, who works under Yoshida. Since this thesis counts as cyberdrama, therefore, the thesis writer uses drama structures. The drama structures itself contains speech and acts. The speech in this thesis will be shown as dialogues, and the acts will be shown as quests. Scenes in plays and movies are carefully made to bring out feelings and guide the audience through the story, just like quests and levels in the game *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker* are created to draw players into the game's setting, people, and story. Each quest or level acts like a small story within the bigger story, adding details, challenges, and growth for the characters.

In the Endwalker expansion, there are a hundred and eight quests in total. Meanwhile, there are eleven out of eighteen quests that the thesis writer uses, where Meteion is involved in the game's narrative and her interaction of other characters which indicates nihilism.

The data and all the information are gained from the dialogues and the quests and levels provided by the game through Meteion, Hermes as Meteion's creator, and interaction with other characters in the Endwalker expansion quests as the main data. Social media such as [reddit.com](https://www.reddit.com), [youtube.com](https://www.youtube.com), and [forum.square-enix.com](https://www.forum.square-enix.com) for other people's opinions about Meteion are used to support the main data.

C. Techniques of Data Collection

According to Creswell (2014: 438), The data collection steps include setting the boundaries for the study, collecting information through unstructured or semi-structured observations and interviews, documents, and visual materials, as well as establishing the protocol for recording information.

To collect the data needed, the thesis writer used audiovisual digital materials to collect transcripts of all dialogues in the game. Here are the full explanations by the thesis writer:

**QUALITATIVE DATA COLLECTION
BY CRESWELL (2014)**

DATA COLLECTION TYPE	OPTIONS WITHIN THE TYPES	ADVANTAGE OF THE TYPE	LIMITATION OF THE TYPES
AUDIOVISUAL DIGITAL MATERIALS	1. PHOTOGRAPHS 2. VIDEOTAPES 3. ART OBJECTS 4. COMPUTER MESSAGES 5. SOUNDS 6. FILM	1. MAY BE AN UNOBTUSIVE METHOD OF COLLECTING DATA. 2. PROVIDES AN OPPORTUNITY FOR PARTICIPANTS TO DIRECTLY SHARE THEIR REALITY. 3. IT IS CREATIVE IN THAT IT CAPTURES ATTENTION.	1. MAYBE DIFFICULT TO INTERPRET. 2. MAY NOT BE ACCESSIBLE PUBLICLY OR PRIVATELY 3. THE PRESENCE OF AN OBSERVER (E.G., PHOTOGRAPHER) MAY BE DESTRUCTIVE AND AFFECT RESPONSES.

Figure 2. One of the Qualitative Data Collection by Creswell (2014: 242)

Creswell (2014: 240) stated that a final category of qualitative data consists of qualitative audio and visual materials. This data may take the form of photographs, art objects, videotapes, website main pages, e-mails, text messages, social media text, or any forms of sound. Include creative data collection procedures that fall under the category of visual ethnography and which might include living stories, metaphorical visual narratives, and digital archives.

One of the visual materials is computer messages, which include a visual narrative from *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*. This is intended to collect data related to this study. The thesis writer explained the steps to collect the data, as shown below:

1. The thesis writer played the Final Fantasy XIV Endwalker expansion game;
2. The thesis writer completed all storylines and quests in the Endwalker expansion;
3. The thesis writer searches for the lore of Meteion according to the Endwalker expansion;
4. The thesis writer categorized the dialogues that can be analyzed according to the theory and perspective in the previous chapter.

D. Techniques of Data Analysis

There are six steps of data analysis, according to Creswell (2014: 247-249) used by the thesis writer:

1. Organize and prepare the data for analysis;
2. Read through all the data;
3. Start coding all of the data;
4. Use the coding process to generate a description of the setting or people as well as categories or themes for analysis;

5. Advance how the description and themes will be represented in the qualitative narrative;
6. A final step in data analysis involves making an interpretation in qualitative research of the findings or results.

Figure 3. Data Analysis in Qualitative Research by Creswell

Based on the steps stated above, the thesis writer summarizes step by step to analyze the source of data as follows:

In the first step, the thesis writer prepares the data, such as the dialogues and cutscenes in the game. Then, the thesis writer read and watched the dialogues and cutscenes in *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker* and kept the research questions in mind while carefully reading the data, looking for the indicator of nihilism in the dialogue through Meteion.

The next step is categorizing the data. The thesis writer classified the dialogues for each quest where Meteion indicates nihilism. This implies that the thesis writer examined the gathered dialogues and arrange them according to the research questions. In this case, the thesis writer categorized the conversations for each quest in which Meteion show proofs of nihilism and interactions with other characters in Table 5 and the effects of nihilism in Table 6. This is an important step since it makes the data easier to organize and evaluate.

Third, the thesis writer analyzed the previous gathered data to determine the research's findings. After examining the data, the thesis writer would like to decide whether or not it can be used to solve the research questions. The thesis writer might need to gather more information or rewrite the study questions if the data is insufficient.

The fourth step involves identifying the proofs of nihilism and the effects of nihilism. The analysis will be based on the nihilism theory and *Übermensch* by the perspective of Friedrich Nietzsche which was mentioned in this thesis' previous chapter as shown in Table 5 and Table 6. This step is important because it helps to understand the underlying reasons for Meteion's nihilistic views.

Lastly, the thesis writer would like to interpret the meaning of the quotation. After analyzing the data, the thesis writer identified key themes and patterns. Based on this theme, the thesis writer analyzed the meaning of the quotation and come to conclusions regarding the research questions.

CHAPTER IV

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

The thesis writer explores Naoki Yoshida's *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker* through Meteion to discover the nihilism portrayed in the game by examining Meteion's dialogues and interactions with other characters. The analysis focuses on identifying Meteion's nihilism using the Nihilism theory of Friedrich Nietzsche. This chapter describes the result of coding the dialogues to show the Nihilism Represented by Meteion in Naoki Yoshida's *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*.

A. Proofs of Nihilism in *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*

1. Results

As mentioned in chapter two that there are three states that Meteion can be identified to undergo nihilistic point of view, which are the recognition of nihilism, systematization of nihilism, and disbelief in true world. The judgment that Meteion has the three states of nihilism is studied based on the Meteion's dialogues, Hermes as Meteion's creator's dialogues, and Meteion's conversations with the player and other characters.

Table 3. The Proofs of nihilism and its Indicators in Meteion's dialogues and her conversations with other characters in *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*

Indicator	Data No.	Quotation
	1.	Meteion: "This is my power. I can read the emotions of those around me, and project my emotions to others"

Recognition of Nihilism		in return.” (Quest: Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86))
	2.	Meteion: “I am not actually speaking to you in your mind. Rather, you are converting my emotions into words and intention—a process performed subconsciously by intelligent life-forms.” (Quest: Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86))
	3.	Meteion: “This ability is vital to my mission, for it allows me to interact with intelligent beings even should they communicate via unknown languages or other nonverbal means.” (Quest: Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86))
	4.	Meteion: “Yet though I struggle to express myself in this fashion, Hermes wants me to speak as much as possible, for everyone has thoughts and feelings that they may wish to hide...” (Quest: Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86))
	5.	Meteion: “I harbor an affection for you. One that is difficult to define.” (Quest: Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86))
	6.	Meteion: “Aside from the fact that you share common traits with us, your thoughts are complex. Prismatic. They draw me in, and leave me wanting to know more.” (Quest: Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86))
	7.	Meteion: “It’s heavy... Hermes’ pain...” (Quest: Aether to Aether (Level 86))
	9.	Meteion: “Ooh, Elpis flowers! They’re here too! Hermes likes and dislikes them. At the same time.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	10.	Meteion: “Like me, they’re entelechies. Like me, they feel his pain and turn dark...” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	11.	Meteion: “That’s only for Hermes, though. For others, they’re always white and bright.” (Quest: Aether to Aether (Level 86))
	12.	Meteion: “Truly!?! The flower was dark in your home!?” (Quest: Aether to Aether (Level 86))

	13.	Meteion: “Then...do you have it too? A dark emotion?” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	14.	Player: “I’ve known the pain and sorrow of loss.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	15.	Meteion: “I see...” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	16.	Meteion: “Hermes has known the same. The feeling that a part of you is gone. Again and again. But no one notices...” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	17.	Meteion: “Please, (player). Won’t you lend it to me? Your pain and sorrow...” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	18.	Meteion: “He (Hermes) has been in a dark place. Since before he created me. He needs to know that he isn’t there alone. That others are sad too.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	19.	Meteion: “You’re not the only one, Hermes. Others feel sad too. You’re not alone.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	21.	Hermes: “And yet, in carrying out my duties here, there are times when I am plagued by doubt.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	27.	Hermes: “Pain and suffering... Confusion and despair... Writ plain in the eyes of those poor creatures.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	28.	Hermes: “Yet no one sees. We turn a blind eye and carry on in blissful ignorance. Naught amiss, and always—always the blossoms shine pure and white.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	51.	Meteion: “Executing scheduled task. Suspending individual self and connecting to shared consciousness.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))
	52.	Meteion: “So scared... so lonely... The pain... it’s too much...” (Quest: Words Without Sound (Level 87))

53.	Meteion: “Why...why...why do we..they..hurt...hurt...hate...HATE!” (Quest: Words Without Sound (Level 87))
54.	Meteion: “This is wrong! All wrong!” (Quest: Words Without Sound (Level 87))
55.	Meteion: “Stay away. Please. This is wrong. My mistake. So please...” (Quest: Words Without Sound (Level 87))
56.	Meteion: “Our survey is complete. We shall now report our findings.” (Quest: Words Without Sound (Level 87))
57.	Meteion: “All units safely arrived at their respective destinations. Seeking answers to Hermes’s question, we attempted to make contact with the intelligent denizens of each star.” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))
58.	Hena (Meteion’s Sister): “Traces of civilization found—structures believed to have served as domiciles. No extant life-forms detected.” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))
59.	Dyo (Meteion’s Sister): “Ruined remnants of buildings scattered across star, surface of which is encased in ice. Presence of life could not be verified.” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))
60.	Tria (Meteion’s Sister): “Evidence of large population centers akin to cities recovered. No extant life-forms found—only their lingering essence.” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))
61.	Tessera (Meteion’s Sister): “Edifices surmised to be abandoned residences found. No extant life-forms detected. Deadly plague or extreme environmental degradation likely to have led to mass extinction.” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))
62.	Hermes: “They are all...dead?” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))
63.	Emet-Selch: “Remind me, Hermes. What exactly was the question you entrusted to Meteion?” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

	65.	Emet-Selch: “Did you consider what may happen if the premise of the question is flawed?” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))
	66.	Emet-Selch: “To be able to answer it, one must be living—and desire to continue doing so.” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))
	67.	Emet-Selch: “But if Meteion finds no living beings in the course of her journey...” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))
	68.	Emet-Selch: “Or none who desire to live, what then?” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))
	69.	Emet-Selch: “What answers would she derive from their silence?” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))
	70.	Deka-pente (Meteion’s Sister): “Local civilization once flourished under auspices of higher power. Said power later laid waste to civilization in fit of rage.” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))
Systematization of Nihilism	8.	Hermes: “We have a duty to the star, this I know. But it doesn’t mean we don’t also have a responsibility to the lives we bring into existence here.” (Quest: Aether to Aether (Level 86))
	20.	Hermes: “I do not think it wrong that we live for the star. That we strive to make it a better place.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	22.	Hermes: “Death is the privilege of those who have fulfilled their purpose. A choice they embrace of their own free will. And when they depart, it is always beautiful.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	23.	Hermes: “Some scarcely born into the world. Afforded a handful of breaths before life and potential are abruptly extinguished.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	24.	Hermes: “We make an effort to spare them the pain. But they sense what awaits. Rage in anguish and cower in fear...and it is not beautiful.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

	25.	Hermes: “Yet no one cares. No one.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)) (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	26.	Hermes: “So fixated are we upon the duty that we do not pause to question the method.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	29.	Hermes: “A contradiction so blatant I could scream. Want to scream. How can you all accept this...aberration!?” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	30.	Hermes: “Then I wonder...am I the aberration for thinking thus? And I am filled with dread...” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	31.	Hermes: “But now I know I’m not alone. Not the only one for whom the flowers weep.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	32.	Hermes: “Nevertheless...I thank you.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	33.	Hermes: “To know that you too have experienced suffering...is a comfort.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	34.	Hermes: “The stars in the heavens... Know you what they are?” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	35.	Hermes: “Though it is too far to tell, each glittering light could be a world not unlike Etheiry’s. A world filled with life.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	36.	Hermes: “So many stars, so many lives... For us, there may be no higher purpose than to live for our world, but what of the other living beings out there?” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	37.	Hermes: “What is it that gives their lives meaning? That drives them day after day after day?” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	38.	Hermes: “To pose that question to our undiscovered cousins, I created beings of dynamis, who can traverse the vast emptiness between the stars. Meteion and her sisters.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

	39. Hermes: “She has a great many of them, and they have already departed on their journey. Traveling to one star, and then the next, in search of life.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))
	40. Hermes: “Every step of the way, I’ve been reminded how little we understand creation. How the universe defies imagination.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))
	41. Meteion: “But soon we won’t need to speculate. We’ll know the answers—what others live for!” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))
	42. Hermes: “Whatever intelligent beings that exist out there are bound to be vastly different from us.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))
	43. Hermes: “Diverse in form and culture. Possessed of unique ways of thinking.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))
	44. Hermes: “Their conception of life and its purpose will be no exception. Completely and utterly unlike ours.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))
	45. Hermes: “Yet whatever answers we receive, I will not dismiss them out of hand. No, I will think earnestly on them all.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))
	46. Hermes: “Then I will share them with our people, that together we may contemplate our own existence.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))
	47. Hermes: “Perhaps then our star will become a better place—not only for man, but for all life.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))
	48. Hermes: “Meteion. Though I gave you wings to soar the heavens, I did not teach you how to walk the earth. So loath was I to bind another living being.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))
	49. Hermes: “In the course of your long journey, you will learn from those you meet. Learn to walk and run and so much more.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))

	50.	Hermes: “And when you return, older and wiser, we will have a celebration to mark your homecoming and coming of age both.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))
	64.	Hermes: “I tasked her with asking what others live for. What gives their lives...meaning...” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))
	72.	Meteion: “We scoured historical records. Communed with the spirits of the deceased.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	73.	Meteion: “Heard the final testaments of the dying. Welcomed their shadowed hearts into our own.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	74.	Meteion: “One race had striven to create a world bereft of animosity.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	75.	Meteion: “They renounced relationships to avoid interpersonal strife, and in so doing brought about societal collapse.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	76.	Meteion: “One race had renounced war and devoted itself to the enrichment of its people.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	77.	Meteion: “They were conquered. Though they destroyed the enemy in reprisal, they could not regain their former glory.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	78.	Meteion: “One race had concluded that finite time was the root of all woes. Aspiring to shatter its shackles, they went in search of infinity.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	79.	Meteion: “They discovered nothing is infinite, and that neither time or death can be cheated. Disillusioned, they gave up on the future—and themselves.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	80.	Meteion: “One race had discarded all things that gave rise to sorrow, hoping to have only joy.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

	81.	Meteion: “They found joy lost its savor in the absence of sorrow, and lost their will to live.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	82.	Meteion: “Though worlds apart, these people shared a belief. The belief that they had tried their best.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	83.	Meteion: “That they had tried to fulfill their potential, with every step and success.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	84.	Meteion: “That they would never be free of fear and sorrow, anger and despair—of loneliness—so long as they yet lived.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
Disbelief in True World	71.	Meteion: “Upon revealing this to me, entity elected to self-terminate in lieu of providing answer to question. No other intelligent life-forms found.” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))
	85.	Meteion: “Even now, their souls cry out for oblivion. And to this song of anguish, I lend my voice. We lend our voice.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	86.	Meteion: “O beloved mankind, shimmering jewels of beautiful Etheiryrs... Rejoice, for we will free you from the cruel yoke of existence.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	87.	Meteion: “There is no need to struggle in vain, for in nihilism awaits salvation. You will know peace and serenity...and it will be beautiful.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	88.	Meteion: “We will make our nest at the edge of the universe, and there in the dark of dead worlds hoard sorrow and suffering.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	89.	Meteion: “There we will sing, our chorus ever louder and ever clearer, that our song may reach even this aether-shrouded star.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))
	90.	Meteion: “Such is the answer we have found in the stars. Such is the gift we now offer to Etheiryrs.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

91.	Meteion: “Why have you come? All you had to do was wait. I would’ve delivered to you your ends.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))
92.	Meteion: “I don’t understand. All life is destined to end.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))
93.	Meteion: “Why choose to prolong your suffering?” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))
94.	Meteion: “Effort, ambition, love—they amount to naught. Happiness, should you find it, is inevitably lost. Stolen away by events beyond your control.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))
95.	Meteion: “There is no logic nor meaning in it. You think there is, convince yourselves, but it’s all a cruel accident.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))
96.	Meteion: “Come now, I speak the truth. A truth you would recognize if you looked up at the night sky.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))
97.	Meteion: “Unbroken emptiness. Cold, dark, and silent. Your world, like every other, is but a blemish upon its perfect fabric.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))
98.	Meteion: “Life is an anomaly. It is unnatural and cannot continue. The sooner you accept this, the easier it will be.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))
99.	Meteion: “I know it well. For the same passion once burned in many a star before yours.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))
100.	Meteion: “Suffocated and extinguished now.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))
101.	Meteion: “You approach the bounds of my Ultimatum, where emotions dictate reality.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))
102.	Meteion: “Where resignation and acceptance unite to embrace the end.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))
103.	Meteion: “Where those who yet valiantly cling to life cannot thrive...” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))

104.	Meteion: “This is how I found it when I arrived. Another star which once pulsed with life, but no longer.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))
105.	Meteion: “How it ended, I do not know. Invasion, sickness, suicide — none can say.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))
106.	Meteion: “None lived to speak for the dead. They are gone. Gone. Search all you like, but you’ll only end up turning back.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))
107.	Meteion: “You think you’ve caught me? This form is barely a drop from the ocean that swells within the dead sun.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))
108.	Meteion: “Even so, I could easily unmake you. You are only still alive because of your comrades. But they cannot protect you forever.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))
109.	Meteion: “Until they fade away, I’ll satisfy myself with watching you try—and fail—to find a way out of this lifeless place.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))
110.	Meteion: “Here the path ends. There is no way to reach our nest.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))
111.	Meteion: “I told you. Resignation and acceptance reign in this place.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))
112.	Meteion: “The rejection of life by those who came to curse it.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))
113.	Meteion: “Those whose dreams were unfulfilled. Whose prayers were unheard. Whose labors were unrewarded.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))
114.	Meteion: “Hope cannot deliver you unto hopelessness. Our refuge is beyond you.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))
115.	Meteion: “Struggle will avail you naught, nor will it grant your comrades peace.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))
116.	Meteion: “Come, let me relieve you of your burden. You have suffered enough.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))

117.	The Endsinger: “Ahhh, the rage... It rises... Rises...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
118.	The Endsinger: “We die in pain. We die in suffering! Who are you to live? Who are you to hope!?” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
119.	The Endsinger: “We will not suffer alone...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
120.	The Endsinger: “All will know our pain... You will be battered and torn and made to crawl.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
121.	The Endsinger: “You will weep and wail and curse your impotence. Curse your life as it fades.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
122.	The Endsinger: “As we did! As we died!” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
123.	The Endsinger: “Such pain and sorrow we felt... Such anguish and rage... We tried. We tried. But it was no use...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
124.	The Endsinger: “Only when we surrendered did we find release. Only when we embraced death.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
125.	The Endsinger: “So join us in despair...and embrace yours!” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
126.	The Endsinger: “You struggle in vain. You will not silence our song of oblivion!” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

2. Analysis

a) Recognition of Nihilism

Recognition of Nihilism, according to Nietzsche, happens when a person starts feeling that humans are not important in how the world changes and grows, resulting in a sense of purposelessness and a lack of accomplishment, leading to emotions of despair and futility (Nietzsche, 1968: 12). The first proof of recognition

of nihilism is Meteion shows her power; that is, Meteion can read the feelings of the creatures around her and project her emotions to others. This feeling is expressed when Meteion talks to the player about her power when Hermes tells the player to accompany Meteion outside while waiting for his meeting. The following quotation supports the statement:

(Data number-1)

Meteion: “This is my power. I can read the emotions of those around me, and project my emotions to others in return.” (Quest: Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86))

In the context of the statement above, the thesis writer explores that Meteion might be understood as a reflection of empathic nihilism, a type of nihilism that accepts the emotional experiences of others, even given the reality of a universe lacking any inherent meaning or value. Meteion possesses the unique ability to read the emotions of others and project their own emotions in return. This power enables them to interact with intelligent beings, even when faced with language barriers or nonverbal communication.

Nihilism can have a complex connection with emotions. Nihilism can result in adverse emotional conditions, such as sadness, anxiety, and rage, as it rejects the fundamental significance or worth of existence. Empathy can be regarded as a form of nihilism in this context. It recognizes the emotional encounters of others without giving any inherent or objective significance. This is consistent with the nihilistic perspective that life and the universe do not possess inherent significance or meaning. As a result, while nihilism can lead to negative emotional experiences, it

can also create a type of empathic understanding that is free of the limits of objective meaning or value.

Meteion continues, where she tries her ability to the player. Meteion uses emotions to communicate instead of words or telepathy. Those she speaks with are able to decipher her communications because they are subconsciously translating her feelings into words and intentions, as stated in the quotation below:

(Data number-2)

Meteion: “I am not actually speaking to you in your mind. Rather, you are converting my emotions into words and intention—a process performed subconsciously by intelligent life-forms.”
(Quest: Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86))

The thesis writer emphasizes from the quotation above that nihilism can be observed in Meteion’s capacity for nonverbal communication via feelings. She is able to express her own feelings as well as acknowledge the emotional experiences of others without the need for words, which are frequently thought of as a way to communicate something’s objective meaning or value. Meteion’s statement also emphasizes the subconscious process by which intelligent life forms turn emotions into words and goals. This process might be viewed as an acknowledgment of the existential condition of being influenced by emotions without any inherent or objective purpose or significance. This is consistent with the nihilistic belief that there is no objective purpose or significance to life and leads to the recognition of nihilism as it reflects a form of communication that bypasses the constructs we use to impose meaning and order on the world, and highlights the role of the subconscious and emotions in shaping our understanding of the world. However, it also highlights the potential for emotions to lead to a form of nihilism, reflecting

Nietzsche's recognition of the potential for nihilism to arise from despair and pessimism.

Meteion while trying her ability to the player, explains that her ability is very important to her mission because it allows her to interact with other intelligent beings that is not from Etheiry's. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-3)

Meteion: "This ability is vital to my mission, for it allows me to interact with intelligent beings even should they communicate via unknown languages or other nonverbal means." (Quest: Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer understands that Meteion's capacity to communicate with intelligent beings, despite of their language or nonverbal methods of communication, is a manifestation of her distinctive mode of being. She was created as an entelechy, originating from the energy called dynamis, which enables her to communicate through emotions and thoughts. Meteion's ability to communicate with intelligent beings has the potential to result in a feeling of isolation or discord since she is not bound by the same frameworks of language and communication that delineate human interaction. This may ultimately result in a nihilistic point of view, where she perceives no inherent meaning or value in her interactions with others. Her talent defies conventional constructs of language and communication, in line with Nietzsche's nihilistic perspective of the world's lack of fundamental order or structure. Nevertheless, this capability also has the potential to result in feelings of seclusion or estrangement, which aligns with Nietzsche's acknowledgment of nihilism's capacity to cause despair and pessimism.

Although Meteion finds it challenging to express herself in this manner, Hermes encourages her to speak openly, recognizing that everyone harbors thoughts and sentiments they may prefer to conceal. This ability to connect with others on an emotional level can be seen as a connection to Nietzsche's nihilism, which argues for the meaninglessness of life and the absence of objective values. Their ability to read and project emotions highlights the importance of human connection and the significance of emotions in navigating the complexities of existence.

Meteion continues telling the player where she struggles in expressing herself and her creator, Hermes, wants her to speak as much as possible so she can understand other people's thoughts and feelings that is unsaid or cannot be expressed easily. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-4)

Meteion: "Yet though I struggle to express myself in this fashion, Hermes wants me to speak as much as possible, for everyone has thoughts and feelings that they may wish to hide..." (Quest: Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86))

The thesis writer underlines that Meteion presents a problem for her to communicate these feelings in a way that makes sense. Despite her difficulties, Hermes, the creator of Meteion, urges her to communicate as much as she can. This is because everyone, including Hermes, has thoughts and feelings that they may prefer to hide. Meteion's difficulty in conveying her own emotions and the concealed emotions of others reflects the nihilistic idea that there is no inherent meaning in life. By trying to share these hidden feelings, Meteion questions the

belief that traditional ways of communication can capture the true essence of human experiences.

Meteion's difficulty in expressing herself and Hermes' insistence that she should communicate more can be seen through the perspective of Nietzsche's Recognition of Nihilism. This perspective suggests that traditional ways of communication and language may not fully capture the depth of human emotions and experiences. This aligns with Nietzsche's nihilistic view that the world has no inherent meaning or value. In simpler terms, Meteion finds it hard to share her feelings and thoughts, and even though Hermes encourages her to do so, it is a challenge. This situation can be seen as a reflection of Nietzsche's idea of nihilism, which suggests that life does not have a built-in meaning or value. This idea also suggests that the usual ways human use to express our feelings and experiences might not be enough to truly represent them. However, this struggle could lead to despair and pessimism.

Meteion's attraction to the player with complicated emotions appears to derive from her capacity to understand and share feelings with the player. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-5)

Meteion: "I harbor an affection for you. One that is difficult to define." (Quest: Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86))

The quotation above can be seen through the lens of nihilism, especially recognition of nihilism, because when Meteion talks about an affection that is hard to describe, it goes against the usual ways that we use words and communication to

talk about feelings and experiences. Nietzsche believes that the world has no meaning or worth in and of itself, so this fits with that view. It means that the usual ways of showing emotion might not fully capture the depth of human experiences. This quotation may also imply that Meteion's affection is impacted by or entwined with the emotion of the character they are speaking to, given Meteion's capacity to perceive and project emotions.

Meteion talks with the player about their thoughts where they share common traits, and Meteion wants to know more about it, as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-6)

Meteion: “Aside from the fact that you share common traits with us, your thoughts are complex. Prismatic. They draw me in, and leave me wanting to know more.” (Quest: Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86))

The thesis writer underlines from the quotation above that Meteion's desire may be understood as a reflection of Nietzsche's concept of active nihilism. According to Nietzsche, realizing that existence does not have any intrinsic purpose might actually serve as a starting point for developing our own values and meanings. One could see Meteion's quest to learn more about the human mind as an effort to give meaning to a universe that lacks meaning.

Meteion is a character who was created by Hermes and has the ability to read and project emotions. Meteion expresses her heavy feelings and the pain that Hermes is having to the player, as stated in the quotation below:

(Data number-7)

Meteion: “It's heavy... Hermes' pain...” (Quest: Aether to Aether (Level 86))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer explores that Meteion's recognition of Hermes' pain can be seen as a recognition of the nihilistic suffering that Nietzsche describes. As Meteion's creator, Hermes may represent the traditional values and meanings that Nietzsche believed were becoming obsolete. His pain could symbolize the existential crisis that comes with the realization of life's inherent meaninglessness.

Meteion describes Hermes' pain as "heavy" and expresses her understanding of his sadness, especially when he thinks about death. The way that Meteion describes Hermes' suffering and the nature of existence in Final Fantasy XIV is reminiscent of Nietzsche's idea of nihilism. Such beliefs include the idea that life has no purpose, that suffering is inevitable, and that effort and desire are pointless.

After looking around Elpis to find a flower for Hermes, Meteion and the player finds the most fitting flower for him. They find the Elpis flower, a flower that represents Elpis and can also read human emotions. Meteion tells the player that Hermes loves and hates Elpis flowers at the same time. This statement is from a dialog in the quest A Sentimental Gift with the following quotation:

(Data number-9)

Meteion: "Ooh, Elpis flowers! They're here too! Hermes likes and dislikes them. At the same time." (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

In the quotation above, the thesis writer emphasizes that Meteion understands how Hermes expresses about the Elpis flower. Hermes expresses a feeling that can be interpreted as a simultaneous liking and disliking of certain things: the Elpis flower. He loves them and hates them at the same time. The concept of liking and disliking something at the same time can be linked to the ambivalence or

complexity of human emotions and thoughts. Nietzsche remarks that there are emotions which “augment” one’s energy and feeling of life and emotions “in opposition to” those, which function to depress one’s activity and inhibit one’s feeling of life (Creasy, 2020: 98). Nietzsche’s quotation is about the idea that feelings can either make mankind more alive and fuller of energy, like happiness or excitement, or they can make them less alive and full of energy, like sadness or fear. To put it simply, he talks about how feelings are dual and how they affect our lives.

After Meteion finds Elpis flower while traveling around Elpis with the player and talks about how Hermes feels to Elpis flower, Meteion reveals how Elpis flower feels and reacts to Hermes’ emotions, which is Elpis flower feels pain from Hermes and the color of the petals of Elpis flower changes to black. This statement is supported by the following quotation from the quest A Sentimental Gift:

(Data number-10)

Meteion: “Like me, they’re entelechies. Like me, they feel his pain and turn dark...” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

In the quotation above, the thesis writer explores that Meteion understands the meaning of pain and the dark color that represents pain or depression. Meteion’s view of Hermes is dark, which is defined as pain and sorrow. In the context of “entelechies” refers to Meteion and her sisters, who are dynamis beings created by Hermes to travel the vast void between the stars in search of life. Meteion also says “like me, they feel his pain and turn dark...” which mean that Meteion has read and felt Hermes’ emotions like how Elpis flower reads Hermes’ emotions. This perspective highlights the impact of the belief that life has no inherent meaning can affect people’s emotional health. It suggests that this belief can lead to feelings of

despair and suffering. This is often discussed from a nihilistic perspective, which is a viewpoint that denies life's intrinsic value or meaning. In simpler terms, it is like saying that thinking life is pointless can make people feel really down and miserable, especially when looks at from a viewpoint that life has no real purpose.

After explaining to the player on how the Elpis flower reacts to Hermes, Meteion emphasizes her explanation again where she says that the dark color only applies to Hermes, and for others the color of their Elpis flower is white and bright. This statement is shown in the quest of A Sentimental Gift as quoted below:

(Data number-11)

Meteion: "That's only for Hermes, though. For others, they're always white and bright." (Quest: Aether to Aether (Level 86))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer portrays that Meteion's statement sees a different 'color' or emotional state for Hermes compare to the others, shows that the meaning or value she attributes to the others is subjective and depends on her own perspective or Hermes' perspective. Meteion is a character who can read and project emotions, and this quotation refers to her perception of emotions or states of being, which are different for Hermes, her creator, than for others. Drawing a link with Nietzsche's perspective of nihilism, there are certain similarities. Nietzsche's nihilism states that life has no objective meaning, purpose or intrinsic value. He believes that values do not come from outside, but are imposed on reality by human beings.

When Meteion explains that Elpis flower turn dark only applies to Hermes and the others are always white and bright, Meteion surprises that the Elpis flower

owns by the player also turns dark. This statement is shown in the dialog in the quest A Sentimental Gift as follows:

(Data number-12)

Meteion: “Truly!?! The flower was dark in your home!?” (Quest: Aether to Aether (Level 86))

In the quotation above, the thesis writer can understand that not only Hermes has dark emotion in his Elpis flower, but the player’s Elpis flower is also the same as Hermes. This connects to the previous quotation where Meteion said that only Hermes whose Elpis flower is dark and for the others is white and bright. In light of Nietzsche’s theory of nihilism, the dark flower can be seen as a representation of life not having any external meaning, purpose, or intrinsic value. The dark flower could reflect the player’s realization of this existential nothingness, which is a significant thought in Nihilism.

After Meteion knows that not only Hermes has a dark Elpis flower but the player also has it, Meteion asks the player if he/she has the same dark emotion as Hermes. This statement is supported by one of the dialogs in the quest A Sentimental Gift in the following quotation:

(Data number-13)

Meteion: “Then...do you have it too? A dark emotion?” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

The thesis writer implies the quotation above that Meteion wants to know more about the player, especially the player’s emotion because of the dark Elpis flower. In relation to Nietzsche’s theory of nihilism, Meteion’s question is one of existential despair or meaninglessness, which are two major themes of nihilism. Nietzsche’s nihilism claims that life has no meaning or value, and that traditional

values are worthless. This can lead to feelings of despair, pessimism and the conviction that life has no beauty, love or truth. Nietzsche's nihilism is the idea that life has no meaning, purpose or value in and of itself. A state of hopelessness happens when traditional ideals fail to help one understand and live in the world anymore. In this case, the "dark emotion" Meteion talks about can be seen as a sign of nihilistic despair and recognition of nihilism.

The player replies to Meteion about her question, which the player says that she has known the pain and sorrow of loss. The statement can be seen from one of the dialogues of the quest A Sentimental Gift on Table 3, as stated in the quotation below:

(Data number-14)

Player: "I've known the pain and sorrow of loss." (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

The thesis writer understands the quotation above that the player tells Meteion that she recognizes that loss, as a confrontation with the meaninglessness and misery inherent in existence, which is a significant theme of nihilism. The agony and grief of loss can result in a sense of existential disillusionment and despair, which is a common reaction to the nihilistic awareness that traditional life ideals have no basis. Though the player's words might not directly express this darker side of nihilism, they could be seen as a sign of hopelessness or acceptance in the face of life's pain. We have learned that pain is projected to a part of the body without being situated there—we have learned that sense impressions naively supposed to be conditioned by the outer world are, on the contrary, conditioned by the inner

world; that we are always unconscious of the real activity of the outer world (Nietzsche, 2006: 205).

Meteion, as a character, personifies this philosophy. Hermes creates her as an artificial being to understand the feelings and experiences of people. Meteion understand the pain and sorrow of the player as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-15)

Meteion: “I see... (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer ponders that when Meteion says “I see...”, she recognizes that the person is in pain and sorrow, which helps her understand that suffering is a normal part of life. Meteion, an artificial being made to understand human feelings, can tell what the player is feeling, which could be a form of existential despair or an awareness that life might not have any meaning. This fits with Nietzsche’s idea that realizing that life does not have any meaning can make people nihilistic, where they have no faith in any values or beliefs. Meteion’s ability to understand how the player feels is similar Nietzsche’s view that understanding the depth of human experience, including its darker aspects, is part of the human condition.

After Meteion understands the player’s emotions, Meteion says that Hermes has a similar feeling with the player but sadly no one notices. This statement is supported with the dialogue stated below:

(Data number-16)

Meteion: “Hermes has known the same. The feeling that a part of you is gone. Again and again. But no one notices...” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

The thesis writer examines the above quotation that given the situation, Hermes seems to be feeling like he keeps losing things or parts of himself that are important to him. This can be analyzed as a metaphor for the existential crisis that Nietzsche talks about, in which people struggle with life's meaninglessness and the lack of unchanging values or ultimate truths. The statement "but no one notices..." may express the isolation and loneliness that often accompanies this existential crisis, as individuals believe that their personal troubles are unnoticed by others. Furthermore, Hermes' creation, Meteion, has the power to read and project emotions. This can be understood as a metaphor for the existentialist concept of 'existence precedes essence,' in which individuals are free to construct their own meaning in life, but this freedom brings anxiety, sadness, and a sense of loss.

As Meteion tells the player that Hermes also has the same feelings of pain and sadness and that part of him is gone, Meteion wants the player to lend Meteion the pain and sadness, as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-17)

Meteion: "Please, (player). Won't you lend it to me? Your pain and sorrow..." (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

From the above quotation, the thesis writer can understand that Meteion is willing to share the player's pain and sorrow so the player will not feel alone just like Hermes in the previous quotation, where Meteion says that no one notices Hermes' pain. Nietzsche's idea of the will to power can be seen in Meteion's wish that the player expresses the pain and sorrow to her. Nietzsche thinks that everyone has this basic drive, which can show up as a desire to control other people or, in this case, to understand and feel other people's feelings. Meteion's capacity to read and

transmit emotions, as well as her desire to comprehend the player's suffering can be seen as the recognition of nihilism.

Meteion, as the creature created by Hermes, wants him to know that he is not alone even though he is in a dark place and feels sad. Meteion wants Hermes to know that not only him but other people are sad too. This statement is supported by the dialogue from the quest A Sentimental Gift, as stated below:

(Data number-18)

Meteion: "He (Hermes) has been in a dark place. Since before he created me. He needs to know that he isn't there alone. That others are sad too." (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

The thesis writer actualizes the quotation above that Meteion's description of Hermes' emotional state as a "dark place" might refer to an existential crisis or a sense of despair. Nietzsche believed that when traditional values and beliefs are stripped away, individuals are left in a state of nihilism, when existence becomes meaningless. This appears to be the case with Hermes, who, despite his role as a creator, appears to be in emotional distress. It is a state in which traditional values have lost their meaning and existence has become meaningless and empty. Nihilists, antecedently, might seem to be those who, in the wake of God's death, have lost their sense that anything matters and fallen into existential despair (Huddleston, 2019: 2).

Meteion's statement that "...others are sad too." can be interpreted as an attempt to foster a sense of shared experience or community, which Nietzsche might say is a way of constructing meaning in a nihilistic world. Meteion is trying to help Hermes feel less alone by pointing out that everyone is going through pain. This is a typical effect of nihilistic thinking. The affective nihilist, as an individual with a

weakened will, experiences the weakening of “desires, the feelings of pleasure and pain, the will to power, the feeling of pride, having and wanting to have more” (Creasy, 2020: 60).

Meteion and the player talk, then they wait outside of the meeting room to give the Elpis flower to Hermes to cheer him up. Hermes finishes his meeting and is surprised because Meteion shows him the Elpis flower. Meteion tells Hermes that he is not the only one because others feel sad too and he is not alone. This statement can be seen in Table 3 as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-19)

Meteion: “You’re not the only one, Hermes. Others feel sad too. You’re not alone.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

The thesis writer underlines that Meteion tries to comfort Hermes, who is sad and feels alone. The recognition of nihilism by Nietzsche can relate to this quote and reveal some interesting similarities. The idea that there is no essential value, meaning, or purpose to life is known as nihilism, according to Nietzsche. Hermes is going through a sort of existential crisis throughout the game, wondering what his life is all about and if it is worth it. In response, Meteion tries to reassure Hermes that he is not alone in his pain in an effort to lessen his sense of loneliness. This is similar to Nietzsche’s concept of shared suffering as a common human experience as written in *BEYOND GOOD AND EVIL* that “the intellectual haughtiness and loathing of every man who has suffered deeply,” (Nietzsche, 2006: 218).

Meteion’s power to absorb and project emotions, on the other hand, mirrors Nietzsche’s concept of “eternal recurrence,” the idea that all events will repeat indefinitely. Like the eternal recurrence of the same situations of circumstances,

Meteion is able to repeatedly experience the same feelings because she shares consciousness with her sisters.

Hermes in the previous dialogue states that it is not wrong to live for the stars and to make it a better place. Yet, Hermes says to the player that there are times when he is surrounded by doubt. This statement is shown in the quest A Sentimental Gift in Table 3 as stated below:

(Data number-21)

Hermes: “And yet, in carrying out my duties here, there are times when I am plagued by doubt.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

The thesis writer investigates the quotation above that Hermes, just like ordinary humans, has doubts, especially Hermes is carrying out his duties to the stars, which can be said to be a big responsibility. Hermes’ doubt could be interpreted as an existential crisis, a questioning of the purpose and worth of his responsibilities, which is in line with the concept of nihilism. He is carrying out his responsibilities, but he questions its significance, probably because he sees no ultimate purpose or value in them. This may be considered a sort of passive nihilism, in which one understands the lack of ultimate meaning yet continues to live within the existing value system.

Hermes understands the feeling of the poor creatures which are pain, suffering, confusion, and despair. This statement can be seen in the quest called A Sentimental Gift in Table 3, as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-27)

Hermes: “Pain and suffering... Confusion and despair... Write plain in the eyes of those poor creatures.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer understands that Hermes aware of the pain, suffering, confusion, and despair of those poor creatures. Hermes expresses deep empathy and concern for the suffering and pain of other beings. He recognizes the visible signs of their suffering, such as confusion and despair, and is troubled by the fact that others seem indifferent to their fate. Nietzsche (2006: 69) in *BEYOND GOOD AND EVIL* says that “Among men, as among all other animals, there is a surplus of defective, diseased, degenerating, infirm, and necessarily suffering individuals.” In his writings, Nietzsche says that both humans and animals have a significant number of flawed, sick, and declining individuals who suffer a lot. This suggests that suffering is a natural and common part of life. Hermes’ statement demonstrates the connection between suffering and nihilism. By acknowledging these beings’ pain and suffering, he indirectly recognizes the nihilistic idea that life has no inherent significance or value. The awareness that existence has no inherent meaning or purpose may lead to despair and indifference, which can be seen as the recognition of nihilism. This quotation underlines the importance of empathy and compassion in the face of such misery and criticizes the nihilistic attitude of apathy towards suffering.

Hermes expresses his sadness to the player, for those who are ignorant to reality. The statement can be seen on the following quotation:

(Data number-28)

Hermes: “Yet no one sees. We turn a blind eye and carry on in blissful ignorance. Naught amiss, and always—always the blossoms shine pure and white.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

The thesis writer analyzes the quotation above that Hermes is angry and sad that the other individuals do not understand nor care about the suffering and pain in their world. "...blossoms shine pure and white" stand for the peace and cleanliness that people keep even when they do not want to deal with the problems that are really there. The phrase "turn a blind eye" means to consciously escape or deny these painful facts. It can be seen as a criticism of the emptiness and meaninglessness that people encounter in life. Hermes' despair can be interpreted as a manifestation of existential despair, another fundamental idea in Nietzsche's nihilism. He is troubled by the fact that individuals refuse to acknowledge the realities of life, preferring to live in denial. This can be interpreted as an existential crisis in which Hermes struggles with the meaninglessness of life and the ignorance of others.

Meteion connects herself to her sisters in other stars to share the result of the findings about in search of meaning of life. Hermes, player, Emet-Selch, and Venat are waiting for what Meteion is about to report. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-51)

Meteion: "Executing scheduled task. Suspending individual self and connecting to shared consciousness." (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer implies that Meteion tries to connect herself to her sisters to share the results of their mission. The phrase "Suspending individual self and connecting to shared consciousness" means that Meteion is putting her own identity and activities on hold for now so she can

connect with her sisters in other stars. As a result, she can share information, experiences, or instructions with her sisters and get the mission's results.

Meteion experiences fear and pain from the report she receives in the previous quotation. The quotation from the quest *Words Without Sound* in Table 3 supports this statement:

(Data number-52)

Meteion: "So scared... so lonely... The pain... it's too much..."
(Quest: *Words Without Sound* (Level 87))

The thesis writer indicates the quotation above that Meteion is experiencing fear and suffering as she receives the reports from her sisters that traverses different worlds. Meteion is able to read and project emotion, which is the same as her sisters, makes her able to feel the same feelings as her other sisters in other stars. Meteion's travels through different worlds and her power to understand and absorb other people's feelings could be seen as an actual illustration of this part of Nietzsche's nihilism theory. She encounters multiple worlds through the emotions of others, which may cause disbelief or doubt in a single, true world.

Meteion feels not only pain and lonely but also hurt and hate. These shared feelings are from her sisters who travels to other stars to seek meaning of life. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-53)

Meteion: "Why...why...why do we...they..hurt...hurt... hate...HATE!" (Quest: *Words Without Sound* (Level 87))

The thesis writer analyzes the quotation above that the hopelessness and confusion Meteion feels about all the pain, suffering, and hate she sees in the world. Meteion is a character who can read and project emotions, and she is severely

affected by the unpleasant feelings she encounters. She tries to understand why other beings in other stars are hurt and hate each other. It is a cry of hopelessness, and an asking of what life is all about. Meteion's despair and confusion can be seen as a form of existential nihilism, in which she questions the point and worth of life because she sees so much pain and hate. Becoming is of equivalent value every moment; the sum of its values always remains the same; in other words, it has no value at all, for anything against which to measure it, and in relation to which the word "value" would have meaning, is lacking (Nietzsche, 1968: 378).

Meteion experiences overpowering negative emotions and decides that existence is a cause of suffering. This statement can be seen in the dialog of the quest Words Without Sound in Table 3, as shown below:

(Data number-54)

Meteion: "This is wrong! All wrong!" (Quest: Words Without Sound (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer understands that Meteion is in a moment of distress and confusion. Her interactions with numerous civilizations and their tragic fates lead her to a nihilistic conclusion. She has seen societies try to eradicate misery, pursue eternity, or enrich their people, only to end in despair, disappointment, or destruction. Meteion concludes from these experiences that as long as existence exists, it will never be free of negative feelings such as fear, grief, wrath, and despair. In line with Nietzsche's idea of passive nihilism, this means that when life seems pointless, someone might want nothingness or the end of existence.

Meteion and her sisters connects with other beings in other stars and absorbs their emotions. She feels their hopelessness and pain, which makes her very sad. As a result, she begs the player and other characters that close to her to stay away, admitting that something is wrong yet blaming it to her own mistake. This statement supports the dialogue in the quest Words Without Sound in Table 3, as shown below:

(Data number-55)

Meteion: “Stay away. Please. This is wrong. My mistake. So please...” (Quest: Words Without Sound (Level 87))

From the above quotation, the thesis writer learns that Meteion expresses sorrow, fear, and a call for others to avoid a mistake that Meteion makes. The repetitive “please” in Meteion’s voice stresses how urgent and desperate she sounds, indicating a strong desire to keep others from making the same mistake or being hurt. It leads to sentiments of hopelessness or regret, which are common feelings associated with nihilism. This struggle is an important part of Nietzsche’s theory because it leads to adverse effects, such as pessimism, cynicism, and despair.

Meteion tells the player and other characters that she and her sisters’ exploration is done and will report their findings. This statement supports the dialogue in the quest Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen in Table 3 as shown below:

(Data number-56)

Meteion: “Our survey is complete. We shall now report our findings.” (Quest: Words Without Sound (Level 87))

The thesis writer emphasizes the quotation above that Meteion says the part of exploring and gathering data is over and now is the time to show what she and her sisters discovers. Meteion may provide information about the different societies

her sisters find, including their cultures, ways of life, and ideas about what life is all about.

Meteion continues to tell that her sisters arrive at their respective destination in search of answers to Hermes' question. Meteion's sisters tries to contact with the intelligent beings of each star. This statement can be seen in the dialog of the quest Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen in Table 3 as shown below:

(Data number-57)

Meteion: "All units safely arrived at their respective destinations. Seeking answers to Hermes's question, we attempted to make contact with the intelligent denizens of each star." (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

The thesis writer underlines the quotation above that Meteion reports on the task Hermes assigns her. Meteion and her sisters, who is also a dynamis being, are to travel to various stars and talk to the intelligent life there as part of their assignment. The purpose of this mission is to find the answer to the question Hermes asks: "What do other people live for?" "What does their life mean to them?"

Hena as one of the Meteion's sister that travels to other stars, reports her findings through Meteion. Hena reports that she finds traces of civilization but does not detect any extant life forms. This statement can be seen in the quest Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen in Table 3 as shown below:

(Data number-58)

Hena (Meteion's Sister): "Traces of civilization found—structures believed to have served as domiciles. No extant life-forms detected." (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

From the above quotation, the thesis writer explores that Hena reports on her exploration of a faraway star. Some of the things she finds are the remains of a

civilization, including buildings that were probably homes. However, she cannot locate any living beings in the area at present. In Nietzsche's theory of nihilism, the lack of life in a society that used to be thriving could be seen as a sign that life is temporary and has no purpose in the end. The idea behind Nietzsche's nihilism is that life has no real meaning, objective, or value. The finding of a dead civilization with no living beings to carry on its legacy may be seen as a representation of this nihilistic viewpoint. This is a reminder that even stars that once bore civilizations are now left with only traces of their previous existence.

After Hena finishes reporting her findings, next is to hear the findings from Dyo, who is also one of Meteion's sisters. Dyo reports that the existence of life cannot be verified, and the remains of a ruined building scattered across star which surface is covers in ice. This statement supports the dialog in Table 3 as shown below:

(Data number-59)

Dyo (Meteion's Sister): "Ruined remnants of buildings scattered across star, surface of which is encased in ice. Presence of life could not be verified." (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

The thesis writer emphasizes the quotation above that Dyo as Meteion's other sister portrays an ice star where relics of a civilization are discovers but no contemporary life. The scattered buildings on the star make it look like a society that once existed but has since fallen apart or disappeared. The ice covering the star's surface shows that it is a cold and possibly uninhabitable place to live. Nietzsche's nihilism says that our reality, or "true world," is just an illusion and that life has no meaning or worth on its own. The empty star, which used to be home to

a society but now has no living things on it, can be seen as a metaphor for this idea. The society that used to be strong is gone, leaving only ruins behind. This is similar to how nihilism says life has no point and ends in nothingness.

Tria, one of Meteion's sisters, tells what she finds out from exploring the universe. She finds the remains of big population centers that look like cities, but there are no living things there, only signs that they used to be there. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-60)

Tria (Meteion's Sister): "Evidence of large population centers akin to cities recovered. No extant life-forms found—only their lingering essence." (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer investigates that Tria reports on her results from her research of different stars. She finds signs of big population centers that look like cities, but there are no living things there. The statement "lingering essence" refers to buildings, artifacts, or even feelings or energy that are left over from the societies that used to live in these places. Nietzsche's nihilism says that traditional beliefs and values are baseless, such as the idea that there is a "true" or objective world. He says that people may become hopeless or nihilistic when they learn there is no objective truth or meaning. They will then think that life has no point.

Tessera, Meteion's sister, surveys a star. She discovers what she thinks are abandoned houses. There are no signs of life, which makes her think that either a terrible disease or a lot of damage to the environment possibly kills everyone who lives there. This statement supports the dialog in Table 3 as shown below:

(Data number-61)

Tessera (Meteion's Sister): “Edifices surmised to be abandoned residences found. No extant life-forms detected. Deadly plague or extreme environmental degradation likely to have led to mass extinction.” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

The thesis writer actualizes the quotation above that Tessera discovers what she thinks are the remains of homes, but there are no live things inside. She thinks that a mass extinction might have been caused by a deadly disease or serious damage to the environment. A nihilism point of view shows by the report's tone of objective observation and the fact that these abandoned buildings are not inhabited by any living things that could give them meaning or value. The report lacks anything sad about the loss of these societies; it just says that they are gone. One way to look at this is as an example of the nihilistic view that life has no real meaning, purpose, or value.

Hermes is surprised when he hears the report from Meteion which basically all civilizations are dead. This statement supports the dialog in the quest Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen as shown below:

(Data number-62)

Hermes: “They are all...dead?” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer ponders that Hermes does not believe what he hears from Meteion, which is the result of her sisters' findings. All of the civilization in other stars are dead. Being—we have no idea of it apart from the idea of “living.”— How can anything dead “be”? (Nietzsche, 1968: 312). Hermes feels despair after this finding, which is similar to Nietzsche's view of how dangerous Nihilism is. The understanding that all existence ends in death, along

with the absence of a universal purpose or meaning, can lead to feelings of pessimism or existential dread.

Emet-Selch, as one of Hermes' colleagues who also hears the report from Meteion, asks Hermes what task he gives to Meteion. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-63)

Emet-Selch: "Remind me, Hermes. What exactly was the question you entrusted to Meteion?" (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

From the above quotation, the thesis writer learns that Emet-Selch asks Hermes to repeat the task he gives to Meteion. Meteion is instructed by Hermes to ask the intelligent beings she encounters on her journey across the universe, about what gives meaning to life. Nietzsche's Nihilism can be seen in this question, which questions the idea that life has an inherent or universal meaning or not.

Emet-Selch questions Hemes if he ever considers the danger if the results are negative. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-65)

Emet-Selch: "Did you consider what may happen if the premise of the question is flawed?" (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer analyzes that Emet-Selch asks Hermes, the one who poses the question to Meteion, if he has thought about the fact that the basis of his question might be incorrect or misguided. If the premise is wrong, then the conclusions that are taken from it might also be wrong, which can lead to negative or misleading results. If these beings do not share these views or

values, this might be interpreted as Nihilism. If they do not want to live or cannot express what gives their lives value, then the question's premise is flawed. This can lead to the nihilistic view that life has no point or meaning, which is what Meteion seems to find on her journey.

Emet-Selch continues, to answer the question that Hermes gives to Meteion, the beings in other stars must be alive and have the desire of living. This statement can be seen in Table 3 as shown below:

(Data number-66)

Emet-Selch: "To be able to answer it, one must be living—and desire to continue doing so." (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer understands that Emet-Selch illustrates that the question's premise may be flawed due to the requirement of not only being alive but also possessing a desire to continue existing in order to provide an answer. If Meteion does not meet any living beings, or beings that have no desire to live, the replies it gets from their silence might not be accurate or meaningful. Emet-Selch is afraid that Meteion will come to the wrong conclusions about life if she fails to encounter any living things or people who want to live. This illustrates Nietzsche's concept of Nihilism and its possible consequences when taken to an extreme, such as the denial of life itself.

Emet-Selch asks to Hermes what if Meteion cannot find living beings in her journey to other stars. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-67)

Emet-Selch: “But if Meteion finds no living beings in the course of her journey...” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer indicates that it is not possible to answer the question of what gives life meaning if Meteion fails to discover any living things on her journey or if the ones she does find are unwilling to continue living.

Emet-Selch continues his question, what will happen if Meteion also cannot find the living beings who have desire to live. This statement supports the dialog in Table 3 in the quotation below:

(Data number-68)

Emet-Selch: “Or none who desire to live, what then?” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

The thesis writer actualizes the quotation above that Emet-Selch’s question reflects this Nihilistic perspective. If Meteion fails to discover any beings that want to live, it possibly can mean that these beings do not have any meaning or purpose in their life, which is why they lack the desire to keep living. This fits with Nietzsche’s idea of nihilism because it shows how hopeless and unstable life can become when someone thinks it has no meaning or purpose. Emet-Selch’s words suggest that Hermes’ plan might not work as it is planned, and he also hints that Meteion’s task might have results that are unexpected and may be dangerous.

Emet-Selch asks Hermes, what answers in the meaning of life that Meteion will get from the quietness of the other stars. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-69)

Emet-Selch: “What answers would she derive from their silence?”
(Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

The thesis writer explores the quotation above that Emet-Selch wants to know what Meteion learns from their silence. He implies that quiet, or not responding, can also be an answer, even if it is an uncomfortable one. This silence can indicate that the beings is unwilling to live or fails to see any point in living, which makes Meteion think about existence in a troubling way. This might make Meteion and, by extension, the other characters in the game wonder what the point and worth of their own lives are, which is similar to Nietzsche’s idea of nihilism.

Meteion, who ignores Venat’s orders to stop her mission, continues with the report from one of her sisters, Dekapente. Dekapente reports that a local civilization once flourished under the auspices of a higher power. That power then destroys the civilization in a fit of rage. This statement can be seen in Table 3 as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-70)

Dekapente (Meteion’s Sister): “Local civilization once flourished under auspices of higher power. Said power later laid waste to civilization in fit of rage.” (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer emphasizes that Dekapente, one of Meteion’s sisters who travels to another star, portrays a civilization that once grew under the guidance of a higher power. However, this same power causes the destruction of the civilization in a fit of rage. The fact that the society is so easily wiped out suggests that its existence lacks any meaning or value on its own. Furthermore, the greater power’s fury could be seen as a reaction to the

understanding of the meaninglessness of its own existence or acts, a common theme in Nietzsche's nihilism which can lead to the recognition of nihilism. The higher power may serve as a metaphor for the idea of a "True World." Its ability to lead a society to success suggests that people believed it was greater or superior than others.

b) **Systematization of Nihilism**

According to Nietzsche's Systematization of Nihilism, people frequently believe in a higher power or universal principle to give their life meaning and value. When individuals lose trust in this idea, they lose faith in themselves, leading to a state of nihilism in which existence appears pointless. Nietzsche states in his *The Will to Power* book that at bottom, man has lost the faith in his own value when no infinitely valuable whole works through him; i.e., he conceived such a whole in order to be able to believe in his own value (Nietzsche, 1968: 12). The first proof of Systematization of Nihilism appears in the dialogue on the quest Aether to Aether.

Hermes, the creator of Meteion, talks about their duty to the star and existence as seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-8)

Hermes: "We have a duty to the star, this I know. But it doesn't mean we don't also have a responsibility to the lives we bring into existence here." (Quest: Aether to Aether (Level 86))

The thesis writer implies that Hermes admits his responsibility to the stars or universe in general when he says, "We have a duty to the star," which could be seen as a dedication to the more general aims or purposes of his species or society. This

might have to do with advancing knowledge, protecting the environment, or pursuing a higher goal. However, Hermes underlines that this duty to the star does not eliminate the responsibility for the lives that are created in the process. By stating, “But it doesn’t mean we don’t also have a responsibility to the lives we bring into existence here,” he implies that he is responsible for the welfare and destiny of the creatures he has created, like Meteion. This might involve making sure that they are happy, protecting them from danger, or valuing their individuality and uniqueness.

Hermes understands that Meteion shares much with the player because of what she says earlier that he is not the only one who feel sad and alone. Hermes asks the player to talk in private without Meteion. Hermes starts the conversation about the purpose of life and make the star a better place. This statement can be seen in the Table 3 as stated below:

(Data number-20)

Hermes: “I do not think it wrong that we live for the star. That we strive to make it a better place.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer understands Hermes’ statement as a response to the nihilistic way of thinking. When he says “...we live for the stars”, he is defining the purpose of life, which is to live for something greater than oneself, in this case “the stars”. The stars can be interpreted as a metaphor for the world or the universe in general because in this game’s world, it has thirteen alternate “reflections,” which are named the First to Thirteenth where it started as a single Source world. His statement that “we strive to make it a better place” further

underlines the idea of purpose and action. It implies that human have not only a reason to survive, but also a responsibility to improve our surroundings.

Hermes discusses death where death is a privilege to those who fulfill their purpose in this world, the choice of their own will, and he also admires it when they depart. This statement is shown in the following quotation:

(Data number-22)

Hermes: “Death is the privilege of those who have fulfilled their purpose. A choice they embrace of their own free will. And when they depart, it is always beautiful.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

In the quotation above, the thesis writer is aware that Hermes considers people who have fulfilled their purpose and then die, own wonderful life because they can choose their free will. It can be taken as a reflection on the nature of life and death, as well as the meaning of existence. Hermes’ statement “...And when they depart, it is always beautiful.” can be interpreted as a poetic reflection on the beauty of a life of ones who lived in their life with the full of will and purpose, where death is not a tragic end, but a beautiful end to a life with purpose, implying that even in the face of death, life can have meaning and beauty. Hermes’ quotation can also be interpreted as an important reminder of how crucial it is to find and develop a purpose in life as instead of rushing towards the end.

I took the will to beauty, to persist in like forms, for a temporary means of preservation and recuperation: fundamentally, however, the eternally-creative appeared to me to be, as the eternal compulsion to destroy, associated with pain (Nietzsche, 2006: 224). Nietzsche is saying that people think that seeking beauty and making forms that are consistent are ways to keep and get back vitality. But he

thinks that the real meaning of life is an endless force that can both make things and break them, and this process is painful by nature. Basically, Nietzsche is saying that the drive to make things is related to the drives to destroy and suffer.

Hermes, the creator of Meteion, talks about the lost lives that are barely get the chance to live and die young. It can be seen on the quotation below:

(Data number-23)

Hermes: “Some scarcely born into the world. Afforded a handful of breaths before life and potential are abruptly extinguished.”
(Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

The thesis writer ponders the quotation above that Hermes shows his sadness and hopelessness at how short life is, especially when it ends as soon as it starts. It indicates nihilism that there is no objective meaning, purpose, or intrinsic value to life. Hermes’ statement “handful of breaths” represents how short and fragile life is, while the sudden death of life and possibility represents the apparent meaninglessness and unpredictability of existence. The idea that some lives are “scarcely born into the world” before they die, highlights the nihilistic viewpoint, implying that individual lives have no effect on the universe at all. This statement represents nihilistic despair, a perspective that believes existence is short-lived, fragile, and ultimately meaningless.

Hermes tells the player about how other beings’ feels even though they spare the pain away, they still rage and cower in fear and he thinks it is not beautiful as what he says in the previous dialog about how beautiful it is when they depart and embrace their own free will. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-24)

Hermes: “We make an effort to spare them the pain. But they sense what awaits. Rage in anguish and cower in fear...and it is not beautiful.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer underlines that Hermes tries to protect other beings from the harsh reality of life and death from his statement “make an effort to spare them the pain.” But despite the effort, other beings know what awaits on their future life and they cover in rage and fear. Hermes finds that this process is far from beautiful, contrary to the popular belief that death is a beautiful moment for those who have fulfilled their purpose.

Hermes expresses his feeling to the player that he is sad because no one cares on the pain and despair of creatures. This statement can be seen on the quotation below:

(Data number-25)

Hermes: “Yet no one cares. No one.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)) (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

The thesis understands the quotation above that Hermes shows how hopeless and disappointing world around him. He witnesses the agony and sorrow of creatures and is sad by the indifference of others to this suffering. Hermes believes that some people are ignoring or undervaluing the pain and suffering that some beings go through. This feeling comes up when he thinks about his responsibilities and the moral choices he has to make. He feels like life and promise are often cut off quickly, but no one seems to care or notice. He feels bad that other people seem to have no concern about the pain of beings who are seen as “useless” or “unwanted.” His words are a criticism of what people see as indifference and a plea for

understanding and empathy. It shows how he struggles with the moral implications of his tasks and how much he wants to have a more caring view of life and existence.

Hermes is a character who is greatly concerned with the meaning of life and what can be employed to carry out responsibilities. He finds it difficult that people too much focus on their duties that they fail to think about whether the way they are doing is right or wrong. This statement can be seen on the quotation below:

(Data number-26)

Hermes: “So fixated are we upon the duty that we do not pause to question the method.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

The thesis writer analyzes the quotation above that Hermes is too anxious with carrying out responsibilities without considering the ethical consequences of the methods uses to accomplish so. Hermes’ statement is a critique of this worldview, implying that people should not simply carry out their tasks without considering the moral consequences of their actions. By questioning the methods used to accomplish, people can overcome the despair and apathy associated with nihilism and create new value and meaning for themselves.

Hermes feels frustrated and wants to scream because of the contradiction and aberration that others can accept. This statement is proven in the quest called A Sentimental Gift in Table 3, as shown below:

(Data number-29)

Hermes: “A contradiction so blatant I could scream. Want to scream. How can you all accept this...aberration!?” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer ponders that it is obvious that Hermes disagrees with what is going on and cannot believe what he is seeing. The word “aberration” shows that he thinks the situation is different from what should

be normal or expected. He wants to scream to show how strongly he feels, which is a mix of anger, rage, and disbelief which reflects existential crisis that often accompanies nihilistic thought.

Hermes questions himself if he goes astray in thinking so and he fills with fear. This statement can be seen in the quest A Sentimental Gift in Table 3, as shown below:

(Data number-30)

Hermes: “Then I wonder...am I the aberration for thinking thus? And I am filled with dread...” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer indicates that Hermes talks about his own thoughts and views, he shows fear and doubt. Since his opinion seems to be different from what other people around him think, he starts to wonder if it is strange or off. He probably feels afraid because he thinks that having a different point of view will make him alone and rejected. Nietzsche’s nihilism says that traditional values are baseless and that life has no point, which can make people reject life or desire nothingness. This is shown by Hermes’ fear, as he seems to be struggling with the idea that his thoughts may not have any basis or value.

Hermes now understands that he is not alone because he is not the only one who feel the pain and sorrow as the player also shares the same emotion. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-31)

Hermes: “But now I know I’m not alone. Not the only one for whom the flowers weep.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

The thesis writer implies the quotation above that Hermes’ statement is a metaphor for mutual grief and empathy. “Flowers” represent emotions, particularly

sadness and despair such as Elpis flower. “Flowers weep”, Hermes adds, referring to the shared experience of sadness and suffering. The phrase “I am not alone” represents his acknowledgment that his feelings are shared by others, and that he is not alone in his state of despair because the player also shares the same feelings.

Hermes expresses his gratitude to the player because of the shared feelings of pain and sorrow that he feels. This statement can be seen in the quest A Sentimental Gift in Table 3 as shown below:

(Data number-32)

Hermes: “Nevertheless...I thank you.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer understands that Hermes is talking to the player. Even though Hermes feels alone with his pain and sorrow, he thanks the player because they shared similar feelings and he knows that he is not alone anymore. He thinks that no one else is aware of the pain and suffering going on around him, so he feels alone in his sadness and hopelessness. This shared experience between Hermes and the player provides a sense of companionship and comfort, easing the loneliness and despair that Hermes feels.

Hermes feels comfortable because of the similar feelings between him and the player. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-33)

Hermes: “To know that you too have experienced suffering...is a comfort.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer investigates that even though Hermes feels pain and sorrow, he also feels comfort because the player also experienced suffering, which stated in the previous dialogue between Meteion and

the player where it says “I’ve known the pain and sorrow of loss.” In a nihilistic society, Hermes’ words can be interpreted as a way of finding comfort and connection. The common experience of suffering can foster a sense of community and understanding, even in the event that existence is ultimately worthless.

Hermes questions the player what are the stars in the heavens. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-34)

Hermes: “The stars in the heavens... Know you what they are?”
(Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer investigates that Hermes is expressing his wonder and interest about the universe to the player and the possibility of life on other planets. Not just on their planet but also in other parts of the universe, he questions about the nature of existence and the meaning of life. If the character of existence should be false—which would be possible—what would truth, all our truth, be then?— An unconscionable falsification of the false? The false raised to a higher power? (Nietzsche, 1968: 292). Essentially, Nietzsche is challenging the possibility that the nature of life or the universe could be fundamentally false in a way that destroys all of human ideas of what is true. Realities would then be distortions based on a lie one could not escape.

Hermes says that even though the stars in the heavens are too far to tell, he thinks that every shimmering light could be a world not very different from Etheiry's, the star he currently inhabits, which is full of life. This statement is supported by dialog from Hermes, the creator of Meteion in the quest A Sentimental Gift as shown below:

(Data number-35)

Hermes: “Though it is too far to tell, each glittering light could be a world not unlike Etheiry’s. A world filled with life.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

From the statement above, the thesis writer actualizes that Hermes is filled with wonder and curiosity about the universe. He proposes that each star in the universe could be a place similar to Etheiry’s, their own world, teeming with life. This phrase shows a sense of hope and opportunity, as well as a desire to understand and connect with the larger the universe.

Hermes thinks that the purpose in life of the people in Etheiry’s is no higher than living for the world, while there are so many stars out there, in other words, so many lives. Hermes wonders what the purpose of other living beings beyond Etheiry’s is. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-36)

Hermes: “So many stars, so many lives... For us, there may be no higher purpose than to live for our world, but what of the other living beings out there?” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer explores that Hermes expresses wonder and curiosity about the universe and the possibility of life beyond their own world. He knows that other beings in the universe might have different goals than them, even though theirs in Etheiry’s might be to live for their world. Hermes’ words also show an interest in the meaning of life and a desire to connect and understand. He says he wants to know what gives other beings’ lives meaning, which shows that he values the different experiences and points of view that exist in the world.

Hermes curious about what is their meaning of life that motivates them. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-37)

Hermes: “What is it that gives their lives meaning? That drives them day after day after day?” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer studies that Hermes poses a deep philosophical question about why and how life exists, and not just for people. He questions the motivation of all living things in the universe. It makes him wonder what it is that drives people to keep living, to persist, and to try, even though life is often hard. Similar to Nietzsche’s nihilism, Hermes recognizes that there might not be a higher purpose or perfect world that gives life value.

Hermes tells the player the reason why he creates Meteion and her sisters from dynamis. Because Hermes wanted to pose the question of the meaning of life to other beings on other stars. Meteion can traverse the vast void between the stars. This statement is shown in the quote below:

(Data number-38)

Hermes: “To pose that question to our undiscovered cousins, I created beings of dynamis, who can traverse the vast emptiness between the stars. Meteion and her sisters.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

The thesis writer understands the quotation above that Hermes refers to the creation of Meteion and her sisters, who are able to explore the vast void of the universe. Meteion and her sisters develops with a specific purpose: to ask questions to other unknown life forms in the universe. What gives their lives purpose and meaning is the question. This is part of Hermes’ quest to understand the meaning of life beyond their world.

Hermes tells the player that Meteion has many great sisters that travels to one and another stars in search of life. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-39)

Hermes: “She has a great many of them, and they have already departed on their journey. Traveling to one star, and then the next, in search of life.” (Quest: A Sentimental Gift (Level 86))

The thesis writer underlines the quotation above that Hermes speaks about Meteion and her sisters, who are dynamis beings that he made to travel through the huge empty space between the stars. Their job is to ask any intelligent life they find on other stars what gives life value. The phrase “in search of life” implies a search for the meaning of life, which is an essential topic in many philosophical discussions, including Nietzsche’s idea of nihilism.

The player accesses Hermes and Meteion’s past conversation memories with the help of Venat. Hermes talks with Meteion about the task he gives to Meteion and her sisters and it reminds him how little they understand creation and how universe defies imagination. This statement can be seen in the quest A Flower upon Your Return in Table 3 as shown below:

(Data number-40)

Hermes: “Every step of the way, I’ve been reminded how little we understand creation. How the universe defies imagination.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))

Hermes shows his respect and admiration for how large and complex the universe is. He recognizes that, despite all the knowledge and wisdom humans possess, there are still many things about the universe and the process of creation that humans cannot reach. The term “every step of the way” implies a journey or a

constant process of learning and discovery. With each new discovery or piece of knowledge learned, Hermes is reminded of how much more there is to learn and understand about the universe. Meanwhile, “How the universe defies imagination” pushes this idea even more. It implies that the universe’s reality is so complicated and huge that it exceeds our ability to imagine or conceptualize it. When people think about how big and complicated the world is, this could be a reflection on how little human can understand and imagine. This is in line with Nietzsche’s nihilism that traditional beliefs and ideals are not based in reality; objective truth is something people make up, not something that is naturally present in the world.

Meteion replies to Hermes’ statement, that they will know the answer which what other beings in the other stars live for. This statement can be seen in the quest A Flower upon Your Return in Table 3, as shown below:

(Data number-41)

Meteion: “But soon we won’t need to speculate. We’ll know the answers—what others live for!” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))

From the above quotation, the thesis writer explores that Meteion’s comment implies a comparable journey to understand the subjective meanings that other civilizations create for themselves. The phrase “we need not speculate” means that they will know more about things based on facts, not theories. Furthermore, “we will know the answer-to what other people live for” implies a quest to understand all the purposes and meanings that other civilizations establish for their lives. Meteion is excited to get the answer of what others live for. As what Metz Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy stated that people tend to pose one of three questions: “What are you talking about?”, “What is the meaning of life?”, and “Is life in fact

meaningful?” (Metz, 2007). Meteion’s statement reflects nihilistic viewpoint. She is not expecting a single definite answer to the question of what gives life meaning. Instead, she is open to the potential of various, diverse answers, which represent the universe’s diversity of life forms and cultures. Nietzsche’s theory of real-world nihilism is to be open to different meanings and not believe in a single, ultimate truth or meaning.

Hermes thinks that the beings in other stars are intelligent and very different from the beings in Etheiryrs. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-42)

Hermes: “Whatever intelligent beings that exist out there are bound to be vastly different from us.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))

From the above quotation, the thesis writer emphasizes that Hermes says that any intelligent life that might exist in the world would have probably evolved in different ways and under different conditions, which is why their bodies, cultures, and ways of thinking will be very different from the Etheiryrs people.

Hermes says from the previous statement that the intelligent beings exist out there are very different from the beings in Etheiryrs. Not only different, but also possess unique ways of thinking, Hermes adds. This statement is supported by the dialogue shown below:

(Data number-43)

Hermes: “Diverse in form and culture. Possessed of unique ways of thinking.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))

The thesis writer implies the quotation above that the way Hermes see and value the variety and uniqueness of living things, not just in how they look but also in their cultures and ways of thinking. Hermes' statement "unique ways of thinking" appears as an acceptance of these different points of view and a rejection of the idea of a single, perfect society or form. In the systematization of nihilism, Nietzsche says that "he conceived such a whole in order to be able to believe in his own value" (1968: 12). He posits that the idea of gods, objective truths, universal meanings, etc., was conceptualized by humans as a psychological aid to help them believe that their lives had meaningful value.

Hermes believes that other beings' purpose of life is completely different from the beings in Etheirys. This statement can be seen in the quest A Flower upon Your Return in Table 3, as shown below:

(Data number-44)

Hermes: "Their conception of life and its purpose will be no exception. Completely and utterly unlike ours." (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))

From the above quotation, the thesis writer learns that Hermes speaks about the different kinds of life and ideas that could exist in the world. He agrees that intelligent beings from other worlds might have very different ideas about life and its meaning than they do. This can be seen as a reflection of the belief that there is no absolute or universal truth.

Hermes continues, that whatever answers they receive, he will not just ignore it and will think about every answers seriously. This statement can be seen in the quest A Flower upon Your Return in Table 3, as shown below:

(Data number-45)

Hermes: “Yet whatever answers we receive, I will not dismiss them out of hand. No, I will think earnestly on them all.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))

The thesis writer emphasizes the quotation above that Hermes’ willingness to understand different points of view and keep an open mind. He states that he will continue to think about all of the answers he gets, no matter how different or difficult they may be, and to really think about it. Hermes is ready to deal with the world as it is, with all of its differences and complexity. He does not think that any answer or point of view is wrong or less important. Instead, he tries to understand them all.

Hermes explains that he will share the answers with the people of Etheiry's and reflect their own existence together. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-46)

Hermes: “Then I will share them with our people, that together we may contemplate our own existence.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer draws that Hermes says he wants to share with his own people the different points of view and answers he gets from other beings. He hopes that by doing this, they can all think about their lives and maybe get a better sense of their purpose and the meaning of life. It displays an awareness of the variety of ideas and experiences that exist in the world and a desire to interact with them in order to gain a deeper understanding of what existence is all about. “The value of life.”— Life is a Unique case; One must justify all existence and not only life— the justifying principle is one that explains life, too (Nietzsche,

1968: 375). Nietzsche says that nothing about life can survive without some kind of meaning, purpose, or support. Life is a “unique case” because, unlike some other things that might not need a reason to exist, life seems to need a reason to be here.

Hermes hopes that with all the answers he will get, Etheiry's will become a better place not only for man but for all life. This statement can be seen in the dialogue between Hermes and Meteion in the quest A Flower upon Your Return in Table 3, as shown below:

(Data number-47)

Hermes: “Perhaps then our star will become a better place—not only for man, but for all life.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))

The thesis writer draws the quotation above that Hermes expresses hope that by understanding and accepting the various points of view and responses he encounters, the world might become a better place for all living beings, not just humans. Hermes thinks that things can get better and change for the better. It means that they can make the world a better place by learning from and knowing different kinds of life. This could mean learning from the actions and experiences of different living things and then using what humans have learned to make choices and take actions that are good for all living things.

Hermes tells Meteion that even though he gives Meteion wings to soar in the sky, Hermes does not teach Meteion how to walk on earth. He does not want to bind another being. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-48)

Hermes: “Meteion. Though I gave you wings to soar the heavens, I did not teach you how to walk the earth. So loath was I to bind another living being.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))

The thesis writer emphasizes the quotation above that Hermes expresses sadness and responsibility for Meteion’s situation. The “wings to soar the heavens” are a metaphor for Meteion’s abilities and powers, which let her travel the universe and connect with different kinds of life. Hermes does admit, though, that he did not teach Meteion “how to walk the earth.” This could mean that he did not give her the skills or information she needed to deal with the difficulties and complexities of life on a more personal, grounded level. “So loath was I to bind another living being” shows that Hermes did not intend to limit or control Meteion. This shows that he values her independence and wants her to learn and grow on her own.

Hermes continues to tell Meteion that she will learn through the people she will meet in her journey. Hermes wants Meteion to learn to walk and run so much more. This statement can be seen through the dialogue in the quest A Flower upon Your Return, as shown below:

(Data number-49)

Hermes: “In the course of your long journey, you will learn from those you meet. Learn to walk and run and so much more.” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer observes that Hermes’ speech is a metaphor for life’s journey, highlighting the value of learning from others and personal improvement. “In the course of your long journey” refers to a process or trip that will last a long time. “You will learn from those you meet” means that

getting to know other people is an important part of this journey. This means interacting with other characters in the game. It means that everyone one meet has something to teach, like a new skill, a different point of view, or a lesson from their own life. In this case, “learn to walk and run and so much more” means to grow and develop as a person. Walking and running could be seen as basic skills or important stops along the way. Along with these basic skills, the phrase “and so much more” suggests that a lot of different situations and lessons are being learned. It may include emotional development, gaining insight, or learning new skills.

Hermes adds that when Meteion and her sisters return from their mission in search of the meaning of life, they will have a celebration to mark their homecoming and become older and wiser. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-50)

Hermes: “And when you return, older and wiser, we will have a celebration to mark your homecoming and coming of age both.”
(Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer draws that “return” in this case refers to Meteion’s final return to their home after her trip through the stars. The phrase “coming of age” refers to the knowledge and understanding Meteion is supposed to gain from meeting different kinds of living things. The word “celebration” means that Meteion’s growth and the useful information she would bring back are being recognized. Nietzsche’s idea says that there is no one absolute world or truth, and that people give their lives meaning and worth. In this light, Meteion’s journey can be seen as an attempt to learn about the different ways that different life forms in the world see the meaning of life.

Hermes tells Emet-Selch the tasks he gives to Meteion, which is to ask what other beings live for and what gives their lives meaning. This statement supports the dialog in the quest Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen in Table 3 shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-64)

Hermes: “I tasked her with asking what others live for. What gives their lives...meaning...” (Quest: A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87))

The thesis writer analyzes from the quotation above that Hermes gives Meteion the mission to ask other beings what they live for, which basically aims to find the meaning or purpose behind their lives. This task can be viewed as a direct encounter with nihilistic thought. By asking these questions, Meteion is essentially looking for the individual, subjective meanings that people give to their lives, which is consistent with Nietzsche’s philosophical views. This shows that Hermes is interested in learning different viewpoints and the reasons behind the behavior of different living beings. It suggests that meaning is subjective and changes from individual to individual that means there is no universal truth. Nietzsche (2006: 100) in *BEYOND GOOD AND EVIL* simply believes that anything that is a living and not a dying body... must be an embodied will to power; it will endeavor to grow, spread, seize, and become dominant -- not because of morality or immorality, but because it is alive and life is precisely Will to Power.

Meteion, as a dynamis being with an ability to read and project emotions, is able to communicate with the spirits of the dead. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-72)

Meteion: “We scoured historical records. Communed with the spirits of the deceased.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

From the excerpt above, the thesis writer learns that Meteion and her sisters communicate with the spirits of the deceased to find out why they died and find the meaning of life from the stars they inhabit. The statement “scoured historical records” means looking into the past in great detail, while “Communed with the spirits of the deceased” means trying to get in touch with the dead, to learn from their experiences. As shown in the game, the results often show a world full of pain, hopelessness, and disappointment. This fits with Nietzsche’s idea of nihilism because Meteion and her sisters realize that their attempts to find meaning or purpose in life may not work, which makes them feel hopeless and lead to an existential crisis.

Meteion hears the last will from those who are dying and they welcome the emotions into their own consciousness. This statement supports the dialog from Table 3 as shown below:

(Data number-73)

Meteion: “Heard the final testaments of the dying. Welcomed their shadowed hearts into our own.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer ponders that Meteion hears their last words, their last testaments, and takes in their despair, fear, and sadness. The statement “shadowed hearts” are the dark feelings and experiences that these dying civilizations are experiencing. Meteion lets these into her mind, becoming a vessel for their sadness to reach others. She sees how various civilizations attempt

different things to find meaning or end suffering, but all of them fail and end up feeling hopeless and wanting to disappear. They abandoned relationships, sought infinity, avoided violence, and even abandoned all things that cause misery, yet all of these route's results in societal collapse, disillusionment, or lack of will to live. This fits with Nietzsche's idea of nihilism, because these societies have not discovered any real or lasting value in their lives.

Meteion adds that one race strives to create a world without hostility. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-74)

Meteion: "One race had striven to create a world bereft of animosity." (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

The thesis writer actualizes the quotation above that the race Meteion mentions in this quotation tries to get rid of all kinds of hatred and strife so that the world can remain peaceful. The race's efforts to eliminate hostility can be seen as a form of nihilism, as they reject the inherent value of negative emotions and conflict in life.

Meteion talks about a society that give up on relationships to avoid conflict, which ended up being the downfall of that society. This statement supports the dialog in Table 3 as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-75)

Meteion: "They renounced relationships to avoid interpersonal strife, and in so doing brought about societal collapse." (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer actualizes that Meteion talks about a society that gave up relationships to avoid fighting with each other. But this choice caused their society to fall apart. Ironically, the people's efforts to get rid of disagreements and conflict lead to the end of their society. The civilization Meteion describes reflects this nihilistic perspective. In order to avoid conflict, they discarded relationships, which are often the source of meaning and purpose in life. This, however, results in the collapse of their society, demonstrating Nietzsche's idea that rejecting life's basic structures (such as relationships) can have negative effects.

Meteion continues that one race abandons war and devotes itself to enriching its people. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-76)

Meteion: "One race had renounced war and devoted itself to the enrichment of its people." (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

The thesis writer implies the quotation above that is part of Meteion's report about her journey across several civilizations. In particular, it refers to a race that chose to stop fighting and work on making people's lives better instead. In this quotation, Meteion talks about the endings of different societies she meets. Each one makes different decisions in its search for meaning and happiness, but all of them ended up in despair and destruction.

Sadly, the race that Meteion mentions in the previous quotation is defeated. Although they destroyed the enemy in revenge, they could not regain their former glory. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-77)

Meteion: “They were conquered. Though they destroyed the enemy in reprisal, they could not regain their former glory.”
(Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

The thesis writer analyzes the quotation above that Meteion tells the story of what happens to a society that gives up war and works to make its people better in the previous quotation. But they end up defeated, and even though they fight back and destroyed their enemy, they cannot get back to their old glory. This sentence shows the sad circle of fighting and losing, where even winning cannot bring back what is lost. Even though they try hard to make their lives have meaning, they are defeated and are unable to get back up. The phrase “former glory” is as a symbol of higher values or goals that used to give life meaning and purpose. Being defeated and not being able to get back to their previous glory could be a sign of losing these higher values, which can lead to nihilism. This shows that nihilist beings believe there is no objective truth, purpose, or real value in life.

Meteion continues to explain that another race searches the infinity because they think that limited time was the cause of all issues. This statement can be seen in the quest Caging the Messenger shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-78)

Meteion: “One race had concluded that finite time was the root of all woes. Aspiring to shatter its shackles, they went in search of infinity.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer understands that one of the races Meteion encounters in other stars concludes that finite time is the root of destruction and misery. The race wants to prevent that destruction, and they end up going in search of infinity. Nietzsche’s nihilism is often linked to the idea of an infinity. This

can be read from the lens of Nihilism where they do not believe in their own fate and world. Therefore, they search for infinity to change the fate. Nietzsche (1968: 12) says that “At bottom, man has lost the faith in his own value when no infinitely valuable whole works through him; i.e., he conceived such a whole in order to be able to believe in his own value”.

Meteion continues, that the race in the previous quotation finds nothing about infinity, nor is infinity real. Besides that, time or death can be manipulated. In the end they give up on themselves and their future. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-79)

Meteion: “They discovered nothing is infinite, and that neither time or death can be cheated. Disillusioned, they gave up on the future—and themselves.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

From the above quotation, the thesis writer indicates that Meteion reports one of the stars where other civilizations are destroyed because they give up on their lives and future. The reason behind it is that they find nothing in their journey to search for something infinite and cheat time and death. Nihilism is usually related to death because people cannot find the meaning of their lives and give up on their future.

Meteion explains that there is another race that throws away all the things in their lives that cause sadness and hopes to only experience happiness. This statement can be seen in the quest Caging the Messenger in Table 3, as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-80)

Meteion: “One race had discarded all things that gave rise to sorrow, hoping to have only joy.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

The civilization that Meteion describes, turns to a form of nihilism. By trying to get rid of everything that makes them sad, they have inadvertently removed the purpose and value of life. This is in line with Nietzsche’s idea that suffering is an essential part of being human and trying to get rid of it can leave human feeling empty and hopeless.

Meteion adds that the race in the previous quotation finds that joy loses its meaning in the absence of sorrow, which makes them lose the will to live. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-81)

Meteion: “They found joy lost its savor in the absence of sorrow, and lost their will to live.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

The thesis writer investigates the above quote that the Meteion race is mentioned as losing the will to live because they cannot find the joy they desire as they discard sorrow. Joy and sadness are like two sides of the same coin; they are both a part of being human. Without sorrow, joy loses its meaning because there is no contrast to show its goodness. Nihilism, the theory of Friedrich Nietzsche, says that life has no objective meaning, purpose, or intrinsic value. This idea fits with that view. A reddit user named tormenteddragon comments on a post entitled *Endwalker’s story and the theme of nihilism (6.5)* that “The lesson is that joy doesn’t come from eliminating all problems—that’s an impossible goal since you’ll only end up having new problems take their place.” If the suffering and oppressed

lost the faith that they have the right to despise the will to power, they would enter the phase of hopeless despair (Nietzsche, 1968: 37).

Meteion finds many civilizations that fall apart or perish in various ways. He comes to the conclusion that these civilizations, although different, all believe that they have done their best during their lifetime. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-82)

Meteion: “Though worlds apart, these people shared a belief. The belief that they had tried their best.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer ponders that Meteion’s statements come after she completed her assignment and reported on what she discovered. She meets people from many different cultures, and each is struggling to find meaning or make their lives better. Meteion realizes that although they are very different and live far apart, they all believe in the same thing: they have done their best to reach their full potential.

Meteion notes that all of these beings in other stars believe that they try their best and are working toward their full potential with each step they take. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-83)

Meteion: “That they had tried to fulfill their potential, with every step and success.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

The thesis writer explores the quotation above that Meteion is able to deeply understand the suffering of these civilizations because she can read and project

feelings. She come to the conclusion that all beings, everywhere in the universe, think that they have done their best and are taking steps towards their full potential.

Meteion continues, despite their efforts to overcome difficulties and find meaning in their lives, these civilizations eventually faced despair and extinction, understanding that negative feelings like fear, sorrow, rage, and loneliness are an unavoidable part of life. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-84)

Meteion: “That they would never be free of fear and sorrow, anger and despair—of loneliness—so long as they yet lived.”
(Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

Meteion shows a deep understanding of the human condition by recognizing that everyone will feel negative feelings like fear, sadness, anger, hopelessness, and loneliness as long as they are living. Friedrich Nietzsche posits the idea of nihilism, which is the view that life has no real meaning, purpose or value. Often, this leads people to reject moral or religious rules. According to Nietzsche, realizing that life is pointless can cause one to experience bad feelings such as those that Meteion talks about.

c) **Disbelief in True World**

When people understand that life does not have a grand purpose or ultimate goal, Nietzsche says in *The Will to Power* that they might try to escape this reality by calling the world of becoming (the world that is always changing) false and making up a “true world” that is beyond it. People enter the last stage of nihilism when they realize that the “true world” they think, exists only a kind of a lie based

on their psychological needs and that they have no right to it. But as soon as man finds out how that world is fabricated solely from psychological needs, and how he has absolutely no right to it, the last form of nihilism comes into being: it includes disbelief in any metaphysical world and forbids itself any belief in a true world (Nietzsche, 1968: 13). This kind of nonbelief includes the refutation on believing in any spiritual world and the refutation on believing in a real world.

After Meteion finishes her sisters' report about the findings, Meteion adds that a civilization destroys itself as a substitute for the answer to the questions. She also finds no other intelligent beings. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-71)

Meteion: "Upon revealing this to me, entity elected to self-terminate in lieu of providing answer to question. No other intelligent life-forms found." (Quest: Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87))

The thesis writer learns the quotation above that the entity who meets Meteion decides to end its own life instead of answering a question. Meteion also says she cannot discover any other intelligent beings. This can be seen as a rejection of Meteion's question, which is the meaning or purpose of life. In Nietzsche's nihilism, the awareness that life may lack inherent meaning or purpose might lead to feelings of alienation and despair, similar to Meteion sisters' journey across the universe.

Meteion and her sisters' song of oblivion can bring the final day to the star they aim. Meteion and her sisters lend their voice to bring the final day to those souls who want it. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-85)

Meteion: “Even now, their souls cry out for oblivion. And to this song of anguish, I lend my voice. We lend our voice.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer investigates that Meteion is showing that she feels empathy with the souls that seek death, which means the end of life. The fact she sings on this “song of anguish” shows that she feels their pain and wants them to stop even more. This shows that she can take in and show other people’s feelings. The disbelief in true world can be seen in Meteion’s compassion for souls desperately seeking death. She sees others’ pain and sorrow, and this affects her own emotional state and actions to sing the song of oblivion.

Meteion wants to sing the song of oblivion to the Etheiryys people, because she believes that she can free the people from the pain of existence. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-86)

Meteion: “O beloved mankind, shimmering jewels of beautiful Etheiryys... Rejoice, for we will free you from the cruel yoke of existence.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

The thesis writer investigates the quotation above that “Beloved mankind” and “shimmering jewels” are words Meteion uses to describe the people of Etheiryys. She tells them to be joyful because she and her sisters will “free” them from life’s “cruel yoke” which mean she will sing the song of oblivion to bring the final day to Etheiryys. Her message is one of despair rather than hope, matching with ideas of passive nihilism in Nietzsche’s disbelief in true world. Nietzsche (1968: 130) writes that “The true life is only a faith (i.e., a self-deception, a madness). The whole of

struggling, battling, actual existence, full of splendor and darkness, only a bad, false existence: the task is to be redeemed from it.”

Meteion says that the living beings in Etheirys do not have to suffer in their life and death is beautiful because they will know peace and serenity. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-87)

Meteion: “There is no need to struggle in vain, for in nihilism awaits salvation. You will know peace and serenity...and it will be beautiful.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer analyzes that Meteion tells the people of Etheirys that they do not need to struggle in vain because salvation awaits them in “nihilism,” or “oblivion.” She says that not existing will bring them peace, beauty, and quiet. Meteion believes that life is full of pointless pain, which is why she offers oblivion as a way to escape the cruelty of life. She comes to think that life and its pain are so useless that not existing is better, just like Nietzsche’s idea. Nietzsche thinks nihilism as the idea that life has no meaning, purpose, or value. He believes it can lead to passive nihilism, the idea that life is miserable that we are better off not existing.

Meteion reveals to the player that their nest will be at the edge of the universe, which is almost impossible to get there. That star is a dark dead worlds hoard sorrow and suffering. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-88)

Meteion: “We will make our nest at the edge of the universe, and there in the dark of dead worlds hoard sorrow and suffering.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer actualizes that Meteion expresses a desire to escape to the edge of universe to make a nest for her and her sisters and hoard sorrow and misery. It is possible to see Meteion's words through the lens of existential nihilism, which is the idea that life has no meaning or worth on its own. The "dark of dead worlds" may serve as an example for the emptiness or nothingness that nihilism is often linked to.

Meteion plans to sing the song of oblivion with her sisters in the star she mentions in the previous quotation, which locates in the edge of the universe. This statement can be seen below:

(Data number-89)

Meteion: "There we will sing, our chorus ever louder and ever clearer, that our song may reach even this aether-shrouded star."
(Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer explores that Meteion wants to sing a chorus that gets "ever louder and ever clearer," so that their song can reach even the "aether-shrouded star" in which mean Etheiry's. The song she means is song of oblivion, which is a song to bring the final day or destruction to the star she aims. This fits the idea of nihilism because Meteion finds no meaning in life from other stars and want to bring destruction to the leftover stars.

Meteion's sisters gets the answer they find in another stars, which is there is no meaning in life because all civilizations are destroyed. Then, Meteion offers to give the destruction to Etheiry's. This statement supports the dialog in Table 3 as shown below:

(Data number-90)

Meteion: “Such is the answer we have found in the stars. Such is the gift we now offer to Etheiryys.” (Quest: Caging the Messenger (Level 87))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer ponders that Meteion refers to the knowledge or insights her sisters obtain from their exploration in other stars. Their exploration ends up with the reports that no civilization found in any stars because of certain problems and then destroyed. The “gift” she means in this quotation is her song of oblivion, which is a destruction to Etheiryys. Nietzsche’s disbelief in true world connects to Meteion’s journey and the despair that she sees. A Reddit user called theRazielim comments on a post entitled *[Spoilers: 6.0] Nothing in life matters* that “I would argue that both we and Meteion are nihilists, but Meteion goes “oh well, might as well die then” and we go “oh well, might as well enjoy our time with our friends as much as we can then”.” Meanwhile, a user called Jaxyl replies that “We’re not nihilists, we’re existentialists. We acknowledge there is no greater meaning outside of suffering but we make our own purpose all the same.”

Meteion tells the player and his/her companions they should have not come to find Meteion because she will deliver the final day into Etheiryys with the song of oblivion. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-91)

Meteion: “Why have you come? All you had to do was wait. I would’ve delivered to you your ends.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))

The thesis writer indicates the quotation above that Meteion refers “you” to the player and his/her other comrades who are on a journey to stop Meteion to sing the song of oblivion because they want to save Etheiryys, the star they currently

living in. Meteion will sing the song of oblivion to deliver them to death and tell the player to remain in Etheirys. This is a clear example of the destructive side of nihilism, where denying the value of life makes people want to end it. It reaches its maximum of relative strength as a violent force of destruction—as active nihilism (Nietzsche, 2006: 18). Meteion’s statement can be understood as active nihilism while relating it to Nietzsche’s writings.

Meteion does not understand why the player and his/her companions try to stop her because she knows that all life is destined to end. This statement supports the dialog in Table 3 as shown below:

(Data number-92)

Meteion: “I don’t understand. All life is destined to end.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer implies that Meteion questions the player and his/her comrades in the ship where the player and his/her comrades use to find Meteion’s nest, which is in the star located in the edge of universe. Meteion fail to understand the reason why the player wants to save Etheirys from her song of oblivion and suffers instead of waiting for her to bring them to death. Nihilism” an ideal of the highest degree of powerfulness of the spirit, the over-richest life—partly destructive, partly ironic (Nietzsche, 1968:14).

Meteion questions the player the reason why he/she wants to stop her song of oblivion and to suffer in the meaningless existence. This statement can be seen in the quest Unto the Heavens in Table 3 as shown below:

(Data number-93)

Meteion: “Why choose to prolong your suffering?” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer analyzes that Meteion continues her question to the player and his/her comrades in the same ship. Meteion is being curious about why people or groups choose to stay in pain and suffering when there may be other options. The option she means is to deliver their ends which is the song of oblivion. It represents disbelief in a “true world” in which suffering is an unavoidable aspect of life and instead promotes the possibility of alternate viewpoints and experiences.

Meteion explains that effort, ambition, and love are meaningless. Meanwhile, happiness is easily stolen by events or problems beyond human control. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-94)

Meteion: “Effort, ambition, love—they amount to naught. Happiness, should you find it, is inevitably lost. Stolen away by events beyond your control.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer understands that Meteion shows a feeling that human actions and feelings are pointless. She says that no matter how hard someone tries to reach their goals or how much they love someone, these things are unimportant in the end. Happiness is short-lived and can be taken away by things that are out of one’s control. Because life is unpredictable and chaotic, the “true world” of lasting happiness and satisfaction that people seek might not exist. Nietzsche (1968: 12) states that “At bottom, man has lost the faith in his own value when no infinitely valuable whole works through him.”

Meteion expresses her belief that existence is a tragic accident, lacking logic or meaning in it. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-95)

Meteion: “There is no logic nor meaning in it. You think there is, convince yourselves, but it’s all a cruel accident.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))

The thesis writer ponders the quotation above that Meteion expresses the idea that people think their lives have a purpose or a sense, but she sees it all as a “cruel accident.” This viewpoint is consistent with nihilistic philosophy, which contends that life lacks a higher purpose or order in the universe. Nietzsche’s nihilism is often linked to the idea that life has no meaning, purpose, or worth in and of itself. This viewpoint may be linked with Nietzsche’s statement of the “Death of God,” which refers to the rejection of the belief in a universally applicable, absolute ethics or higher purpose set forth by a higher power. A Reddit user named esgaldr comments on a post entitled *[Spoiler: 6.0] I see a lot of “what if X never happened” comments and... that “Much as we meme about it, I think the idea of “killing god” is very central to FFXIV. Actual philosophers here will have to forgive me, but I’ve heard the term used to describe removing the possibility of the ideal and forcing oneself to contend with reality. In one way or another, that’s what all the primals and tempering were--devotion to a savior or ideal that created a barrier to pursuing difficult but realistic alternatives.”*

Meteion asks the player to realize the truth that she is speaking about, in which her viewpoint in the previous dialog can be seen if one were to look up at the night sky is a reflection of existence. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-96)

Meteion: “Come now, I speak the truth. A truth you would recognize if you looked up at the night sky.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))

Meteion is stating that she is telling the truth and asking the player to agree with her. The “truth” she is talking about is there is no logic or meaning in life and it is all just a cruel accident, and how big the universe is and how many lives it holds. Unfortunately, the big universe and stars are no longer have any civilization living in it because they are destroyed. So does Nietzsche’s Disbelief in the True World. Both of them reject the idea of a greater, divine order or purpose and instead focus on the truth of existence. Nietzsche (1968: 96) writes in *The Will to Power* that “For action—has no meaning, action binds one to existence, but all existence has no meaning.”

Meteion implies that the unbroken emptiness of the night sky, which is cold, dark, and silent, is a reflection of the basic meaninglessness of existence. This statement can be seen in the quest Unto the Heavens as shown below:

(Data number-97)

Meteion: “Unbroken emptiness. Cold, dark, and silent. Your world, like every other, is but a blemish upon its perfect fabric.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer learns that Meteion speaks of the universe as a vast, empty, cold, dark and silent space. This makes it sound like the presence of the world, including the world of players, is an anomaly or flaw in the perfect emptiness of space. She says that life is unnatural and disrupts the perfect void of the universe. This is relevant to Nietzsche’s disbelief of the “true world”

and his claim that the universe has no fundamental meaning or purpose, where its existence is more of an anomaly than the fulfillment of the universe's destiny.

Meteion states that the world is a place of suffering, where joy is temporary and sorrow is constant. This emphasizes her belief in the futility and meaninglessness of existence, which she believes cannot be overstated. This statement can be seen in the quest *Unto the Heavens* in Table 3 as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-98)

Meteion: "Life is an anomaly. It is unnatural and cannot continue. The sooner you accept this, the easier it will be." (Quest: *Unto the Heavens* (Level 89))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer actualizes that Meteion represents a nihilistic view by saying that life is strange, abnormal and cannot continue on. From this point of view, there is a deep sense of hopelessness and disappointment with life. Meteion's words imply that she thinks life is basically flawed and cannot continue because it is full of suffering and change. Meteion tells the player that the sooner the player accepts death and the final day, the easier it will be. Meteion thinks of life as something strange and different from how things should be. This is similar to Nietzsche's criticism of the idea of a "true world" as denying the value of life.

Meteion knows the feelings and emotions of the player because her sisters sense the same feelings that once existed in many other stars that are long gone before the player's star. This statement supports the dialog in Table 3, as shown below:

(Data Number-99)

Meteion: “I know it well. For the same passion once burned in many a star before yours.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))

The thesis writer indicates in the quotation above that Meteion acknowledges a desire she witnesses in many other stars or civilizations before she comes across the player’s star, Etheirys. She implies that this intense passion, which possibly drives the actions of these societies, ended up destroying them. Meteion’s words show how societies and their driving forces change over time. Nietzsche’s belief that there is no “true world” or ultimate goal that may prevent the unavoidable fall or end of life as it is known.

Meteion continues the previous dialog that the civilization she means is already gone because of many calamities and hardships those civilizations face. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-100)

Meteion: “Suffocated and extinguished now.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer understands that Meteion refers to the strong feelings she feels for other people or the loss of hope or life. “Suffocated” and “extinguished” both mean that something died violently or by force from the previous quotation, which once burned in many a star before Etheirys, usually after a fight or resistance. “suffocated” and “extinguished” can be a metaphor for the despair and loss of meaning that comes with the disbelief in a true world.

Meteion tells the player that he/she reached her ultimatum, which is her nest, where she mentions in the previous dialogue that it is located on the edge of the universe. Her ultimatum is a place where emotions dictate reality. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-101)

Meteion: “You approach the bounds of my Ultimatum, where emotions dictate reality.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer analyzes that Meteion refers to a place called “ultimatum,” which means the nest of her and her sisters, a place where feelings can change the reality or truth. She says that within the limits of her Ultimatum, emotions are more than just inside things; they have real effects on the world. Meteion’s realm, where emotions shape reality, reflects Nietzsche’s view that realities are constructed through subjective experiences, emotions, and perspectives. Nietzsche argues that the concept of a true world is a construct with no basis in reality. Pratt (2023) quotes Nietzsche’s writings that “Every belief, every considering something-true,” “is necessarily false because there is simply no true world”. Meteion’s Ultimatum can be interpreted as a space that embodies this Nietzschean revaluation, where the subjective emotional realities of individuals are the only “truths” that exist. Nietzsche in *The Gay Science* (1974: 203) states that “Thoughts are the shadows of our feelings—always darker, emptier, and simpler.” The thesis writer implies that thoughts are mere reflections of emotions, but they do not fully capture the depth and complexity of these emotions. Like shadows, thoughts are darker, less substantial (emptier), and less complex (more straightforward) than the feelings that produce them.

Meteion adds that her nest is where resignation and acceptance come together to embrace the end. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-102)

Meteion: “Where resignation and acceptance unite to embrace the end.” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer underlines that Meteion’s ultimatum, which is a star at the edge of the universe, is in a state of accepting and giving up on life. Acceptance is the process of coming to terms with the fact one will die, while resignation is the act of admitting that one will die. Death is one example of the “end” that is being accepted. Another example is the “end of all existence,” which may refer to the end of the universe or life as humans know it. Meteion’s statement can be understood as a rejection of the idea that there is a single, objective meaning or purpose to life, which is the “true world,” and an acceptance that life will end eventually.

Meteion continues, where even the toughest people, who are hanging on to life by the threads, cannot get ahead or grow. It refers to a tough or unfriendly environment that makes it hard to grow and stay alive, even when people are trying hard. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-103)

Meteion: “Where those who yet valiantly cling to life cannot thrive...” (Quest: Unto the Heavens (Level 89))

The thesis writer investigates the quotation above that Meteion considers how pointless it is to insist on living in a place or state where surviving and thriving are not possible. This is a comment on the harsh realities of the world she knows, where

different civilizations are unable to get past the problems they face and cannot really thrive, no matter how hard they try. It suggests a nihilistic view of the world, in which nature sees life as meaningless and pointless, especially when faced with extreme hardship or sadness.

Meteion states her reason for finding this star on the edge of the universe, which fills with life, but the civilization is no longer there. This statement supports the dialog in Table 3, as shown below:

(Data number-104)

Meteion: “This is how I found it when I arrived. Another star which once pulsed with life, but no longer.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer underlines that Meteion talks about another star that is the same as many other destroyed stars. She finds that this star once supports life but no longer does, just like many other stars. Her comment about finding a dead star that used to be home to life shows how temporary and fragile life is. It means that there are no absolute truths about how long or how well societies will do in the universe.

Meteion continues explaining that she does not know why there is no more civilization. None can tell if it is because of invasion, sickness, or suicide. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-105)

Meteion: “How it ended, I do not know. Invasion, sickness, suicide—none can say.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer learns that Meteion is not sure what happens to the civilizations she encounters on her journey to the star at the edge of the universe. Some of the things she thinks might have taken their lives are an invasion, illness, or suicide, but she says she cannot say for sure. This idea is shown by Meteion's uncertainty about what will happen to the societies she encounters. Nietzsche believes there is no single "true" purpose or objective, so she is unsure what their true objective is.

Meteion says that the civilization is gone, and no one is left to speak up on what happens in their star. Meteion tells the player to search every place or area in the star, but the player will not find any clue. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-106)

Meteion: "None lived to speak for the dead. They are gone. Gone. Search all you like, but you'll only end up turning back." (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer studies that Meteion claims that no survivors or witnesses are alive to speak of the civilization. She says that the people who lived there are gone; anyone who tries to find them or discover what happened will fail and have to turn back. Her statement indicates that these civilizations are beyond salvation or recovery, with no way to share their history left. This view is similar to a nihilistic view, which says that life has no meaning, purpose, or worth in and of itself.

Meteion tells the player that the player does not catch her because Meteion's current form is just a small part of a bigger and more powerful entity that resides in a "dead sun." This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-107)

Meteion: "You think you've caught me? This form is barely a drop from the ocean that swells within the dead sun." (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))

The thesis writer explores the quotation above that Meteion claims her huge power and existence by saying that her present form is like a drop in the ocean inside a "dead sun." This means that Meteion is saying that her present form or manifestation is not even close to what she is really capable of or powerful. The "dead sun" represents a massive source of energy or life that is currently dormant or inactive. Meteion's words can be seen as an affirmation of her many sides and abilities, a rejection of a singular and limited identity, and her overwhelming power that is yet to be fully recognized.

Meteion is talking to the player who is still alive because his/her friends protect her, but the player needs to be careful because their support will not last forever. This statement supports the dialog in Table 3, as shown below:

(Data number-108)

Meteion: "Even so, I could easily unmake you. You are only still alive because of your comrades. But they cannot protect you forever." (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))

The thesis writer underlines that Meteion expresses a sense of superiority from the quotation above. She hints that the player's survival is not because he/she is strong but because the player's comrades are there for them, and she says that

this protection will not last forever. This shows a nihilistic view, where people think that trying to stay alive and look out for each other is pointless because of a powerful force or fate. Nihilism in *THE ANTICHRIST* (2016: 46) states that “Life itself appears to me as an instinct for growth, for survival, for the accumulation of forces, for *power*: whenever the will to power fails there is disaster. My contention is that all the highest values of humanity have been emptied of this will—that the values of *decadence*, of *nihilism*, now prevail under the holiest names.” The writer implies that Nietzsche sees life as an inherent impulse to develop, survive, strengthen, and influence. He thinks bad things happen when people try to get power or influence but fail. He says that the desires for power are no longer part of the most important ideals that people have held dear. People still hold these values sacred or very important, but more and more people are embracing values that show decline and the idea that life has no point.

Meteion tells the player that until the player’s comrades die, Meteion will satisfy herself by watching the player suffer. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-109)

Meteion: “Until they fade away, I’ll satisfy myself with watching you try—and fail—to find a way out of this lifeless place.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer investigates that Meteion is talking to the player, who is lost or stuck in empty place which is the star in the edge of universe. She takes a sarcastic pleasure in watching the player’s futile attempts to leave or find a solution in a universe devoid of life. Meteion’s words

give off a sense of hopelessness and fate, as if trying to change things will only end in failure. Meteion's viewpoint aligns with Nietzsche's belief that life lacks an inherent, objective meaning or purpose. Nietzsche says that the search for a "true world" or absolute meaning is pointless, which is what she says about the player's attempts.

Meteion tells the player and his/her comrades that they cannot go further to Meteion's nest, in purpose of stopping the final day. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-110)

Meteion: "Here the path ends. There is no way to reach our nest."
(Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))

The thesis writer investigates the quotation above that Meteion tells the player that his/her journey has come to an end and that the player cannot continue any further to get to the place she calls "nest." This sentence could be metaphor or literal, which means that the player has reached a point where they are unable to progress any further, either because of physical barriers, their limited abilities, or the meaninglessness of their goal which is to stop Meteion's song of oblivion and save Etheirys from the final day.

Meteion continues that in their current place which is the star in the edge of universe, the civilization gives up and accepts their fate. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-111)

Meteion: "I told you. Resignation and acceptance reign in this place." (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer explores that Meteion tells the player again that the location or area he/she is right now fills with the feelings of resignation and acceptance of death. It is a place where hope and disagreement are abandoned. “The concept “the true world” insinuates that this world is untruthful, deceptive, dishonest, inauthentic, inessential—and consequently also not a world adapted to our needs (— inadvisable to adapt oneself to it; better to resist it)” (Nietzsche, 1968: 320).

Meteion refers to the civilization who grows to hate life and therefore reject it. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-112)

Meteion: “The rejection of life by those who came to curse it.”
(Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer understands that Meteion talks about the civilizations she meets that are against life itself, probably because they go through too much pain. These societies reach a point where they are unable to see any point in living and therefore rejects it, which could lead to the end of themselves or a desire for non-existence as a whole. Meteion’s observation of civilizations rejecting life reflects Nietzsche’s belief that existence has no inherent value or purpose.

Meteion talks about the people who experiences disappointment because there is no answer for their prayer, their dream is not come true, and their hard work does not pay off. This statement supports the dialog in Table 3 as shown below:

(Data number-113)

Meteion: “Those whose dreams were unfulfilled. Whose prayers were unheard. Whose labors were unrewarded.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer learns that Meteion represents those whose dreams are never realized, whose requests for help go unanswered, and whose hard work goes unappreciated. Meteion’s statement suggests that the beliefs people hold dear, such as hard work being rewarded and their views being heard, may be illusory, with oblivion being the only real outcome, similar to Nietzsche’s claim that the “true world” people have historically believed in does not exist.

Meteion states that hope cannot deliver the player and his/her comrades into despair, and Meteion’s nest is beyond of reach. This statement can be seen in the quest Forge Ahead as shown below:

(Data number-114)

Meteion: “Hope cannot deliver you unto hopelessness. Our refuge is beyond you.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer actualizes that Meteion thinks that there is only hopelessness left. She and her sisters give up and go somewhere the player is unable to get to. This negative view relates to Nietzsche’s idea of “Disbelief in True World.” Nietzsche argues against believing in a “true” world or any meaning in life. Meteion’s rejection of hope and retreat into meaninglessness show that she has lost faith in any “true world” that offers a reason for living.

Meteion declares that struggle will not help the player and bring his/her comrades’ peace. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-115)

Meteion: “Struggle will avail you naught, nor will it grant your comrades peace.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer explores that Meteion expresses a sense of nihilism, which is the belief that life is without meaning, purpose, or value. Meteion’s statement above reflects this view because her statement “struggle will avail you naught,” implies that efforts or difficulties are meaningless. The second statement which “nor will it grant your comrade peace” means that the struggle will not bring peace or comfort to the players’ comrades.

Meteion offers the player to take away his/her troubles, acknowledging that the player suffers a lot. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-116)

Meteion: “Come, let me relieve you of your burden. You have suffered enough.” (Quest: Forge Ahead (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer ponders that Meteion invites the player to end the player’s pain, implying that she can lift the player’s heavy burden. This means that she is able to end the player’s life and struggle because the player suffers enough. Meteion’s statement expresses the loss of hope and despair that can come when life fails to live up to the expectations set by faith in a “true world” or greater purpose.

Meteion and her sister merges, becoming a monster which is called The Endsinger. The Endsinger shows an increasingly high level of rage. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-117)

The Endsinger: “Ahhh, the rage... It rises... Rises...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer learns the quotation above that Meteion and her sisters' anger and resentment are rising, which gets worse by her ability to take on and reflect on the emotions of others. Meteion's transformation and rage can be seen in the perspective of Nietzsche's concept of Nihilism and his disbelief in the “True World.” Nihilism, as defined by Nietzsche, is the rejection of religion and moral ideals, which is frequently coupled with the belief that existence is pointless.

The Endsinger questions the player's right to live and have hope, while The Endsinger states that the other beings die in pain and suffer. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-118)

The Endsinger: “We die in pain. We die in suffering! Who are you to live? Who are you to hope!?” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer analyzes that as so many people suffer and die, The Endsinger questions the player character's right to hope and live. This shows The Endsinger's own despair as well as the despair of all the people it takes in. The Endsinger reflects on the pain of many lives and now thinks that life is painful and possesses no point. The Endsinger's questioning reflects the nihilistic aspects of Nietzsche's philosophy, which denies the existence of a true world and views life as fraught with suffering. This is a form of nihilism which fails to value the chance of hope or joy in life. Nietzsche (1968: 13) in *The Will to Power* states

that Existence has no goal or end; any comprehensive unity in the plurality of events is lacking: the character of existence is not “true,” is false.

The Endsinger tells the player that she is not going to suffer alone and intends to inflict pain on others. This statement can be seen in the quest Endwalker as shown below:

(Data number-119)

The Endsinger: “We will not suffer alone...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer explores that The Endsinger claims that she will not be the only one who suffers. This implies that she seeks to inflict misery, despair, and, eventually, oblivion on others, including the player. Her goal is for everyone to feel her pain. This is taken to an extreme by The Endsinger’s nihilism. Since she fails to discover a “true world” without pain, she rejects all meaning and wants everyone to suffer the same amount.

The Endsinger suffers great pain and believes that others should experiences similar pain. The Endsinger threaten the player that he/she will go through the same pain as The Endsinger. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-120)

The Endsinger: “All will know our pain...You will be battered and torn and made to crawl.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer explores the quotation above that The Endsinger’s words show how they (Meteion and her sisters) feels about their hopelessness and pain. They want other people to understand this pain by going through it themselves, which comes from a nihilistic view that life is full of pain and has no purpose. It

fits with Nietzsche's idea of "disbelief in a true world" because The Endsinger rejects a single, objective view of truth or morality. Instead, they stand by their own view, which is formed by their own suffering. A Reddit user named ChrisMurray comments on a post entitled *[Spoiler: 6.0]. I see a lot of "what if X never happened" comments and...* that "Endsinger ended up being the worst take on nihilism. "Everything is meaningless because everything is fleeting, so everything must end now"."

The Endsinger says that the player will feel sorrow and helplessness, and that he/she will eventually curse their own helplessness and the end of their life. Because The Endsinger thinks that all humans will suffer and lose hope. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-121)

The Endsinger: "You will weep and wail and curse your impotence. Curse your life as it fades." (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer ponders that The Endsinger says that she is going to cause the player so much pain that he/she will weep, wail, and swear in agony as his/her life ends. The Endsinger wants the player to feel the same pain and hopelessness that she gathers from many societies from other stars. One of the main ideas in Nietzsche's theory is existential despair and helplessness, which is reflected in Endsinger's words. Nietzsche thought that suffering is an intrinsic component of human existence and that people often feel helpless in the face of their suffering.

The Endsinger conveys the feelings of suffering and hopelessness from the previous quotation and continues with her experiences with death. This statement supports the quotation from the quest Endwalker as shown below:

(Data number-122)

The Endsinger: “As we did! As we died!” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer emphasizes that the quotation above represents the sorrow of The Endsinger, who is aware of the fate and the hopelessness of the other beings’ existence. “As we did! As we died!” is repeated over and over to stress that everyone suffers and feels the same way. “Death. — One must convert the stupid physiological fact into a moral necessity. So to live that one can also will at the right time to die!” (Nietzsche, 1968: 484).

Endsinger shows a deep loss and hopelessness. The Endsinger, a being that represents the hopelessness of many souls, is talking about their experience of intense suffering and how pointless their attempts to end it. This makes them feel like giving up. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-123)

The Endsinger: “Such pain and sorrow we felt... Such anguish and rage... We tried. We tried. But it was no use...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer studies that The Endsinger is showing her hopelessness and anger at being unable to stop the suffering and pain she sees in the world. The repeated phrase “We tried” emphasizes the tireless effort and determination that fails, leading to a sense of hopelessness and uselessness. As

the statement says, this can lead to existential depression if one thinks their life is full of pain and problems that seem impossible to solve.

The Endsinger explains that opposing or being afraid of death can cause pain, while accepting it can bring peace. This statement supports the dialog in Table 3, as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-124)

The Endsinger: “Only when we surrendered did we find release.
Only when we embraced death.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer understands that The Endsinger makes one think about accepting, giving up, and how death can change things. The first phrase, “Only when we surrendered did we find release,” implies that The Endsinger gains peace or freedom by surrendering. This means that their resistance or struggle is likely to cause pain or conflict in the past, and they can only feel better after letting go of this struggle. The second part, “Only when we embraced death,” means actual death, which implies gaining some freedom or change by passing away. Nietzsche rejects both the idea of a “true world” and the notion of an ultimate, objective meaning to life and death.

The Endsinger’s words here can be interpreted as a manifestation of Nietzschean ideas. Accepting death as a natural part of life is consistent with Nietzsche’s belief that people should face truth directly, without the solace of delusions. As The Endsinger argues, accepting death might bring about a sense of ease similar to that which arises from accepting reality as it is, without the need for external validation.

The Endsinger demands others to join her in sorrow and embrace their own deaths. This statement can be seen in the quest Endwalker as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-125)

The Endsinger: “So join us in despair...and embrace yours!”
(Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer emphasizes the quotation above that The Endsinger invites, or rather encourages, the player to surrender to the same despair she encounters. The Endsinger sees civilizations falling apart and the sadness that is an unavoidable part of life. Through her request for players to “embrace yours”, she is saying that they, too, must accept death as other civilizations in other stars do. Nietzsche’s philosophy denies the existence of a real, objective world. Instead, he believes that what people perceive as reality is shaped by their thoughts and interpretations. This viewpoint can cause feelings of hopelessness because it challenges common beliefs about truth, purpose, and worth. If there is no absolute truth or built-in purpose in the world, then people might feel confused, aimless, and filled with despair.

The Endsinger says that trying to fight back or stop them is pointless. They also say they are determined to keep up their “song of oblivion,” which means bringing the final day. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-126)

The Endsinger: “You struggle in vain. You will not silence our song of oblivion!” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer indicates that The Endsinger tells the player character that their struggle is useless and that the player cannot stop her

song of oblivion. The Song of Oblivion is about The Endsinger's mission to eliminate all existence and return all to nothingness, which is the final day. The Endsinger's statement shows a similar disbelief in any "true" meaning or purpose to life. Because she thinks that life is painful and not existing is better, trying to stop her from destroying everything will not work. Like Nietzsche, The Endsinger has no faith in set truths or values. Instead, she possesses her own nihilistic view that comes from all the despair she experiences. "But there is no "other," no "true," no essential being—for this would be the expression of a world without action and reaction" (Nietzsche, 1968: 305).

B. Effects of Nihilism in *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*

1. Results

Through the concept of *Übermensch*, the thesis writer will analyze the effect of Nihilism in Meteion, as mentioned in chapter two. Meteion's dialogue, Hermes' dialogue as Meteion's creator, and Meteion's dialogue with the player and other characters are used to determine that the effects of nihilism make Meteion become *Übermensch*.

Table 4. The Effects of nihilism and its Indicators in Meteion's dialogues and her conversations with other characters in *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*

Indicators	Data No.	Quotation
Overcoming Nihilism	127.	Meteion: "Can you...hear me...?" (Quest: You're Not Alone (Level 90))

	128.	Meteion: “The voices within... Crying in pain, wailing in sorrow... Hurting... Hurting...” (Quest: You’re Not Alone (Level 90))
	129.	Meteion: “End it...silence it... Silence our song of oblivion!” (Quest: You’re Not Alone (Level 90))
	130.	Meteion: “That you still stand... Your determination defies all reason.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	131.	Meteion: “The souls within me writhe and recoil in your presence...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	132.	Meteion: “What must I do? What pain must I visit upon you to make you surrender to despair?” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	133.	Alisaie: “No one is unbreakable. What pains one may weather may bring another to tears.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	134.	Alisaie: “But therein lies our strength, for when we fall, our brothers and sisters are there to raise us up. Again and again. Without end.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	135.	Meteion: “I see...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	136.	Meteion: “But no matter how much hope exists, ever will there be more despair.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	137.	Meteion: “Ever will the living curse the present and lament the future.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	138.	Meteion: “So shall we sing until life ceases to be.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	139.	Meteion: “No matter where we flew, there was only darkness and loneliness and pain.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	140.	Meteion: “We couldn’t find the answers Hermes yearned for. The answers he deserved.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
Creating New Values	141.	Meteion: “Greetings... You who are my final encounter...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

	142.	Meteion: “I wish to hear your words... Share your feelings... Know your thoughts.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	143.	Meteion: “Yes, I can see them... The memories of a long, long journey...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	144.	Meteion: “So many people... The thoughts of them overflowing in your heart...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	145.	Meteion: “What they live for, what gives their lives meaning... There was never a single answer.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	146.	Meteion: “You gather pieces of happiness, precious and fragile, only to lose them. Then start again.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	147.	Meteion: “On and on it goes, until death takes you into its gentle embrace.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	148.	Meteion: “That which Hermes sent us to find...was there all this time. On Etheirys.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	149.	Player: “We created it together.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	150.	Meteion: “Like a field of flowers, perhaps. At first a single blossom, it spreads and takes on more colors.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	151.	Meteion: “Thank you for guiding me here. To find these words at journey’s end fills me with joy.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
The Will to Power	152.	Meteion: “And so, before I fall forever silent, there is one thing I must do.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	153.	Meteion: “No expression of regret will undo what my sisters and I have done. Will restore what we have stolen.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
	154.	Meteion: “But if you would allow it, I would sing one last song. A song of the newfound joy that

	swells in my heart...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
155.	Meteion: “Of the beauty of light when it shines across a dark and starless sea...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
156.	Meteion: “Of a dream that from the soil of worlds now lost to sorrow, life will spring forth once more...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
157.	Meteion: “...Nourished by gentle rains and caressed by uplifting winds. A song of hope.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
158.	Meteion: “One day, life will fill the universe again. And Hermes will see this and smile.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
159.	Meteion: “How, I do not know. But I do know that, where there is a will, there is a way.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
160.	Meteion: “After all, miracles happen every day, do they not?” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
161.	Meteion: “Hold in your heart your desire to return to them, then follow my lead and walk forth.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))
162.	Meteion: “That hope will surely guide you true.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

2. Analysis

a) Overcoming Nihilism

The first evidence of overcoming nihilism in Meteion is when she asks the player if he/she can hear Meteion’s voice. She sounds like she is in pain because she obtains the results of the meaning of life from other stars whose lives are destroyed, and there is no remaining life. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-127)

Meteion: “Can you...hear me...?” (Quest: You’re Not Alone (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer underlines that Meteion is essentially seeking validation of her existence and relationship with others when she asks if she can be heard. She wants to know if her emotions, thoughts, and feelings are recognized and understood. This question also reflects her attempt to communicate herself and her need to be heard, both of which are important aspects of her personality.

Meteion wants to know if she is being heard in the previous quotation and says that the voices inside her are hurt and sad. This statement can be seen in the quest You’re Not Alone, as shown below:

(Data number-128)

Meteion: “The voices within... Crying in pain, wailing in sorrow... Hurting... Hurting...” (Quest: You’re Not Alone (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer analyzes that Meteion’s expression of internal voices crying in pain and wailing in sadness demonstrates an intense empathy for the anguish of others as well as her own. This is compatible with her ability to connect with other people’s feelings and the shared awareness of her sisters, who observe the death and anguish of the stars they visit. The word “hurting” being used over and over again emphasizes how terrible and long-lasting this pain is. “Just as he was beginning to recuperate his health, however, an unkind destiny brought him a number of most painful personal experiences” (Nietzsche, 2006: XV). The thesis writer implies that someone gets better after a tough time, such as getting sick or going through a tough situation, but then more painful things

happen in his life. Meteion's statement and Nietzsche's statement in *Thus Spoke Zarathustra* have a connection, in which both are going through a tough situation and gets worse.

“Song of oblivion” is what Meteion calls the pain she sees and how she wants to end it. That song means bringing the final day or destruction to the star or civilization. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-129)

Meteion: “End it...silence it... Silence our song of oblivion!”
(Quest: You're Not Alone (Level 90))

The thesis writer actualizes the quotation above that Meteion asks the player to end and silence their song of oblivion, which is to stop the final day or destruction in Etheiry's. Meteion calls for silence on the sadness she and her sisters experience from seeing the deaths and suffering of numerous civilizations across the stars. This song reflects the nihilistic conclusion that life is full of unavoidable pain and that the only way out is to end it all.

Meteion praises the player's strength and expresses surprise at how determined he/she is in her task to silence the song of oblivion. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-130)

Meteion: “That you still stand... Your determination defies all reason.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer indicates that Meteion is surprised and impressed by the player's strength and will in the face of great challenges and difficulties Meteion gives to the player and his/her comrades. It can be seen as a

portrayal of the *Übermensch*. Even though they are in a hopeless situation, and their struggles may seem pointless when they think about how big the world is and how hard their job is, they continue to fight and give their journey meaning. This is what the quote from Meteion means. The player's determination and refusal to give up in hopelessness or apathy goes against the logic of a nihilistic view. It is more in line with the idea of the *Übermensch*.

Meteion talks about how the souls inside her reacted negatively to the player being there. Perhaps because of the player's strength and will to live. This statement can be seen in the quest Endwalker as shown below:

(Data number-131)

Meteion: "The souls within me writhe and recoil in your presence..." (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer learns that Meteion's effort to bring pain to the player is useless because the player and his/her comrades will never surrender and give their lives up. When the player is nearby, the souls within Meteion experience great discomfort and attempt to withdraw because of the strength and will of the player to live.

Meteion thinks of what she needs to do to make the player give up and surrender to depression. This statement supports the dialog in Table 4, as shown below:

(Data number-132)

Meteion: "What must I do? What pain must I visit upon you to make you surrender to despair?" (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer ponders the quotation above that Meteion is wondering what acts she needs to take or what sort of misery she needs to inflict in order for the player to lose hope and fall into despair. This could be seen as a twisted view of the *Übermensch*'s mission to create new values: she is not trying to inspire others to go beyond their limits; instead, she is trying to make them feel hopeless, in the hopes that they do not have to suffer in the meaningless world anymore.

Alisaie, one of the player's comrades, acknowledges that everyone's pain level is different. The pain one person experiences can make another person cry or feel hurt. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-133)

Alisaie: "No one is unbreakable. What pains one may weather may bring another to tears." (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer indicates in the quotation above that Alisaie means some people can handle certain problems, but those same problems might be too much for others and make them cry. Alisaie's observation shows that people do not all have the same strength and that support from others is very important. It means that not everyone can be an *Übermensch*, but that there is strength in being able to help each other through hard times.

Alisaie continues that their strength is coming from those experiences. Even when someone falls, they will be picked up by their comrades, and the cycle continues indefinitely. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-134)

Alisaie: “But therein lies our strength, for when we fall, our brothers and sisters are there to raise us up. Again and again. Without end.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer investigates that Alisaie means that her comrades’ strength comes from their willingness to help each other through numerous challenges and difficulties, always helping each other to get better and keep going. Alisaie’s words suggest that the way to get over nihilism does not have to be taken by one person. The *Übermensch* is usually seen as a lone figure. Instead, the support of others can be a source of power that helps people get over their sadness and find meaning in their lives through shared experiences and helping each other.

Meteion acknowledges Alisaie’s words about experiences and comrades who will help and understand each other. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-135)

Meteion: “I see...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer ponders that Meteion conveys an understanding or comprehension of the importance of companionship and mutual support from Alisaie’s statement in the previous quotation. Meteion’s acknowledgment can be seen as a time when the idea of shared human power and resilience works against the destructive and isolating effects of nihilism. Meteion’s discovery can be examined through the lens of Nietzsche’s *Übermensch*. Meteion’s recognition of the value of human relationships can be seen as a step toward the

Übermensch because it means she sees and values something other than the hopelessness that her nihilistic point of view highlights.

Meteion adds that no matter how much hope there is, hopelessness or despair will always be there. This statement supports the dialog in the quest Endwalker as shown below:

(Data number-136)

Meteion: “But no matter how much hope exists, ever will there be more despair.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer emphasizes Meteion’s comment on what life and existence are really like. It means that there will always be more sadness or negativity than hope or positivity, no matter how much people have or make. The *Übermensch* in Nietzsche’s work accepts life with all its problems and sadness and finds meaning in it. In the same way, Meteion’s quote can be seen as an admittance that life is sad, but it does not imply giving up and accepting it. Meteion’s words can be seen as a challenge to finding hope and positivity in the midst of sadness, just like the *Übermensch* make their own values and meanings.

Meteion says that living things will always be unhappy with their current situation and afraid of what the future holds. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-137)

Meteion: “Ever will the living curse the present and lament the future.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer studies that Meteion means living things are always unhappy with their current situation and scared or sad about what

will happen next. This point of view sees life as a never-ending cycle of pain and sadness, with hope always fading. Meteion expresses that sadness is an unavoidable part of being human and that it defeats any effort to find or create hope.

Meteion states that she will keep singing her song of oblivion and bring the final day until there is no more life. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-138)

Meteion: “So shall we sing until life ceases to be.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer actualizes that Meteion and her sisters will continue to sing the “song of oblivion” to bring destruction to the star until there is no more life. This can be interpreted as a form of resignation to the hope and meaninglessness of life. Meteion and her sisters, known as the Meteia, discover that every world they visit is either dead or dying. They decide that life is painful and should end, so they go to the edge of the universe to start the Final Days, a terrible event that will destroy all living things. This viewpoint resembles Nietzsche’s destructive nihilism, which entails a severe rejection of all imposed values and meaning, resulting in the destruction of all values.

After the player and his/her companions kill the Endsinger, Meteion comes back in her usual form. She tells the player that no matter where she and her sisters fly to other stars, they only find darkness, loneliness, and pain in those stars. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-139)

Meteion: “No matter where we flew, there was only darkness and loneliness and pain.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer learns from the quotation above that wherever Meteion and her sisters fly to another star; they only encounter negative experiences without any hope or company. “They meet an invalid, or an old man, or a corpse, and immediately they say: “Life is refuted!” But they only are refuted, and their eye, which seeth only one aspect of existence” (Nietzsche, 2006:45). Meteion’s statement and Nietzsche’s quotation from *Thus spoke Zarathustra* is in line because Meteion only sees existence from one aspect, which is destruction because wherever Meteion’s sisters go, they only see darkness, loneliness, and pain then they immediately say that life is meaningless.

Meteion feels sad because she and her sisters could not find the meaning of life which Hermes tasks them to find. This statement supports the dialog of Meteion in the quest Endwalker as shown below:

(Data number-140)

Meteion: “We couldn’t find the answers Hermes yearned for. The answers he deserved.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer indicates that Meteion regrets that she and her sisters are unable to answer Hermes’ question regarding the reason and purpose of life on other stars. Meteion is created to find answers to this existential question by exploring the world to search for other civilizations. Meteion’s statement, “The answers he deserved,” means that Hermes deserved to find some comfort or peace of mind for his own inner pain and existential desire. Meteion cares about Hermes and wants to help him find purpose and meaning in life.

b) **Creating New Values**

The first evidence of creating new values is when Meteion, upon being defeated by the player and his/her comrades, greets the player as her final encounter. This statement supports the dialog in the quest Endwalker as shown below:

(Data number-141)

Meteion: “Greetings... You who are my final encounter...”
(Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

Meteion acknowledges the player as the final entity with whom she will interact. Meteion’s journey or purpose is over, as this sentence gives the impression of a closed and final chapter because she is defeated by the player and his/her comrades in the previous fight against The Endsinger, which is a form of Meteion and her sisters fused together. Meteion’s final encounter with the player can be interpreted as a manner of overcoming nihilism. She greets the player and talks to her, even though she knows this is her last encounter. This shows that she finds meaning and worth in this interaction, even though it is the end of her journey.

Meteion wishes to hear the player’s words, share the player’s feelings, and know the player’s thoughts. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-142)

Meteion: “I wish to hear your words... Share your feelings... Know your thoughts.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer understands that Meteion’s journey and her experiences with different kinds of life make her believe that life is pointless and full of pain and sadness. Despite this, her desire to hear the player’s words, share her feelings, and know what the player thinks shows that she still hopes

to understand and connect with her. This could be seen as a step toward overcoming nihilism and becoming more like the ideal example of the *Übermensch*.

Meteion sees the player's memories, which are the memories of a long journey. This statement can be seen in Table 4 as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-143)

Meteion: "Yes, I can see them... The memories of a long, long journey..." (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer studies the quotation above that Meteion can see and understand the memories and experiences of the player character from their long journeys and adventures, as this quote suggests. The word "them" she discusses are the memories, and the "long, long journey" is the player's journey and struggles throughout the game. By confirming the player's long struggle across the stars, Meteion acknowledges that people can find meaning and value in their lives by enduring things and overcoming themselves instead of giving up when things get difficult.

Meteion expresses being overwhelmed by the thoughts and emotions of many people from the player's memories, and it fills the player's heart. This statement can be seen in Table 4 as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-144)

Meteion: "So many people... The thoughts of them overflowing in your heart..." (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer learns that Meteion's ability to read emotions enables her to connect with and understand the feelings of others on

a deeper level. Meteion declares that she feels overwhelmed by all of the many people's thoughts and emotions that are overflowing the player's heart.

Meteion says that different people have very different ideas about what gives life value. There is no one solution that fits all people because everyone has their own experiences, values, and points of view that shape how they see what gives their life purpose and meaning. This statement is shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-145)

Meteion: "What they live for, what gives their lives meaning... There was never a single answer." (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer ponders that Meteion shows that different people have different ideas about what life is all about. It means that there is no single answer to the question of what gives life meaning or what people should live for. This shows how different and complicated life and each person's situations are. There is no single answer to the question of what gives life value, and each person has to make their own.

Meteion understands that the player gathers pieces of precious and fragile happiness from her journey but ends up losing them. But then the player starts to pick those pieces again. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-146)

Meteion: "You gather pieces of happiness, precious and fragile, only to lose them. Then start again." (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer explores the quotation above that Meteion can understand the player's suffering, which the player gathers pieces of happiness throughout

his/her life, which are valuable but also fragile and easy to lose. Despite this loss, the player continues to seek out those pieces and repeat the process all over again. It can be interpreted as the effect of nihilism, in which *Übermensch* creates the idea and meaning of life even though, through the journey, it will hurt.

Meteion continues her previous dialog that the player's experiences keep going until death takes them, which she puts the people in the player's memories into its gentle embrace. This statement supports the dialog in the quest Endwalker, as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-147)

Meteion: "On and on it goes, until death takes you into its gentle embrace." (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer analyzes that Meteion is saying that life is a journey that never stops, only when someone dies. Through this journey, people have many events that shape who they are today. When death comes, it takes with it all of those memories and experiences. The continuous journey she talks about might imply that each person is always trying to find their own meaning in life or to become the *Übermensch*. The problems and difficulties a person face during this process is what make them. Therefore, death can be seen as the final acceptance of the meaning that each person makes, carrying with it the unique values and experiences that they build over their lifetime.

Meteion understands that the answer where Hermes seeks and tasks Meteion's sisters to travel across the universe is actually in Etheirys. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-148)

Meteion: “That which Hermes sent us to find...was there all this time. On Etheiry’s.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer learns that Meteion figures out that the answers to the questions Hermes instructs her and her sisters to look for all over the universe are on their star, Etheiry’s. Meteion only realizes this after reading the memories and feelings of the player on his/her lifetime journey with his/her comrades. This represents the idea that meaning or value is not something that can be found outside or in a faraway place (or, in the case of nihilism, not at all) but something that can be created or discovered in one’s own life or home.

The player tells Meteion that the meaning of life in Etheiry’s is because the people in Etheiry’s created it together. This statement can be seen in Table 4 as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-149)

Player: “We created it together.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer underlines that the player interprets “We” as a group attempt to solve the existential problem caused by nihilism. It says that people can create their own meanings and ideals by working together and sharing their efforts, which is what the *Übermensch* idea means. This process of making things together could be seen as an effect of nihilism, a way to fight the hopelessness and sense of purposelessness that nihilism can cause. It means that people can move beyond the nihilistic view and create their own meaningful lives.

Meteion says that the growth of understanding or happiness, which can be understood as the meaning of life, is like a field of flowers that starts with one and grows into a wide range of bright colors. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-150)

Meteion: “Like a field of flowers, perhaps. At first a single blossom, it spreads and takes on more colors.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer studies that one way to look at Meteion’s image of the flower field is as a metaphor for the way to becoming an *Übermensch*. The single flower shows how a person starts out. As they grow and change, they take on more colors or a more complex and detailed view of life. One might say that this growth and variety is the process of getting over nihilism and becoming an *Übermensch* to create their own meaning in life.

Meteion expresses gratitude to the player for directing her to a discovery that brings her happiness at the end of her journey. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-151)

Meteion: “Thank you for guiding me here. To find these words at journey’s end fills me with joy.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer indicates that Meteion is grateful for the player’s assistance or guidance, which helps her discover something important and fills her with joy with the memories of the player as her journey reaches an end. Throughout *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*, Meteion deals with the pain and despair she sees all over the world. But her last words show that she

changes from a nihilistic point of view to one that finds joy and meaning, which is similar to the process of becoming an *Übermensch*.

c) **The Will to Power**

The first evidence of the will to power is when Meteion informs the player that she has one more thing to do before she can no longer live or communicate.

This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-152)

Meteion: “And so, before I fall forever silent, there is one thing I must do.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer understands that Meteion is on the edge of becoming forever silent, but she has one more mission to do before that happens. Her resolve to do one last thing before she falls forever silent can be seen as an attempt to give her life meaning or purpose, similar to the *Übermensch*'s ability to choose for themselves and make their own values.

Meteion recognizes that no amount of regret can erase the past or return what she and her sisters take. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-153)

Meteion: “No expression of regret will undo what my sisters and I have done. Will restore what we have stolen.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer ponders that no matter how much Meteion and her sisters regret everything about what they did, they are unable to take it back or undo what they did. This statement shows that they regret what they

did and understand that it cannot be changed. Meteion requests permission from the player to perform one final act to the player, singing a song that represents the joy she now feels. This statement can be seen in Table 4 as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-154)

Meteion: “But if you would allow it, I would sing one last song. A song of the newfound joy that swells in my heart...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer emphasizes the quotation above that Meteion conveys a desire to share a last song with the player, which represents an emotional expression or message. Meteion’s statement “newfound joy” represents the song, which means a significant change or understanding in her feelings. Connecting this to Friedrich Nietzsche’s *Übermensch* concept, it views Meteion’s newfound joy as a possible overcoming of nihilism. “Overman” or “*Übermensch*” in Nietzsche’s writings is a character who creates new values and overcomes nihilism.

Meteion wishes to sing to the player as her last action, about the beauty that can appear even in the worst and most lonely places. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-155)

Meteion: “Of the beauty of light when it shines across a dark and starless sea...” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer studies that this phrase is a metaphor by Meteion for showing that beauty and hope can be found even in the worst and most hopeless conditions. It means that even in the worst and most lonely places, there may be a small bit of beauty or light that can bring comfort and hope.

This light may stand for hope, strength, or the spirit of the human race, which never gives up even when things get complicated. Meteion's statement can be seen as a representation of the *Übermensch*'s point of view. Even though the "dark and starless sea" can be seen as the nihilistic view that life is meaningless, the "beauty of light" shows that the *Übermensch* can make their own meaning and find beauty in even the worst situations.

Meteion continues the previous quotation, where she talks to the player about her final action. Meteion portrays a future in which life develops from once sorrowful environments. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-156)

Meteion: "Of a dream that from the soil of worlds now lost to sorrow, life will spring forth once more..." (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer analyzes the quotation above that new life can sprout even from the depths of sadness and loss. The phrase "worlds now lost to sorrow" represents nihilism, a state of mind in which value has no meaning. The "dream" that life will begin again is a metaphor for the rise of the *Übermensch*, who gives meaning and values to a world that appears to have none.

Meteion's song is one of hope, representing life being nurtured and maintained by natural factors. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-157)

Meteion: "...Nourished by gentle rains and caressed by uplifting winds. A song of hope." (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer ponders that Meteion's phrase "gentle rains" is a metaphor for a type of nourishment or care, and the "uplifting winds" are a metaphor for motivation or support. These things work together to help growth and progress. It is a metaphor for the final song Meteion will sing, A song of hope, where the song conveys the idea that care and support will result in a positive ending or future.

Meteion expresses hope to the player, where life will eventually spread to every part of the universe, which will bring happiness to Hermes. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-158)

Meteion: "One day, life will fill the universe again. And Hermes will see this and smile." (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer underlines the quotation above that Meteion portrays a hopeful future in which life spreads throughout the universe. Meteion believes that the universal spread of life will bring joy to Hermes, her creator, who previously tasked her with searching for the reason and purpose of existence in another star. Meteion's wish for life to fill the world can be seen as an affirmation of life, which is a character of the *Übermensch*. She thinks positively for the future and the people of Etheiry's to create their own meaning and purpose in life. Meteion's belief in the potential for life to fill the universe again, despite the despair and suffering she has witnessed, can be seen as an assertion of the will to power, which is the drive to assert oneself and overcome obstacles.

Meteion says to the player that she does not know how this future will come about, but she is sure that people who believe in it will find a way to make it happen.

This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-159)

Meteion: “How, I do not know. But I do know that, where there is a will, there is a way.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer learns that Meteion shows determination and optimism despite uncertainty. Meteion admits that she is unsure how to get a particular result, but she thinks having the desire or determination will help her find a way forward or a solution. Her quotation reflects a transformation from a nihilistic perspective to the will to power, which is the path of becoming an *Übermensch*. She believes that if there is a will to accomplish something, there is a way to transcend despair and create purpose, even if the method is unclear.

Meteion says that miracles happen all the time, which means that the bright future she dreams of is possible. This statement supports the dialog in the quest Endwalker as shown below:

(Data number-160)

Meteion: “After all, miracles happen every day, do they not?” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer indicates in the quotation above that Meteion’s statement talks of hope and faith in the miraculous. It means that extraordinary or mysterious things happen every day, which are called miracles. This sentence insinuates hope and happiness, suggesting that something amazing may happen even when things are bad. Because life is full of wonder and potential. Meteion’s belief in the

possibility of daily miracles, despite the despair and suffering she has witnessed, can be seen as an assertion of the will to power.

Meteion tells the player to remember his/her desire to be with their loved ones or comrades again and to follow her advice to move forward. This statement can be seen in the quotation below:

(Data number-161)

Meteion: “Hold in your heart your desire to return to them, then follow my lead and walk forth.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

The thesis writer studies the quotation above that Meteion tells the player to preserve his/her desire to reunite with loved ones or comrades in his/her heart and to follow her guidance in order to move forward. Meteion encourages the player to keep the emotional connections and use them as a driving force to overcome challenges and proceed on their quest and to go back on the ship where the player’s comrades are waiting for his/her returns after the fight against The Endsinger.

Meteion affirms to the player that she is sure that hope will lead the player in the right way. This statement supports the dialog in the quest Endwalker, as shown in the quotation below:

(Data number-162)

Meteion: “That hope will surely guide you true.” (Quest: Endwalker (Level 90))

From the quotation above, the thesis writer understands that Meteion’s quotation can be examined as a statement of faith in the power of hope. It means that hope will lead one to the right way as long as one holds on to it. This essentially means that hope can be a solid compass in life. “All who do not want to live unless

they learn again to hope unless they learn from thee. Zarathustra, the great hope!” (Nietzsche, 2006:314). Meteion’s statement and Nietzsche’s writings in *Thus Spoke Zarathustra* share similarities because both are based on the idea that hope can change things. They emphasize that hope is more than just a feeling but a driving force that can bring about positive change or help and guide one through difficult times.

CHAPTER V

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The thesis writer included the conclusion of the previous discussion and suggestions in this chapter.

A. Conclusion

In this research, the thesis writer learns from the research objectives that Meteion experiences nihilism related to proving signs of nihilism in herself, which is shown starting from recognition of nihilism, systematization of nihilism, and disbelief in true world. For the recognition of nihilism, Meteion understands Hermes' feelings of sadness and pain as her creator, her tasks to find the meaning and purpose of life, her ability to project other people's emotions and feelings, Hermes' conversations with the player about pain and suffering, and Meteion's sisters' reports on finding the meaning of life. For the systematization of nihilism, Hermes explains his task to the star, the reason why he assigned Meteion and her sisters to search for the meaning of life, Meteion's excitement about the answers she will get from her sisters, Meteion's desire to find the meaning of life, Meteion's findings about the reason why the civilization she finds in other stars are destroyed, and Meteion's statement about other beings' efforts to find meaning in their lives but eventually face despair as long as they live. Lastly, for the disbelief in true world, Meteion conclude her findings where there are no other intelligent beings found, Meteion wants to sing her song of oblivion to bring the destruction and final day to

Etheiry's, Meteion make her nest in the star located in the edge of the universe, and Meteion fused with her other sisters becoming the Endsinger to fight the player.

The effects of nihilism have made Meteion becoming *Übermensch*. The effects of nihilism in Meteion, which uses the theory of *Übermensch*, are seen from Meteion's request to the player to silence her song of oblivion so she cannot deliver the final day. Alisaie as one of the player's comrades, explain the reason why they help each other. The Endsinger is defeated by the player and his/her comrades and stopped her from singing the song of oblivion. Meteion, upon defeated by the player, says that she and her sisters could not find the meaning of life. Meteion greets the player as her final encounter and wishes to hear, share, and know the player's thoughts and feelings. Meteion then projects the memories from the player and she finally understands that the meaning of life Hermes seeks is already in Etheiry's. The player explains that they created the meaning of life together. Meteion sings the song of hope before she forever silent, and send back the player to his/her comrades' ship where they are waiting for his/her returns.

B. Suggestions

By looking at the previous conclusion, the thesis writer would like to offer some recommendations for both the readers and future research. This thesis provides information regarding the proofs of nihilism and effects of nihilism represented by Meteion from becoming nihilist and end up become *Übermensch*, as well as how to analyze them. Future research can discover another side of

philosophy of other characters such as Hermes as Meteion's creator, or even the player/main character itself. Analyze Final Fantasy XIV's storytelling, how the game's lore enriches the player's experience, and look into the various cultural and historical references within the game's lore. Future research can also discuss the game's design philosophy and community engagement among players around the world. Numerous theories can be analyzed in this game especially the expansions.

This thesis is anticipated to be able to inform general readers on what is the meaning and purpose of life, as well as how to overcome those matters in which is *Übermensch*. The readers will be able to create their own meaning of purpose in life.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX I

Biography of the Director and Author

Naoki Yoshida, popularly known as Yoshi-P, is a key player in the video game business and is best known for serving as the producer and director of the highly regarded MMORPG Final Fantasy XIV. Yoshida, a Japanese native born on May 1st, 1973, developed a deep love for video games as a young child, ultimately inspiring him to pursue a career in the gaming industry. He was fascinated by the idea of controlling what was shown on television screens and fascinated by the storytelling potential of games.

Natsuko Ishikawa is a Japanese writer who works for Square Enix. She has been co-lead writer for five expansions in Final Fantasy XIV, including Endwalker as the Lead Story Designer. *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker* has received many awards including Excellence in Narrative by 2022 SXSW Gaming Awards.

APPENDIX II

Synopsis

On the ancient world of Elpis, an ambitious scientist named Hermes creates a race of winged humanoids called the Meteia. Meteion and her sisters, the Meteia, were created from emotion-derived energy known as dynamis rather than aether. They possess a shared consciousness and are sent out into the universe to discover the reason for living.

But one by one, each Meteion returns having succumbed to nihilism after witnessing only civilizations in ruin across the universe. They determine that life has no meaning and that to end all suffering, all life must end. The Meteia then coalesce into the despairing Endsinger, who sings a song to extinguish all existence.

Back in Etheiry's, the Warrior of Light and their fellow Scions go on a journey to uncover the truth behind the Final Days. This leads them to Elpis where they meet Venat, an Ascian who reveals the existence of Meteion and her nihilistic threat. To stop the apocalypse, the Warrior travels to the edge of the universe and confronts Meteion, trying to convince her that there is still meaning in life.

“If this...was not the answer...then what is it? Where lies...happiness...?” The Endsinger, upon being defeated.

With her sisters defeated, Meteion was left at the edge of the universe alongside the Warrior of Light and Zenos. Although Meteion had broken from the overwhelming despair, she still grieved over everything her sisters had discovered on their journey and their failure to find the answers Hermes deserved to have. The Warrior of Light allowed Meteion to share their feelings one last time, and upon grasping her hand, Meteion was overwhelmed by the Warrior's love for their friends and endless pursuit to find hope and happiness in life, even in the darkest moments. Moved by their compassion, Meteion ceases her nihilistic crusade.

Meteion realized that in spite of Hermes' mission, the answer to her question had been on Etheiry's all along. Meteion regained her hope for the future. Though she cannot undo the damage already wrought on Etheiry's, Meteion departs on a new journey to find meaning once again. With Meteion's redemption, the Warrior of Light has saved all existence from annihilation - for now. But the future remains uncertain in Etheiry's.

TABLES OF DATA

Table 5. The Proofs of nihilism in Meteion’s dialogues and her conversations with Hermes as her creators, and other characters in *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*

Data No.	Quotation	Quests and Levels	Analysis
1.	Meteion: “This is my power. I can read the emotions of those around me, and project my emotions to others in return.”	Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86)	Meteion shows the player her power; that is, Meteion can read the feelings of the creatures around her and project her emotions to others.
2.	Meteion: “I am not actually speaking to you in your mind. Rather, you are converting my emotions into words and intention—a process performed subconsciously by intelligent life-forms.”	Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86)	Meteion uses emotions to communicate instead of words or telepathy. Those she speaks with are able to decipher her communications because they are subconsciously translating her feelings into words and intentions.
3.	Meteion: “This ability is vital to my mission, for it allows me to interact with intelligent beings even should they communicate via unknown languages or other nonverbal means.”	Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86)	Meteion explain that her power is important for her mission that Hermes gives, which her power allows her to interact with intelligent beings.
4.	Meteion: “Yet though I struggle to express myself in this fashion, Hermes wants me to speak as much as possible,	Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86)	Meteion discusses with the player about her difficulties in communicating and expressing emotions and feelings.

	for everyone has thoughts and feelings that they may wish to hide...”		
5.	Meteion: “I harbor an affection for you. One that is difficult to define.”	Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86)	Meteion’s attraction to the player with complicated emotions appears to derive from her capacity to understand and share feelings with the player.
6.	Meteion: “Aside from the fact that you share common traits with us, your thoughts are complex. Prismatic. They draw me in, and leave me wanting to know more.”	Ponder, Warrant, Cherish, Welcome (Level 86)	Meteion talks with the player about their thoughts where they share common traits, and Meteion wants to know more about it.
7.	Meteion: “It’s heavy... Hermes’ pain...”	Aether to Aether (Level 86)	Meteion is a character who is created by Hermes and has the ability to read and project emotions. Meteion expresses her ability to feel and understand the emotional pain that Hermes is experiencing to the player.
8.	Hermes: “We have a duty to the star, this I know. But it doesn’t mean we don’t also have a responsibility to the lives we bring into existence here.”	Aether to Aether (Level 86)	Hermes, the creator of Meteion, talks to the player about their duty to the star and responsibility to the existence.
9.	Meteion: “Ooh, Elpis flowers! They’re here too! Hermes likes and dislikes them. At the same time.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Meteion and the player is looking for a flower to give to Hermes. They find the Elpis flower, a flower that represents Elpis and can also read human emotions. Meteion tells the player that Hermes loves and hates Elpis flowers at the same time.

10.	Meteion: “Like me, they’re entelechies. Like me, they feel his pain and turn dark...”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	After Meteion finds Elpis flower while traveling around Elpis with the player and talks about how Hermes feels to Elpis flower, Meteion reveals how Elpis flower feels and reacts to Hermes’ emotions, which is Elpis flower feels pain from Hermes and the color of the petals of Elpis flower changes to black.
11.	Meteion: “That’s only for Hermes, though. For others, they’re always white and bright.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	After explaining to the player on how the Elpis flower reacts to Hermes, Meteion emphasizes her explanation again where she says that the dark color only applies to Hermes, and for others the color of their Elpis flower is white and bright.
12.	Meteion: “Truly!? The flower was dark in your home!?”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	When Meteion explains that Elpis flower turn dark only applies to Hermes and the others are always white and bright, Meteion surprises that the Elpis flower owns by the player also turns dark.
13.	Meteion: “Then...do you have it too? A dark emotion?”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	After Meteion knows that not only Hermes has a dark Elpis flower but the player also has it, Meteion asks the player if he/she has the same dark emotion as Hermes.
14.	Player: “I’ve known the pain and sorrow of loss.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	The player replies to Meteion about her question, which the player says that she has known the pain and sorrow of loss.
15.	Meteion: “I see...”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Meteion, as a character, personifies this philosophy. Hermes creates her as an artificial person to understand the feelings and experiences of people. Meteion understand the pain and sorrow of the player.

16.	Meteion: “Hermes has known the same. The feeling that a part of you is gone. Again and again. But no one notices...”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	After Meteion understands the player’s emotions, Meteion says that Hermes has a similar feeling with the player but sadly no one notices.
17.	Meteion: “Please, (player). Won’t you lend it to me? Your pain and sorrow...”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	As Meteion tells the player that Hermes also has the same feelings of pain and sadness and that part of him is gone, Meteion wants the player to lend Meteion the pain and sadness.
18.	Meteion: “He (Hermes) has been in a dark place. Since before he created me. He needs to know that he isn’t there alone. That others are sad too.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Meteion, as the creature created by Hermes, wants him to know that he is not alone even though he is in a dark place and feels sad. Meteion wants Hermes to know that not only him but other people are sad too.
19.	Meteion: “You’re not the only one, Hermes. Others feel sad too. You’re not alone.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Meteion and the player talk, then they wait outside of the meeting room to give the Elpis flower to Hermes to cheer him up. Hermes finishes his meeting and is surprised because Meteion shows him the Elpis flower. Meteion tells Hermes that he is not the only one because others feel sad too and he is not alone.
20.	Hermes: “I do not think it wrong that we live for the star. That we strive to make it a better place.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes understands that Meteion shares much with the player because of what she says earlier that he is not the only one who feel sad and alone. Hermes asks the player to talk in private without Meteion. Hermes starts the conversation about the purpose of life and make the star a better place.

21.	Hermes: “And yet, in carrying out my duties here, there are times when I am plagued by doubt.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes in the previous dialogue states that it is not wrong to live for the stars and to make it a better place. Yet, Hermes says to the player that there are times when he is surrounded by doubt.
22.	Hermes: “Death is the privilege of those who have fulfilled their purpose. A choice they embrace of their own free will. And when they depart, it is always beautiful.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes discusses death where death is a privilege to those who fulfill their purpose in this world, the choice of their own will, and he also admires it when they depart.
23.	Hermes: “Some scarcely born into the world. Afforded a handful of breaths before life and potential are abruptly extinguished.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes, the creator of Meteion, talks about the lost lives that are barely get the chance to live and die young.
24.	Hermes: “We make an effort to spare them the pain. But they sense what awaits. Rage in anguish and cower in fear...and it is not beautiful.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes tells the player about how other beings’ feels even though they spare the pain away, they still rage and cower in fear and he thinks it is not beautiful as what he says in the previous dialog about how beautiful it is when they depart and embrace their own free will.
25.	Hermes: “Yet no one cares. No one.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes expresses his feeling to the player that he is sad because no one cares on the pain and despair of creatures.
26.	Hermes: “So fixated are we upon the duty that we do not pause to question the method.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes is a character who is greatly concerned with the meaning of life and what can be employed to carry out responsibilities. He finds it difficult that people too much focus on their duties that they fail to think about whether the way they are doing is right or wrong.

27.	Hermes: “Pain and suffering... Confusion and despair... Writ plain in the eyes of those poor creatures.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes understands the feeling of the poor creatures which are pain, suffering, confusion, and despair.
28.	Hermes: “Yet no one sees. We turn a blind eye and carry on in blissful ignorance. Naught amiss, and always—always the blossoms shine pure and white.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes feels sad for those people who are ignorant to reality.
29.	Hermes: “A contradiction so blatant I could scream. Want to scream. How can you all accept this...aberration!?”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes feels frustrated and wants to scream because of the contradiction and aberration that others can accept.
30.	Hermes: “Then I wonder...am I the aberration for thinking thus? And I am filled with dread...”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes questions himself if he goes astray in thinking so and he fills with fear.
31.	Hermes: “But now I know I’m not alone. Not the only one for whom the flowers weep.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes now understands that he is not alone because he is not the only one who feel the pain and sorrow as the player also shares the same emotion.
32.	Hermes: “Nevertheless...I thank you.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes expresses his gratitude to the player because of the shared feelings of pain and sorrow that he feels.
33.	Hermes: “To know that you too have experienced suffering...is a comfort.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes feels comfortable because of the similar feelings between him and the player.
34.	Hermes: “The stars in the heavens... Know you what they are?”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes questions the player what are the stars in the heavens.

35.	Hermes: “Though it is too far to tell, each glittering light could be a world not unlike Etheiry’s. A world filled with life.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes says that even though the stars in the heavens are too far to tell, he thinks that every shimmering light could be a world not very different from Etheiry’s, the star he currently inhabits, which is full of life.
36.	Hermes: “So many stars, so many lives... For us, there may be no higher purpose than to live for our world, but what of the other living beings out there?”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes thinks that our purpose in life is no higher than living for the world, while there are so many stars out there, in other words, so many lives. Hermes wonders what the purpose of other living beings beyond Etheiry’s is.
37.	Hermes: “What is it that gives their lives meaning? That drives them day after day after day?”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes curious about what is their meaning of life that motivates the living beings in other stars.
38.	Hermes: “To pose that question to our undiscovered cousins, I created beings of dynamis, who can traverse the vast emptiness between the stars. Meteion and her sisters.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes tells the player the reason why he creates Meteion and her sisters from dynamis. Because Hermes wanted to pose the question of the meaning of life to other beings on other stars.
39.	Hermes: “She has a great many of them, and they have already departed on their journey. Traveling to one star, and then the next, in search of life.”	A Sentimental Gift (Level 86)	Hermes tells the player that Meteion has many great sisters that travels to one and another stars in search of life.
40.	Hermes: “Every step of the way, I’ve been reminded how little we understand creation. How the universe defies imagination.”	A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87)	The player accesses Hermes and Meteion’s past conversation memories with the help of Venat. Hermes talks with Meteion about the task he gives to Meteion and

			her sisters and it reminds him how little they understand creation and how universe defies imagination.
41.	Meteion: “But soon we won’t need to speculate. We’ll know the answers—what others live for!”	A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87)	Meteion replies to Hermes’ statement, that they will know the answer which what other beings in the other stars live for.
42.	Hermes: “Whatever intelligent beings that exist out there are bound to be vastly different from us.”	A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87)	Hermes thinks that the beings in other stars are intelligent and very different from the beings in Etheiryrs.
43.	Hermes: “Diverse in form and culture. Possessed of unique ways of thinking.”	A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87)	Hermes says from the previous statement that the intelligent beings exist out there are very different from the beings in Etheiryrs. Not only different, but also possess unique ways of thinking, Hermes adds.
44.	Hermes: “Their conception of life and its purpose will be no exception. Completely and utterly unlike ours.”	A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87)	Hermes believes that other beings’ purpose of life is completely different from the beings in Etheiryrs.
45.	Hermes: “Yet whatever answers we receive, I will not dismiss them out of hand. No, I will think earnestly on them all.”	A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87)	Hermes continues, that whatever answers they receive, he will not just ignore it and will think about every answers seriously.
46.	Hermes: “Then I will share them with our people, that together we may contemplate our own existence.”	A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87)	Hermes explains that he will share the answers with the people of Etheiryrs and reflect their own existence together.

47.	Hermes: “Perhaps then our star will become a better place—not only for man, but for all life.”	A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87)	Hermes hopes that with all the answers he will get, Etheirys will become a better place not only for man but for all life.
48.	Hermes: “Meteion. Though I gave you wings to soar the heavens, I did not teach you how to walk the earth. So loath was I to bind another living being.”	A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87)	Hermes tells Meteion that even though he gives Meteion wings to soar in the sky, Hermes does not teach Meteion how to walk on earth. He does not want to bind another being.
49.	Hermes: “In the course of your long journey, you will learn from those you meet. Learn to walk and run and so much more.”	A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87)	Hermes continues to tell Meteion that she will learn through the people she will meet in her journey. Hermes wants Meteion to learn to walk and run so much more.
50.	Hermes: “And when you return, older and wiser, we will have a celebration to mark your homecoming and coming of age both.”	A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87)	Hermes adds that when Meteion and her sisters return from their mission in search of the meaning of life, they will have a celebration to mark their homecoming and become older and wiser.
51.	Meteion: “Executing scheduled task. Suspending individual self and connecting to shared consciousness.”	A Flower upon Your Return (Level 87)	Meteion connects herself to her sisters in other stars to share the result of the findings about in search of meaning of life.
52.	Meteion: “So scared... so lonely... The pain... it’s too much...”	Words Without Sound (Level 87)	Meteion experiences fear and pain from the report she receives.
53.	Meteion: “Why...why...why do we..they..hurt...hurt...hate...HATE!”	Words Without Sound (Level 87)	Meteion feels not only pain and lonely but also hurt and hate. These shared feelings are from her sisters who travels to other stars to seek meaning of life.

54.	Meteion: “This is wrong! All wrong!”	Words Without Sound (Level 87)	Meteion experiences overpowering negative emotions and decides that existence is a cause of suffering.
55.	Meteion: “Stay away. Please. This is wrong. My mistake. So please...”	Words Without Sound (Level 87)	Meteion and her sisters connects with other beings in other stars and absorbs their emotions. She feels their hopelessness and pain, which makes her very sad. As a result, she begs the player and other characters that close to her to stay away, admitting that something is wrong yet blaming it to her own mistake.
56.	Meteion: “Our survey is complete. We shall now report our findings.”	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	Meteion tells the player and other characters that she and her sisters’ exploration is done and will report their findings.
57.	Meteion: “All units safely arrived at their respective destinations. Seeking answers to Hermes’s question, we attempted to make contact with the intelligent denizens of each star.”	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	Meteion continues to tell that her sisters arrive at their respective destination in search of answers to Hermes’ question. Meteion’s sisters tries to contact with the intelligent beings of each star.
58.	Hena (Meteion’s Sister): “Traces of civilization found—structures believed to have served as domiciles. No extant life-forms detected.”	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	Hena as one of the Meteion’s sister that travels to other stars, reports her findings through Meteion. Hena reports that she finds traces of civilization but does not detect any extant life forms.
59.	Dyo (Meteion’s Sister): “Ruined remnants of buildings scattered across star, surface of which is encased in ice. Presence of life could not be verified.”	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	After Hena finishes reporting her findings, next is to hear the findings from Dyo, who is also one of Meteion’s sisters. Dyo reports that the existence of life cannot be verified, and the remains of a ruined building scattered across star which surface is covers in ice.

60.	Tria (Meteion's Sister): "Evidence of large population centers akin to cities recovered. No extant life-forms found—only their lingering essence."	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	Tria, one of Meteion's sisters, tells what she finds out from exploring the universe. She finds the remains of big population centers that look like cities, but there are no living things there, only signs that they used to be there.
61.	Tessera (Meteion's Sister): "Edifices surmised to be abandoned residences found. No extant life-forms detected. Deadly plague or extreme environmental degradation likely to have led to mass extinction."	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	Tessera, Meteion's sister, surveys a star. She discovers what she thinks are abandoned houses. There are no signs of life, which makes her think that either a terrible disease or a lot of damage to the environment possibly kills everyone who lives there.
62.	Hermes: "They are all...dead?"	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	Hermes is surprised when he hears the report from Meteion which basically all civilizations are dead.
63.	Emet-Selch: "Remind me, Hermes. What exactly was the question you entrusted to Meteion?"	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	Emet-Selch as one of Hermes' colleagues who also hears the report from Meteion, asks Hermes what task he gives to Meteion.
64.	Hermes: "I tasked her with asking what others live for. What gives their lives...meaning..."	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	Hermes tells Emet-Selch the tasks he gives to Meteion, which is to ask what other beings live for and what gives their lives meaning.
65.	Emet-Selch: "Did you consider what may happen if the premise of the question is flawed?"	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	Emet-Selch questions Hemes if he ever considers the danger if the results are negative.

66.	Emet-Selch: “To be able to answer it, one must be living—and desire to continue doing so.”	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	Emet-Selch continues, to answer the question that Hermes gives to Meteion, the beings in other stars must be alive and have the desire of living.
67.	Emet-Selch: “But if Meteion finds no living beings in the course of her journey...”	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	Emet-Selch asks to Hermes what if Meteion cannot find living beings in her journey to other stars.
68.	Emet-Selch: “Or none who desire to live, what then?”	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	Emet-Selch continues his question, what will happen if Meteion also cannot find the living beings who have desire to live.
69.	Emet-Selch: “What answers would she derive from their silence?”	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	Emet-Selch asks Hermes, what answers in the meaning of life will Meteion get from the quietness of the other stars.
70.	Meteion: “ <i>Deka-pente (Meteion’s Sister):</i> Local civilization once flourished under auspices of higher power. Said power later laid waste to civilization in fit of rage.”	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	Meteion, who ignores Venat’s orders to stop her mission, continues with the report from one of her sisters, Deka-Pente. Deka-Pente reports that a local civilization once flourished under the auspices of a higher power. That power then destroys the civilization in a fit of rage.
71.	Meteion: “Upon revealing this to me, entity elected to self-terminate in lieu of providing answer to question. No other intelligent life-forms found.”	Follow, Wander, Stumble, Listen (Level 87)	After Meteion finishes her sisters’ report about the findings, Meteion adds that a civilization destroys itself as a substitute for the answer to the questions. She also finds no other intelligent beings.
72.	Meteion: “We scoured historical records. Communed with the spirits of the deceased.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion, as a dynamis being with an ability to read and project emotions, is able to communicate with the spirits of the dead.

73.	Meteion: “Heard the final testaments of the dying. Welcomed their shadowed hearts into our own.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion hears the last will from those who are dying and they welcome the emotions into their own consciousness.
74.	Meteion: “One race had striven to create a world bereft of animosity.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion adds that one race strives to create a world without hostility.
75.	Meteion: “They renounced relationships to avoid interpersonal strife, and in so doing brought about societal collapse.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion talks about a society that give up on relationships to avoid conflict, which ended up being the downfall of that society.
76.	Meteion: “One race had renounced war and devoted itself to the enrichment of its people.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion continues that one race abandons war and devotes itself to enriching its people.
77.	Meteion: “They were conquered. Though they destroyed the enemy in reprisal, they could not regain their former glory.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Sadly, the race that Meteion mentions in the previous quotation is defeated. Although they destroyed the enemy in revenge, they could not regain their former glory.
78.	Meteion: “One race had concluded that finite time was the root of all woes. Aspiring to shatter its shackles, they went in search of infinity.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion continues to explain that another race searches the infinity because they think that limited time was the cause of all issues.
79.	Meteion: “They discovered nothing is infinite, and that neither time or death can be cheated. Disillusioned, they	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion continues, that the race in the previous quotation finds nothing about infinity, nor is infinity real. And also,

	gave up on the future—and themselves.”		that time or death can be manipulated. In the end they give up on themselves and their future.
80.	Meteion: “One race had discarded all things that gave rise to sorrow, hoping to have only joy.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion explains that there is another race that throws away all the things in their lives that cause sadness and hopes to only experience happiness.
81.	Meteion: “They found joy lost its savor in the absence of sorrow, and lost their will to live.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion adds that race in the previous quotation that they find that joy loses its meaning in the absence of sorrow, which makes them lose the will to live.
82.	Meteion: “Though worlds apart, these people shared a belief. The belief that they had tried their best.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion finds many civilizations that fall apart or perish in various ways. He comes to the conclusion that these civilizations, although different, all believe that they have done their best during their lifetime.
83.	Meteion: “That they had tried to fulfill their potential, with every step and success.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion notes that all of these beings in other stars believe they have done their best and are working toward their full potential with each step they take.
84.	Meteion: “That they would never be free of fear and sorrow, anger and despair—of loneliness—so long as they yet lived.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion continues, despite their efforts to overcome difficulties and find meaning in their lives, these civilizations eventually faced despair and extinction, understanding that negative feelings like fear, sorrow, rage, and loneliness are an unavoidable part of life.
85.	Meteion: “Even now, their souls cry out for oblivion. And to this song of anguish, I lend my voice. We lend our voice.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion and her sisters’ song of oblivion can bring the final day to the star they aim. Meteion and her sisters lend their voice to bring the final day to those souls who wants it.

86.	Meteion: “O beloved mankind, shimmering jewels of beautiful Etheirys... Rejoice, for we will free you from the cruel yoke of existence.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion wants to sing the song of oblivion to the Etheirys people, because she believes that she can free the people from the pain of existence.
87.	Meteion: “There is no need to struggle in vain, for in nihility awaits salvation. You will know peace and serenity...and it will be beautiful.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion says that the living beings in Etheirys do not have to suffer in their life and death is beautiful because they will know peace and serenity.
88.	Meteion: “We will make our nest at the edge of the universe, and there in the dark of dead worlds hoard sorrow and suffering.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion reveals to the player that their nest will be at the edge of the universe, which is almost impossible to get there. That star is a dark dead worlds hoard sorrow and suffering.
89.	Meteion: “There we will sing, our chorus ever louder and ever clearer, that our song may reach even this aether-shrouded star.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion plans to sing the song of oblivion with her sisters in the star she mentions in the previous quotation, which locates in the edge of the universe.
90.	Meteion: “Such is the answer we have found in the stars. Such is the gift we now offer to Etheirys.”	Caging the Messenger (Level 87)	Meteion’s sisters gets the answer they find in another stars, which is there is no meaning in life because all civilizations are destroyed. Then, Meteion offers to give the destruction to Etheirys.
91.	Meteion: “Why have you come? All you had to do was wait. I would’ve delivered to you your ends.”	Unto the Heavens (Level 89)	Meteion tells the player and his/her companions they should have not come to find Meteion because she will deliver the final day into Etheirys with the song of oblivion.

92.	Meteion: “I don’t understand. All life is destined to end.”	Unto the Heavens (Level 89)	Meteion do not understand why the player and his/her companions tries to stop her because she knows that all life is destined to end.
93.	Meteion: “Why choose to prolong your suffering?”	Unto the Heavens (Level 89)	Meteion questions the player why he/she want to stop her song of oblivion and to suffer in the meaningless existence.
94.	Meteion: “Effort, ambition, love—they amount to naught. Happiness, should you find it, is inevitably lost. Stolen away by events beyond your control.”	Unto the Heavens (Level 89)	Meteion explains that effort, ambition, and love are meaningless. Meanwhile happiness is easily stolen by the events/problems beyond human control.
95.	Meteion: “There is no logic nor meaning in it. You think there is, convince yourselves, but it’s all a cruel accident.”	Unto the Heavens (Level 89)	Meteion expresses her belief that existence is a tragic accident, lacking logic or meaning in it.
96.	Meteion: “Come now, I speak the truth. A truth you would recognize if you looked up at the night sky.”	Unto the Heavens (Level 89)	Meteion ask the player to realize the truth that she is speaking about, in which her viewpoint in the previous dialog can be seen if one were to look up at the empty night sky is a reflection of the basic meaninglessness of existence.
97.	Meteion: “Unbroken emptiness. Cold, dark, and silent. Your world, like every other, is but a blemish upon its perfect fabric.”	Unto the Heavens (Level 89)	Meteion implies that the unbroken emptiness of the night sky, which is cold, dark, and silent, is a reflection of the basic meaninglessness of existence.

98.	Meteion: “Life is an anomaly. It is unnatural and cannot continue. The sooner you accept this, the easier it will be.”	Unto the Heavens (Level 89)	Meteion states that the world is a place of suffering, where joy is temporary and sorrow is constant. This emphasizes her belief in the futility and meaninglessness of existence, which she believes cannot be overstated.
99.	Meteion: “I know it well. For the same passion once burned in many a star before yours.”	Unto the Heavens (Level 89)	Meteion knows the feeling and emotions of the player because her sisters sense the same feelings once exist in many other stars that long gone before the player’s star.
100.	Meteion: “Suffocated and extinguished now.”	Unto the Heavens (Level 89)	Meteion continues the previous dialog that the civilization she means is already gone because of many calamities and hardships those civilization faces.
101.	Meteion: “You approach the bounds of my Ultimatum, where emotions dictate reality.”	Unto the Heavens (Level 89)	Meteion tells the player that he/she reaches her ultimatum which is her nest, where she mentions in the previous dialog that it is located in the edge of universe. Her ultimatum is a place where emotions dictate reality.
102.	Meteion: “Where resignation and acceptance unite to embrace the end.”	Unto the Heavens (Level 89)	Meteion adds, her nest is a place where resignation and acceptance come together to embrace the end.
103.	Meteion: “Where those who yet valiantly cling to life cannot thrive...”	Unto the Heavens (Level 89)	Meteion continues, where even the toughest people, who are hanging on to life by the threads, cannot get ahead or grow. It refers to a tough or unfriendly environment that makes it hard to grow and stay alive, even when people are trying hard.
104.	Meteion: “This is how I found it when I arrived. Another star which once pulsed with life, but no longer.”	Forge Ahead (Level 90)	Meteion states her reason how she finds this star located in the edge of universe. Which once fills with life but the civilization is no longer there.

105.	Meteion: “How it ended, I do not know. Invasion, sickness, suicide—none can say.”	Forge Ahead (Level 90)	Meteion continues her explanation that she does not know the reason why there is no more civilization. None can tell if it is because of invasion, sickness, or suicide.
106.	Meteion: “None lived to speak for the dead. They are gone. Gone. Search all you like, but you’ll only end up turning back.”	Forge Ahead (Level 90)	Meteion says that the civilization is gone and none left to speak up on what happened in their star. Meteion tells the player to search every place or area in the star but the player will not find any clue.
107.	Meteion: “You think you’ve caught me? This form is barely a drop from the ocean that swells within the dead sun.”	Forge Ahead (Level 90)	Meteion tells the player that she is not caught by the player because Meteion’s current form is just a small part of a bigger and more powerful entity that resides a “dead sun.”
108.	Meteion: “Even so, I could easily unmake you. You are only still alive because of your comrades. But they cannot protect you forever.”	Forge Ahead (Level 90)	Meteion is talking to the player who is still alive because his/her friends who protects him/her, but the player need to be careful, because their support will not last forever.
109.	Meteion: “Until they fade away, I’ll satisfy myself with watching you try—and fail—to find a way out of this lifeless place.”	Forge Ahead (Level 90)	Meteion tells the player, until the player’s comrades die, Meteion will satisfy herself by watching the player suffer.
110.	Meteion: “Here the path ends. There is no way to reach our nest.”	You’re Not Alone (Level 90)	Meteion tells the player and his/her comrades that they cannot go further to Meteion’s nest, in purpose of stopping the final day.

111.	Meteion: “I told you. Resignation and acceptance reign in this place.”	You’re Not Alone (Level 90)	Meteion continues that in their current place which is the star in the edge of universe, the civilization gives up and accepts their fate.
112.	Meteion: “The rejection of life by those who came to curse it.”	You’re Not Alone (Level 90)	Meteion refers to the civilization who grows to hate life and therefore reject it.
113.	Meteion: “Those whose dreams were unfulfilled. Whose prayers were unheard. Whose labors were unrewarded.”	You’re Not Alone (Level 90)	Meteion talks about the people who experiences disappointment because there is no answer for their prayer, their dream is not come true, and their hard work does not pay off.
114.	Meteion: “Hope cannot deliver you unto hopelessness. Our refuge is beyond you.”	You’re Not Alone (Level 90)	Meteion states that hope cannot deliver the player and his/her comrades into despair, and Meteion’s nest is beyond of reach.
115.	Meteion: “Struggle will avail you naught, nor will it grant your comrades peace.”	You’re Not Alone (Level 90)	Meteion declares that struggle will not help the player and bring his/her comrades’ peace.
116.	Meteion: “Come, let me relieve you of your burden. You have suffered enough.”	You’re Not Alone (Level 90)	Meteion offers the player to take away his/her troubles, acknowledging that the player suffers a lot.
117.	The Endsinger: “Ahhh, the rage... It rises... Rises...”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion and her sister merges, becoming a monster which is The Endsinger. The Endsinger shows an increasingly high level of rage.

118.	The Endsinger: “We die in pain. We die in suffering! Who are you to live? Who are you to hope!?”	Endwalker (Level 90)	The Endsinger questions the player’s right to live and have hope, while The Endsinger states that the other beings die in pain and suffer.
119.	The Endsinger: “We will not suffer alone...”	Endwalker (Level 90)	The Endsinger tells the player that she is not going to suffer alone and intends to inflict pain on others.
120.	The Endsinger: “All will know our pain...You will be battered and torn and made to crawl.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	The Endsinger suffers great pain and believes that others should experiences similar pain. The Endsinger threaten the player that he/she will go through the same pain as The Endsinger.
121.	The Endsinger: “You will weep and wail and curse your impotence. Curse your life as it fades.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	The Endsinger says that the player will feel sorrow and helplessness, and that hhe/she will eventually curse their own helplessness and the end of their life. Because The Endsinger thinks that all humans will suffer and lose hope.
122.	The Endsinger: “As we did! As we died!”	Endwalker (Level 90)	The Endsinger conveys the feelings of suffer and hopeless from the previous dialogue, and continues with her experiences with death.
123.	The Endsinger: “Such pain and sorrow we felt... Such anguish and rage... We tried. We tried. But it was no use...”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Endsinger shows a deep loss and hopelessness. The Endsinger, a being that represents the hopelessness of many souls, is talking about their experience of intense suffering and how pointless their attempts to end it. This makes them feel like giving up.

124.	The Endsinger: “Only when we surrendered did we find release. Only when we embraced death.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	The Endsinger explains that opposing or being afraid of death can cause pain, while accepting it can bring peace.
125.	The Endsinger: “So join us in despair...and embrace yours!”	Endwalker (Level 90)	The Endsinger demands others to join her in sorrow and embrace their own deaths.
126.	The Endsinger: “You struggle in vain. You will not silence our song of oblivion!”	Endwalker (Level 90)	The Endsinger says that trying to fight back or stop them is pointless. They also say they are determined to keep up their “song of oblivion,” which mean to bring the final day.

Table 6. The Effects of Nihilism on Meteion’s dialogues and her conversation with Hermes as her creator, and other characters in *Final Fantasy XIV: Endwalker*

Data Number	Quotation	Quests and Levels	Analysis
127.	Meteion: “Can you...hear me...?”	You’re Not Alone (Level 90)	Meteion asks the player if he/she can hear Meteion’s voice.
128.	Meteion: “The voices within... Crying in pain, wailing in sorrow... Hurting... Hurting...”	You’re Not Alone (Level 90)	Meteion wants to know if she is being heard in the previous quotation and says that the voices inside her are hurt and sad.
129.	Meteion: “End it...silence it... Silence our song of oblivion!”	You’re Not Alone (Level 90)	“Song of oblivion” is what Meteion calls the pain she sees and how she wants to end it. That song is mean to bring the final day to the star or civilization.

130.	Meteion: “That you still stand... Your determination defies all reason.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion praises the player’s strength and expresses surprise at how determined he/she is.
131.	Meteion: “The souls within me writhe and recoil in your presence...”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion talks about how the souls inside her reacted negatively to the player being there. Perhaps because of the player’s strength and will to live.
132.	Meteion: “What must I do? What pain must I visit upon you to make you surrender to despair?”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion thinks of what she needs to do to make the player give up and surrender to depression.
133.	Alisaie: “No one is unbreakable. What pains one may weather may bring another to tears.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Alisaie, one of the player’s comrades acknowledges that everyone’s pain level is different. The pain of one person experiences can make another person cry or feel hurt.
134.	Alisaie: “But therein lies our strength, for when we fall, our brothers and sisters are there to raise us up. Again and again. Without end.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Alisaie continues that their strength is coming from those experiences. Even when someone falls, they will be picked up by their comrades and cycle continues indefinitely.
135.	Meteion: “I see...”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion acknowledges Alisaie’s words about experiences and comrades who will help and understand each other.
136.	Meteion: “But no matter how much hope exists, ever will there be more despair.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion adds, no matter how much hope there is, hopelessness or despair will always be there.

137.	Meteion: “Ever will the living curse the present and lament the future.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion says that living things will always be unhappy with their current situation and afraid of what the future holds.
138.	Meteion: “So shall we sing until life ceases to be.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion states that she will keep singing her song of oblivion and bring the final day until there is no more life.
139.	(Player killed The Endsinger) Meteion: “No matter where we flew, there was only darkness and loneliness and pain.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	After the player and his/her companions killed the Endsinger, Meteion comes back in her usual form. She tells the player that no matter where she and her sisters flies to other stars, they only find darkness, loneliness, and pain from those stars.
140.	Meteion: “We couldn’t find the answers Hermes yearned for. The answers he deserved.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion feels sad because she and her sisters could not find the meaning of life which Hermes tasks them to find.
141.	Meteion: “Greetings... You who are my final encounter...”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion, upon defeated by the player and his/her comrades, greets the player as her final encounter.
142.	Meteion: “I wish to hear your words... Share your feelings... Know your thoughts.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion wishes to hear the player’s words, share the player’s feelings, and know the player’s thoughts.
143.	Meteion: “Yes, I can see them... The memories of a long, long journey...”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion sees the player’s memories, which are the memories of a long journey.
144.	Meteion: “So many people... The thoughts of them overflowing in your heart...”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion expresses being overwhelmed by the thoughts and emotions of many people from the player’s memories, and it fills the player’s heart.

145.	Meteion: “What they live for, what gives their lives meaning... There was never a single answer.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion says that different people have very different ideas about what gives life value. There is no one solution that fits all people because everyone has their own experiences, values, and points of view that shape how they see what gives their life purpose and meaning.
146.	Meteion: “You gather pieces of happiness, precious and fragile, only to lose them. Then start again.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion understands that the player gathers pieces of happiness that is precious and fragile from his/her journey, but end up losing them. But then the player starts to gather those pieces again.
147.	Meteion: “On and on it goes, until death takes you into its gentle embrace.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion continues her previous dialog that the player’s experiences keep going until death takes them which the people in the player’s memories into its gentle embrace.
148.	Meteion: “That which Hermes sent us to find...was there all this time. On Etheirys.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion understands that the answer where Hermes seek and task Meteion’s sisters to travel across the universe, is actually in Etheirys.
149.	Player: “We created it together.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Player tells Meteion that the meaning of life in Etheirys is because the people in Etheirys created it together.
150.	Meteion: “Like a field of flowers, perhaps. At first a single blossom, it spreads and takes on more colors.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion says that the growth of understanding or happiness which can be understand as the meaning of life, is like a field of flowers that starts with one and grows into a wide range of bright colors.
151.	Meteion: “Thank you for guiding me here. To find these words at journey’s end fills me with joy.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion expresses gratitude to the player for directing her to a discovery that brings her happiness at the end of her journey.

152.	Meteion: “And so, before I fall forever silent, there is one thing I must do.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion informs the player that she has one more thing to do before she is no longer able to live or communicate.
153.	Meteion: “No expression of regret will undo what my sisters and I have done. Will restore what we have stolen.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion recognizes that no amount of regret can erase the past or return what she and her sisters takes.
154.	Meteion: “But if you would allow it, I would sing one last song. A song of the newfound joy that swells in my heart...”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion requests permission to the player to perform one final act, singing a song that represents the joy she now feels.
155.	Meteion: “Of the beauty of light when it shines across a dark and starless sea...”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion wishes to sing about the beauty which can appear even in the worst and most lonely places.
156.	Meteion: “Of a dream that from the soil of worlds now lost to sorrow, life will spring forth once more...”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion portrays a future in which life develops from environments that were once sorrowful.
157.	Meteion: “...Nourished by gentle rains and caressed by uplifting winds. A song of hope.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion’s song is one of hope, representing life being nurtured and maintained by the natural factors.
158.	Meteion: “One day, life will fill the universe again. And Hermes will see this and smile.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion expresses hope that life will eventually spread to every part of the universe, which will bring happiness to Hermes.

159.	Meteion: “How, I do not know. But I do know that, where there is a will, there is a way.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion says she does not know how this future will come about, but she is sure that people who believe in it will find a way to make it happen.
160.	Meteion: “After all, miracles happen every day, do they not?”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion says that miracles happen all the time, which means that the bright future she dreams of is possible.
161.	Meteion: “Hold in your heart your desire to return to them, then follow my lead and walk forth.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion tells the player to remember his/her desire to be with their loved ones or comrades again and to follow her advice to move forward.
162.	Meteion: “That hope will surely guide you true.”	Endwalker (Level 90)	Meteion affirms that she is sure that hope will lead the player in the right way.